

**DRIVING SUSTAINABILITY:
PROPOSED BUSINESS MODEL FOR SMEs IN THE COSMETIC
INDUSTRY**

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ABSTRACT

The cosmetic industry is rapidly growing, and everyday consumers are becoming more aware of climate change and its effect on planet earth. With the fashion industry coming up with initiatives like #Imadeyourclothes, cosmetic companies need to step up and answer the consumers about sustainability and transparency in the beauty industry. The researcher wants to look at the SMEs in the beauty industry, their sustainability policies and the business models they use. In 2015, since the launch of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, the larger cosmetic companies had already been a part of the change towards sustainability. But there hasn't been much done in the cosmetic industry in the research area regarding the business models they use and how they opt for more sustainable business approach.

The study has been performed using in-depth interviews and thematic analysis for examining the data. The study of Sustainability Reports of large cosmetic businesses incorporates the Triple Bottom Line (TBL), which collaborates the business's environmental, social and economic aspects for enhanced quality of living.

Nevertheless, to implement these aspects, there is a need for innovation in the cosmetic industry concerning packaging, ingredients and transparency in the supply chain. It aimed to look at those that have successfully overcome the challenges. It seems necessary at this point to include innovation as a part of the business model to initiate sustainability across the supply chain and aim for an overall balanced outlook. The researcher's primary goal is to identify a business model that SMEs can use to be sustainable in the beauty industry and be circular in their waste management. While the business model may not have been tried and tested on a large scale, this could be the focus of the subsequent study.

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TERMINIOLOGY

Carbon Emission: Emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and greenhouse gases are produced by burning fossil fuels. The primary sources of which are electricity and heat, transportation and manufacturing.

Sustainability: Sustainability means meeting our own needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

Business model: A business model should answer important questions about the business and set out a strong vision for the business. The key components of a business model should include target customers, the market, organization strengths and challenges, product, and marketing.

Circular Economy: A circular economy decouples economic activity from the consumption of finite resources. It is a resilient system that is good for business, people and the environment. The circular economy is a systems solution framework that tackles global challenges like climate change, biodiversity loss, waste, and pollution.

Carbon Neutral: Carbon neutrality means having a balance between emitting carbon and absorbing carbon from the atmosphere in carbon sinks.

Triple Bottom Line: The TBL is an accounting framework that incorporates three dimensions of performance: social, environmental and financial.

Life Cycle Thinking: Life cycle thinking (LCT) is defined as the way of thinking that includes the economic, environmental, and social consequences of a product or process throughout its life.

Circularity: Circularity is a simple concept. It means that a product is created with its own end-of-life taken into account. In a circular economy, once the user is finished with the product, it goes back into the supply chain instead of the landfill. The motto of the circularity movement, in a nutshell: Waste not, want not.

Upcycle Products: The act of taking something no longer in use and giving it a second life and new function

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

Sustainable businesses have turned out to be the leading way according to which the country gains better future opportunities in economic, social, and environmental contexts. Becoming “carbon neutral” or implementing social standards for both the employees and along the entire supply chains, companies make a clear signal to the stakeholders that optimization of the resource use or the decrease of the pollutants/waste is not only economically profitable but also their chief business goal (Cervellon and Carey, 2011). Moreover, it involves reducing pollutants or waste, which is not just economically cost-effective but even has become a core agenda of the businesses (Azad et al., 2016). Therefore, the organizations working on their sustainability concepts ensure that these issues are well understood and are acted on. The companies are working hard to be gentle with the planet Earth and handle it dutifully (Gardetti and Muthu, 2015). Thus, the organisations that are functioning on sustainability concepts make sure that the concerns regarding sustainability are implicit and represented effectively.

Personal care and cosmetics products have been established since thousands of years ago. These personal care and cosmetics products are being used daily by many people and the consumption of these products is increasing every year (Hashim and Mat Hashim, 2013). The global cosmetics market, already \$507.8 billion in 2018, is still growing, and is expected to reach \$758.4 billion in 2025 (Statista, 2021). There is an evident strong trend towards the use of sustainably produced raw materials in the cosmetics field, mainly as active ingredients in formulations (Barbulova, Colucci and Apone, 2015). Sustainably produced raw materials are being introduced into the cosmetics field not only as ingredients for cosmetics but also as components of the packaging materials. Indeed, cosmetics marketing stresses that the use of green, possibly compostable or biodegradable packaging is an added value to the cosmetics product, since it witnesses customers’ and producers’ environmental attitude and care (Vi, 2020). Accordingly, there are annual events such as the Sustainable Cosmetics Summit (2019), which promote the use of sustainably produced raw materials in the cosmetics field. Even big

companies are tracing and measuring the sustainability of the ingredients used in their cosmetics. In addition, many cosmetics companies are spreading marketing messages on the use of sustainable and responsible packaging for their products.

SMEs refer to the key stakeholders who significantly contribute to the economic activities worldwide, social well-being, and environmental footprint. SMEs are the drivers of innovation and economic growth in the cosmetic industry. Evidently, Europe is the largest cosmetic market in the world making EUR €76.7 billion at retail sales prices (The UK and the European Market, 2021). There are small and medium-sized enterprises in the area of cosmetics that distribute and manufacture cosmetic products. However, statistical analysis of 2019 shows that the number of SMEs in the cosmetics manufacturing industry increased in countries as reaching 814 in Europe, 652 in the UK, 607 in France, 582 in Spain, 531 in Poland 348 in Germany (Riddler, 2021). It shows that it is a significant engine for the value creation of the economies. Therefore, SMEs play a significant role in the development of the economy of a country. The industry places a solid accentuation on guaranteeing social and environmental obligations by supporting proactive, deliberate and self-regulatory activities. Also, taking into note social sustainability, European cosmetic market gender ratio shows 65% women to 35% men being employed (The UK and the European Market, 2021).

The cosmetic industry has been thriving over the years because of its significance in enhancing appearance. As a cosmetic aid, makeup builds up the confidence and self-esteem of an individual. Consequently, in looking presentable and attractive, the use of cosmetics seems inevitable in people of all ages. Even the fashion industry has seen the demand of Eco-fashion and are bringing new products to the market to regulate resource consumption and harmful ecological effects (Weller, 2017). People prefer to buy a cosmetic when it seems highly appealing due to its colours, shimmer, glossy look, and so forth (Sung, 2017). However, today, the trend is changing. Nowadays, people prefer to look beautiful through makeup and do not want to compromise on their skin. Therefore, they demand that the cosmetic they use must suit their skin colour and type and be environmentally sustainable (Khan et al., 2019). Notably, the unprecedented incidents during COVID-19 prompted many changes that changed the existing trends of cosmetics use. The use of skincare products was increased during pandemic

whereas, sale in other products of makeup has been declining (Gerstell, Marchessou, Schmidt and Spagnuolo, 2020). Businesses nowadays are more focused on sustainability, as being sustainable adds to the brand image and benefits in terms of other returns. Personal care and cosmetics products are used for many years (De Caterina, 2019). Many people use cosmetic products daily. The consumption of such products is growing day by day, so consumers want the best ingredients for their skin with the added benefit to nature.

It can be observed that living in a zero-waste lifestyle, most people are striving to decrease the amount of plastic they have been using daily, involving the products used for the skincare (Gardetti and Torres, 2017). It motivates them to reduce the negative impact on the environment as 2018 has witnessed an industry-wide ban based on microbeads (World leading microbeads ban comes into force, 2021). While plastic microbeads were as of late restricted in the UK from flush off items, they are as yet found in numerous other individual consideration items, for example, sun cream and beautifying agents (Biodegradable alternative to replace microplastics in cosmetics and toiletries, 2021). In the previous year, SMEs have tried to adopt waste reduction strategies in the cosmetic industry through eco-design in packaging (Sumrin et al., 2021). They have tried to use recycled plastic packaging along with reusable glass as well as metal containers. The idea is to encourage the consumers for purchasing the refills (Kotschwar, 2014). Moreover, in the conditions when the 100 per cent recycled packaging is not possible, SMEs have opted to lessen the amount of the virgin plastic which they use, choosing 50 per cent virgin whereas, 50 per cent recycled with initiatives of decreasing the amount of virgin plastic over the period (Shahin and Salem, 2014).

Sustainability in the cosmetic sector is not just limited to packaging but involves the overall production procedure from sourcing to creating the formula (Coelho, Corona, Klooster and Worrell, 2020). The reduction of the environmental impact made by the SMEs, both in the manufacturing and cosmetic services, is a core success factor with regards to greening the economy (Kabukuru and Afande, 2016). Improving environmental performance is even a substantial business opportunity for many SMEs themselves as significant suppliers of products and services. Though SMEs' disposition and competence for adopting sustainable practices and seizing the green business opportunities usually face some of the key challenges (Nicholls and

Kang, 2012). Most SMEs are even unaware of various financially attractive opportunities regarding environmental improvements (Gardetti and Muthu, 2015). There is an extensive misunderstanding that the protection of the environment is related to the practical complexity, burdens, and huge costs (Lyytimäki et al., 2012). Also, when SMEs are aware of the possible better environmental performance for improving competitiveness, there is a lack of proper skills and expertise that usually prevents the firms from going on with the win-win chances such as conflicts in management individuals, lack of experts in the critical area of improvement (Jeucken, 2010). Simultaneously, the absence of resources leads the SMEs towards risk-averse and reduced willingness to invest in new technologies (Álvarez Jaramillo et al., 2018).

Globally, considering the consumption of cosmetics products in the market, it is massive. Thus, the sector has reached \$460 billion in 2014 (KO and Kim, 2016) and is still proceeding and was predictable to reach \$675 billion in the last year 2020 (Marcinowski et al., 2020). Therefore, it shows that there has been a growth rate of 6.4 per cent every year (Baghel, 2020). Apart from this, an apparent robust trend is witnessed towards using the sustainably created raw materials in cosmetics, majorly as the active ingredients in terms of the formulations (Lourenço-Lopes et al., 2020). The raw material must be produced sustainably to be used in the cosmetics, not just in the form of the main ingredients for the cosmetics but also the components regarding its packaging (Bom, Ribeiro and Marto, 2020). Indeed, cosmetic marketing is quite stressful because the usage of 'Green', conceivably compostable, or decomposable packaging is a valuable addition to the cosmetics product (Orlandi et al., 2020). It is because it tends to witness the environmental attitude and the care regarding the customers and the producers.

Consequently, many annual events occur globally, like the Sustainable Cosmetics Summit, natural cosmetics masterclass: future directions (Paris, 2019), sustainable cosmetics summit (2019 North American pics) etc. These are arranged and promoted for enlightening the usage of sustainably made raw materials in the field of cosmetics (Lourenço-Lopes et al., 2021). The majority of the big companies are trying to trace and measure the sustainability of all the ingredients used in cosmetics products (Kalesaran, 2021). Furthermore, most cosmetics companies are trying to spread an awareness message as a marketing strategy on sustainable

and responsible packaging for cosmetic products (Kazakova and Lebedynets, 2020). In modern marketing, the term 'Green' has become synonymous with organic and healthy words (Cervellon and Carey, 2011). When consumers read green cosmetics, they automatically tend to make assumptions about the eco-friendly product (Gardetti and Muthu, 2015). Greenwashing is in every corner of the beauty industry, from supply chain to packaging and post-consumer use, the lack of transparency and initiative from everyone involved adds on to this problem (Sandler, 2020). Evidently, L'Oreal claims to be sustainable, but most of its products are not truly sustainable, and their source is also obscure. L'Oreal claims to be sustainable by 2030 but still 5% of its raw material will be derived from non-renewable resources (Pointing, 2021). Similarly, the marketing of Nestlé, which partly own L'Oreal, claims that the products meet the standards and objectives of sustainability, but reality does not project this with the issues of environmental and political issues in the company (Pointing, 2021; Naik, 2020).

"A lot of major global corporations have effectively outsourced their environmental impact to their supply chains," said Dexter Galvin, global director of corporations and supply chains at CDP, a nonprofit group that collects environmental data from companies. "It's a blind spot, which means that most of their carbon emissions, water use and impact on deforestation escape public scrutiny." - (Naik, 2020).

As per the cosmetics industry, green and sustainable cosmetics are cosmetic products that use natural ingredients produced from renewable raw materials (Azad et al., 2016). Most companies use petrochemical ingredients derived from petrol, a non-renewable and economically explosive resource (Danley, 2012). On the other hand, bio-based oleo chemicals derived from natural oils and fats are the core of the movement of green cosmetics as they are wonderful renewable raw materials (Abraham and Höfer, 2012). They are used as supplemental materials or raw materials in perfumes, cosmetics and shampoos. Nowadays, the green production of cosmetic products is trending as sustainable products.

1.2 Motivation

In accordance with the study of McCoy (2009), it is explained that there was a minor medical breakthrough because of the invention of John Ugelstad about micro beads. These micro beads can be treated as a healing substance for cancer, and they can also help with the research based on HIV. But these microbeads became environmental disaster due to failure to remove from wastewater and eventually ending up in ocean and causing harm to marine life.

The micro beads that are commonly used in personal care products can pose an environmental hazard for aquatic life by polluting water for being plastic in nature. In this wake, the United Kingdom banned the sale of products containing micro beads in 2018 because of their extent of generating plastic pollution in the marine environment. One shower is anticipated to send 100,000 micro beads down the drain that can cause serious harm to aquatic life (World leading micro beads ban comes into force, 2018). This initiative was taken in the wake of sustainable development that became a motivation to explore the concept of sustainability in the cosmetic industry.

In general, this era is highly globalised, and people have developed a better understanding of many things. One of them is the concept of sustainable businesses. The present world thrives on having sustainable products that may not affect their lifestyle and the environment. The global environmental issues, including deforestation, global warming, palm cultivation, and water scarcity, have turned this concept under the spotlight, so entities seem more concerned with this. Thus, it has become one of the most general topics in the present time (Sung, 2017).

Following this, the cosmetic industry has been flourishing over the years because of the increasing attention, as individuals are more concerned with their looks. However, being more aware and conscious, people are now more interested in environmentally friendly products (Weller, 2017). The raw material used in it is not harmful to their skin (Khan et al., 2019). At the height of awareness, people first tend to read the product's ingredients and then buy it (De Caterina, 2019). The cosmetic industries are using these microbeads as an ingredient in cosmetic products like face scrubs, body washes, and toothpastes, which have a catastrophic influence on the natural world. Verily, the world has changed, and this change is appreciable.

Being environmentally dutiful is the responsibility of every citizen (Gardetti and Torres, 2017). The cosmetic industry is famous for being such raw material or packaging that is not environmentally friendly (Shahin and Salem, 2014). The companies who tend to use green cosmetics portray that it is pretty expensive and not affordable by all (Gardetti and Torres, 2017). Due to which green production often requires a high investment that is compensated with the purchase price of products. Nevertheless, this is essential to mention that increasing work and research on sustainable development will change the patterns.

SMEs are the strugglers in the market who initially must make all the possible efforts to sustain themselves in the market (Kotschwar, 2014). SMEs are adopting a variety of sustainability practices that can help them to keep the business in profit. SMEs who connect with the cosmetic industry tend to face pressure to make money and impress the public (Shahin and Salem, 2014). Today, the customers' priority is to have green products that are sustainable and not harmful at any level (Coelho, Corona, Klooster and Worrell, 2020). SMEs require a proper plan and budget to meet the expectation level of the customers (Kabukuru and Afande, 2016). SMEs should draw the proper strategic planning in order to improve their sustainability by utilising the benefit of gaining customer satisfaction. A proper monetary plan should be used to spend on green products that have no harmful side effects, damaging the customer fidelity and their expectation with the product.

In order to implement sustainable development in organisations, specific goals and policies are formulated to achieve it. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) tend to illustrate how the policymakers, the public, and the private business have focused on the sustainability of the products (Despaux, 2020). Moreover, The U.N. itself has listed above 4000 deliberate commitments and multi-stakeholder partnerships that explicitly are related to the 17 goals (Reinsons, 2020). It shows that the overall world is focusing on this matter and trying to do sustainable businesses. Similarly, the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) illustrate, how much the attention of policy maker, the public, and private business has shifted towards sustainability considerations (Economist, 2015; Lagarde, 2018).

“The seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are our shared vision of humanity and a social contract between the world’s leaders and the people”

- UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon

Figure 1: The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals

Source: The 17 Goals Sustainable Development

Corporate sustainability begins with a company’s esteem framework and a principles-based approach to doing trade. This implies working in ways that, at a least, meet principal obligations within the regions of human rights, work, environment and anti-corruption. Mindful businesses sanction the same values and standards wherever they have a nearness and know that great practices in one zone don't counterbalanced hurt in another. The Ten Standards of the UN Worldwide Compact into procedures, approaches and methods, and building up a culture of keenness, companies are not as it were maintaining their fundamental duties to

individuals and planet, but moreover setting the arrange for long-term victory (The Ten Principles | UN Global Compact, 2021).

Figure 2: Ten Principles of the UN Global Compact

Source: UN Global Compact

Many cosmetic brands are trying to adopt a better, more eco-based approach to not just their products but even their manufacturing (Nicholls and Kang, 2012). It is appreciable and even enjoyable to explore. Individually, people are trying to raise their concerns against using cosmetic products that are not sustainable. Also, research has been done on halal cosmetics that are ethical and environmentally friendly (Ali, Halim and Ahmad, 2016). There is in-depth information related to this topic that is not limited to one context but many. SMEs are publicising their products through social media marketing (Michaels, 2015). Vloggers have a

central role in this regard (Michaels, 2015). All these aspects are needed to be explored as it is interesting to know how the cosmetic industry might change with sustainable measures.

Apart from this, the tactical significance regarding the business model innovation is supplemented by high failure rates (Lessing, 2010). While the proof is intermittent, failure rates concerning the new ventures might be higher than 90 per cent (Ishak and Adithya, 2020). The reasons with regards to such industrial problems tend to remain comparatively unexplored in the secondary data. This research aims to address this research gap by identifying the factors that tend to challenge the sustainable business model in the cosmetic sector. Moreover, it is even based on an analysis of the likely instruments and mechanisms for reacting to the changing boundaries that tend to make the business models resistant to the changes in the context of environmental, social, and economic domains.

1.3 Industrial problem

In the current years, sustainability with regards to the cosmetics industry has got a growing interest from the side of the consumers, cosmetics companies, and organisations, along with the academics from many disciplinary fields. There has been an escalating concern over the safety of cosmetics (Michaels, 2015). Moreover, the environmental impacts due to cosmetic production, like deforestation, water pollution, soil pollution, and eventually air pollution, need to be considered (Ishak and Adithya, 2020). The reason behind this is the toxic and harmful chemicals and plastic used in manufacturing that end up in either landfills or water bodies, posing severe threats to aquatic life (Gatt,2020). Moreover, carbon emissions cause air pollution following global warming. Some of the waste is not even recyclable that becomes more endangering to the environment. Apart from this, the social impacts resulting from the partial trade have exaggerated the attention on this topic. The environment is affecting because of these waste materials of cosmetic products severely. The sea water and sea creatures are getting the worst impact because of this material, polluting nature and the environment. Based on the study done by LI, Tse, and Fok (2016), it is clear that plastic and waste pollution directly and a deadly impact on wildlife and marine creatures. Every year after

the consumption of plastic or other waste material thrown up in the environment causes thousands of killing of seabirds, sea turtles and other marine animals.

Sustainability refers to a term that tends to have various definitions as well as interpretations. However, the extensively acknowledged explanation rises from the report, namely, *Our Common Future*, published in 1987 (Macias et al., 2017). The concept of sustainability is concerned with Sustainable Development, which is the development that tends to meet the people's present needs while not compromising on future generations for meeting their individual needs (Carvalho, Estevinho and Santos, 2016). Sustainable development is a very carefully planned strategy to embrace the development while utilising the resources more efficiently, also taking into the immediate and the long-term benefits or advantages for the earth and the people that inhabit it. Different aspects can be used to gain sustainable development such as; economic growth, environmental protection, and social inclusion, which is also supported by using the study of Elliott (2012).

One of the key documents regarding the sustainable development movement is Agenda 21 by United Nations in 1992. It had pointed out the unsustainable production as well as the consumption standards as the significant reasons with regards to the environmental degradation. Well ahead, in the year 1994, Elkington had switched to the triple bottom line with regards to sustainability. The focus was on adapting this concept in the business sector, with the integration of the environmental and social dimensions needed for the Development of a global economy that must have sustenance.

The cosmetic industry is an excellent source of economic development across the world. Looking at the European cosmetic market, it is pretty clear that this science determined, fast-paced as well as remarkably innovative sector that has a strong focus on the improvement of the environment and social sustainability of the cosmetic industry (Macias et al., 2017).

For the sustainable business model of innovation, some of the key challenges identified for this study are listed below.

Table 1 Key Challenges in Sustainable Business Model Innovation

Key Challenges	Explanation	Contributing Authors
Triple Bottom Line	Triple Bottom Line (TBL) is a business concept that is the co-relation of people, planet, prosperity, and the balance among these variables is challenging for the business to sustain their business model. According to Deegan et al. (2006), most organisations face the critical challenge of measuring the social and environmental bottom lines. It is a fact that balance among these three variables is challenging for the sustainable business model.	Michaels (2015)
Thinking	To sustainable development of the business model innovation, different business metrics can persuade the thinking process of the business for the introduction of the new business model. These metrics may be business rules and regulations, operations and the guideline they imposed in their business. To enhancing these factors, businesses can implement a practical innovation sustainable business model.	Ishak and Adithya (2020)
Resource Utilisation	There is a bit of reluctance towards allocating the available resources to implement an innovative business model. Moreover, the reconfiguration of the resources and the procedure for a better new business model require human, monetary, and physical capital.	Lessing (2010)
Technological innovation	With the multidimensional technology innovation, most of the businesses create clean technology, as per which the business model innovation turns out to be complicated and multidimensional—the integration of sustainability and technological innovation to create effective technology for an effective, innovative business model.	Macias et al. (2017)
External associations	It requires extra efforts to engage the broad interaction with the external stakeholders and the overall business environment. By this development, the business environment requires extra efforts.	Carvalho et al. (2016)
Means of business modelling	It is a fact that the present methods with regards to business modelling are scarce and hardly sustainability determined. These challenges also enhance productivity and innovative business model.	Bianco et al. (2011)

1.4 Research gap

The analysis of (D'Amato et al., 2020) shows that consumers these days are aware of the operations and applications of sustainability that can be effective for the environment and contribute to corporate social responsibility. The cosmetic industry is one of the largest industries comprised of different products and services that consumers use, as referred to in the study of (Gregurec et al., 2021). On the other hand, (Deborah et al., 2017) has also argued that despite being one of the largest industries worldwide, there is limited research on sustainability in the cosmetic industry. According to Szromek (2021), the leading role of the cosmetics industry is to ensure the beautification of people and provide sustainable products which are not harmful to the environment. However, according to (Joyce, 2019) the chemicals which are used in cosmetics are severely harmful and contain high-risk exposure to health-related severe problems.

The use of toxic chemicals such as carcinogens, Formaldehyde, and other chemicals is very harmful to the environment and people's health (Phornlaphatrachakorn et al., 2020). Therefore, the cosmetics industries must utilise bio-based chemicals that do not harm the skin and health of the users and can also be sustainable for the environment (D'Amato et al., 2020). One of the significant gaps found in the current literature is that a small investigation was carried out to use bio-based chemicals to ensure sustainability in the companies and the environment. Similarly, the organisations producing such cosmetics also need to improvise their operations and some measures to produce renewable resources and restrict harmful chemicals from cosmetics products (Min et al., 2021). This verifies the fact that with the innovation in the biochemical sector benefits the product sustainability, there is less research based on the business dimension of the cosmetic industry. According to (Phornlaphatrachakorn et al., 2020) and (Motilewa et al., 2017), various business models are used to initiate sustainability. These business models are designed and implemented to introduce sustainable measures in production and utilise the safest methods for the consumers and the environment.

Figure 3: The SBM concept and its subcategories, for example, circular business models

Source: Geissdoerfer et al., 2018

Figure 1 demonstrates the sustainable business model in which the organisations provide the possible solutions for initiating sustainability. The research was performed with an amalgamation of various representative from sectors of manufacturing, apparel, food, consulting and clothing but there was gap in the outlook towards the cosmetic market.

According to the study of (Hernita et al., 2021), the overlapping circle model is used by most organisations for initiating sustainability. However, the application and usage of this model are not widely investigated in the cosmetic industry, which creates gaps in the literature. According to (Gregurec et al., 2021), the organisation must address the issues regarding sustainability. On the other hand, Hernita et al. (2021) assessed the need to implement sustainability in the companies. It is needed to have the proper implementation of the triple bottom line. The triple bottom line is the conceptual framework of accounting, consisting of social, environmental, and financial variables.

As the nature of the cosmetic product is mostly science based, the research related to cosmetic industry is predominantly based on biochemistry, chemical engineering, toxicology and so on. Looking at a simple search result of 'cosmetic' from Science Direct presents 163,298 results for year 2000-2021, but on adding a simple term 'business' to the search criteria reduces the results to 12,242 results. The shows a massive gap in the research related to cosmetic businesses, hence the motivation to the researcher to go forward with the study. Also, there

have been studies based on Business Model Innovation and Sustainable Business Model but only handful are directed towards the cosmetic industry. Similarly, looking at the search results of 'business model' from science direct presents 445,840 results for the year 2000 to 2021, and upon adding 'cosmetic' as the keyword reduces the search result to 379 results. The research done by Donato (2021) centres the attention to words the environmental sustainability off the major players of the cosmetic industry. It integrates circular economy and corporate social responsibility dimensions to assess this step towards sustainability taken by MNC's. The research clearly states the gap towards approaching circularity and corporate social responsibility in the smaller companies off the cosmetic industry. Therefore, this research addresses the issues related to implementing sustainability practices in the cosmetic industry by approaching innovation in the business model.

1.5 Research aim and objectives

According to (Gregurec et al., 2021), there are various kinds of issues present in the cosmetic industry about implementing green processes to ensure sustainability in various operations. Therefore, this research aims to assess the processes that can be used in the cosmetic industry to ensure sustainability and effectively introduce sustainable measures for production. Furthermore, as referred to in the study of (Hernita et al., 2021), businesses need to implement sustainability practices that can enhance the quality of operations and bring about a positive change in the environment. As mentioned in the research gap, there is a need to reflect at the business practises of smaller companies specifically in the cosmetic industry. Businesses must take some measures to mitigate the issues regarding sustainability in the companies. Therefore, the objectives of the research are:

- To identify the challenges that SMEs face in the cosmetic industry regarding sustainability and the challenges that SMEs face from product to supply chain.
- To find SMEs outlook towards environmental, social, and economic sustainability measuring triple bottom line.

- To identify measures the cosmetic industry takes to find and cater to the challenges regarding sustainability through a proposed sustainable business model.

1.6 Research questions

The main question of the research is;

What could be the Business model for SMEs in the cosmetic industry, and how can it be a part of sustainable practice?

Moreover, the sub-questions are;

- What are the challenges that SMEs in the cosmetic industry face from product to supply chain?
- What does economic, social, and environmental sustainability mean to SMEs in the cosmetic industry?
- How can these challenges be faced while integrating sustainable practices in the business model?

1.7 Research Significance

Sustainable businesses are leading the way to a better future in an economic, social and environmental sense. Becoming “carbon neutral” or implementing social standards for both the employees and along the entire supply chains, companies make a clear signal to the stakeholders that optimization of the resource use or the decrease of the pollutants/waste is not only economically profitable, but also is on agenda of their business in regard to the gentle handling of the planet Earth. Therefore, the organizations working on their sustainability concepts ensure that the sustainability issues are well understood and are acted on. In recent years, sustainability on the cosmetics industry has received growing interest from consumers, cosmetics industries and organizations, as well as academics from various disciplinary fields. Increasing concerns about cosmetics safety, environmental impacts as deforestation and social impacts as those resulting from unfair trade have intensified attention given to such topic.

Tehseen et al. (2019) have highlighted that cosmetics products, especially personal care, must be according to the regulations based on safety practices regarding using biodegradable products to perform the operations in this regard. The cosmetic regulations in Canada, like European Union regulations, are stringent than US regulations. The Canadian government regularly checks the cosmetic ingredients used in their cosmetic industry, including various contaminated products restricted from cosmetics use. All of those chemicals and contaminated products are allowed in U.S. products. The EU law has banned approximately more than 1000 chemicals from various cosmetics that are suspected to be the cause of genetic mutation, cancer, and reproductive harm (International Laws - Safe Cosmetics, n.d.). As the major cosmetic companies sell products across the globe it is imperative for governments to recognise the need for policies to bring positive change in sustainability actions. According to (Coelho and Nunes, 2017) and (Gasparin et al., 2021), it also improved the environment that can create safety for future generations and allow the environment to be sustainable. According to the study of (Motilewa et al., 2017), the use of a sustainable business model can be effective for the companies for safeguarding the practices of the natural and economic environment. In other companies, such as the products related to personal hygiene and personal care products, such behaviour is evident. The operations based on sustainability include the production and the packaging, transportation, and operations related to marketing in this regard based on the arguments of Safar et al. (2018). The cosmetic industry can achieve sustainability in supply chain management by adopting an aggressive approach and reducing the environmental footprints and waste. Therefore, the study has contributed to the sustainability of the operations belonging to the cosmetic industry.

The capacity for maintaining or enhancing the social, ecological and economic spectrum is sustainable. This lays massive influence on people's lives and calls for more sustainable business activities from customers, encouraging more firms to pursue a more competitive and sustainable company. The exposure of sustainability is growing, primarily because of government and the desire of corporations to enhance their performance and increase their attention to sustainable concerns. Examining the critical aspects to help promote sustainable developments in a saturated cosmetics sector and barriers to overcome for a sustainable

cosmetic product firm. Strategies to better incorporate sustainable development into the heart of their company and management strategies are given (Feng, 2016).

Customers' education, strategic partnership and corporate image building are the three major contributors to establishing the image of a sustainable cosmetic product firm (Feng, 2016). Sustainability has become a competitive advantage for companies and offer up innovative prospects. Sustainability research focuses across many industries on sustainable development but seldom tackles the success factors and barriers to disseminating sustainable ideas. This study aims to address the question 'how firms may compete better in the market with a sustainable business model for the cosmetic industry (SMEs) as an example, with a focus on the challenges, crucial success criteria and methods to assist the spread of sustainable cosmetic and cosmetic goods (Korppi, 2021). The definition of sustainable development in a firm alone is restricted and difficult to portray. Building models may assist collect, communicate analysis, and comprehend the notion better, which this study does.

1.8 Rationale

The cosmetic industry has been faced many challenges such as sustainable sourcing of raw ingredients, carbon and footprints of the whole production, which includes from manufacturing to packaging and also to distribution, waste management, biodegradability, environmental toxicity, energy consumption, CSR in terms of fairness, inclusion, and equal opportunities (Bom et al., 2019). As referred to Coelho and Nunes (2017) arguments, companies need to implement strategies for sustainable practice and create opportunities to cater for the challenges that the cosmetic industry faced in terms of sustainability. It has been assessed that sustainability practices are effective for having better environmental practices for the environment. In the study of AlQershi, Abas and MohdMokhtar (2019), the components based on the production, packaging and transportation of the cosmetics shall be according to the practices of sustainability that can be effective for achieving corporate social responsibility. The rationale behind this research is to address issues related to the sustainability of the operations in the cosmetic industry. The research problems have also highlighted limited research on the aspect of business models that can address sustainability. Therefore, the

research rationale was to address these business models and assess their applicability in the cosmetic industry. Donner and Radić (2021) have highlighted that the companies need to address these models and apply sustainability methods to implement the methods of safety for the environment and bring about innovation in this regard. The researcher has solved the issues regarding assessing business models to apply sustainability practices in the cosmetic industry.

Cosmetic market is drastically shifting now, and conventional corporate methods are at risk. By diversifying company models and employing digital technologies, collecting demographics, technological and consumer data allows local communities to get established. International companies can discover new chances to satisfy their customer demands beyond their native market through digitalisation, based on the study of Korppi (2021). Sustainability is a significant trend that influences the behaviour of individuals, thinking, decision-making and enterprises. Megatrends are characterised as wide-ranging, changeable global forces. This issue is conscious and concerned by consumers and expects enterprises to be sustainable in terms of environment, society and economics.

Companies need to demonstrate sustainability by certifications or other trustworthy ways, such as a commitment to a programme of sustainable development. Based on the study of Joyce (2019), the preservation of natural resources and long-term ecological balances indicates environmental sustainability. The industry remains facing many challenges in the immediate future concerning cosmetics: the sustainable sourcing of rudimentary ingredients, energy consumption, waste management and carbon footprint of the entire production chain— from production to packaging to distribution—biodegradability, lack of human, environmental toxicity and social responsibility in terms of integration.

1.9 Structure of the thesis

The dissertation begins with the research study's introductory chapter, which includes an introduction as well as an explanation of the research motivation. This chapter also included a full background of the study, as well as a discussion of why the researcher chose this particular issue for the study. The statement of the problem and the rationale for research have

also been highlighted. The literature review chapter is about the topic of the research study, which has provided the information of key terms and concepts of the study. The literature review of the study is collected by using prior studies. Furthermore, this chapter has also highlighted the conceptual and theoretical framework of the research. It has also highlighted the factors that are responsible for addressing the research questions.

The dissertation also included Chapter 3 that has highlighted the study's research methodology, which is used for answering the research questions or problem of the study. This chapter discusses the plans and the procedures required to carry forward the study.

The dissertation discusses Chapter 4 is analysis and findings that have provided the findings and analysed the results used in the research. This chapter is based on the methods highlighted in the previous chapter of research methodology.

Lastly, the dissertation integrated Chapter 5, which is conclusion and recommendation that has provided the summary of findings completed in chapter 4 of the research study. This chapter also discuss the future recommendation based on the same topic of the research and has presented the gaps in the current research that future researcher can fill.

1.10 Chapter summary

The following chapter discussed the critical aspect of the innovation in sustainable business model in the cosmetic sector. The chapter highlights that the innovative business model can be effective if the organisation implements it correctly to understand the innovation and sustainability factors for the organisation. There is a significant role of sustainability in the cosmetic industry that can effectively impact the business model. It explains the obligation that the companies apply such business models to achieve their sustainability goals. It can be concluded that the consumers' ultimate requirements are to use sustainable products and have sustainable packaging that can be beneficial for the environment. The businesses shall introduce such operations that can achieve sustainability in the production, packaging and transportation of cosmetic products. Based on these UK government regulate the law that banned different products that are not friendly for the environment. The products related to personal care should be according to the regulations based on safety practices involving using

biodegradable products for performing the operations in this regard. Therefore, the businesses model is needed to be applied in all the sectors of the business.

Many challenges face the cosmetics industry, including sustainable sourcing of raw ingredients, carbon and footprints from production to packaging or distribution, waste management, biodegradability, environmental toxicity, power consumption, CSR as regards equity, inclusion, and equity opportunities. In supply chain management, the cosmetic sector may achieve sustainability by taking a hostile attitude and reducing environmental impacts and waste. This study, will therefore, guide businesses towards the sustainability actions in the cosmetics business operations. This research aims to fill this gap by determining the variables that are likely to threaten the sustainability in the SME sector of Cosmetic industry. It is also based on examining the anticipated reaction instruments and processes to shifting borders, which would resist changes in the environmental, social and economic domains by business models.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter introduces the literature by illustrating the key terminology, the concept of sustainability and its three pillars, economic, social and environmental; the relation between these three pillars; overview of the cosmetic industry; sustainability in the cosmetic industry; business model and innovation; circular economy. It discusses sustainability reports of various big brands of the cosmetic industry to grasp the idea of sustainable work being done in the sector. The final part of the literature sheds light on the theoretical and conceptual framework of the research.

Meanwhile, the three primary grounds of this research revolve around the economy, social perspectives and climate considerations. Indeed, the cosmetic industry is quite vibrant, and almost everyone interacts with it in one way or another. Thus, it is necessary to ascertain whether such brands are considering sustainable measures. In this regard, business models tend to play a vital role in promoting sustainability or rejecting it outright. The theoretical framework of this writes up also highlights existing research that develops the sustainability in cosmetics further. Finally, the chapter has identified the statements and arguments of different authors related to sustainability, highlighting the significant factors associated with sustainability in the cosmetic industry. Similarly, the chapter has also discussed the economic, social, and environmental factors that affect the sustainability of the cosmetic industry. Furthermore, the chapter also discusses the sustainability aspects of various multinational companies of the cosmetic industry to get a clear viewpoint of their work concerning sustainable living.

2.2 Sustainability

According to the study of (Bom et al., 2020), sustainability reflects the production or manufacturing in a way that may not harm the environment. It stands on the pillars of the economy, environment, and society. It has been observed that the companies in

the current business environment need to address the issues regarding sustainability in the business operations that can be effective for imitating the social and economic factors for the country (Feng et al., 2018). Companies require to address the needs of the society. It shall also utilise the resources that can have limited or no harm to the environment (Bom et al., 2019 and Motilewa et al., 2017). Regarding sustainability in the cosmetic industry, several kinds of research were conducted, such as the studies of Sukumaran and Gopi, (2021) talks about the use of biopolymers as derma fillers, which is sustainable and have great skin benefits. However, Feng et al. (2018) goes into a deeper discussion about sustainable innovation in the cosmetic industry, compiling three main strategies of consumer education, company image building and strategic alliance. According to (Carvalho et al., 2016), the consumer should use environmentally friendly products, in which bio-based chemicals are used that are safe for the environment. Moreover, with the recent trends it is evident that consumers are pushing businesses towards sustainable development and are eager for change to come.

Figure 4: Three components of Sustainability

Source: Significant three pillars of sustainability (Hafizyar and Dheyaaldin, 2019)

There are a few reasons why sustainability is important because it helps with analysing the organization's influence on its practices. It is essential because the investors consider the company's footprint related to carbon, water usage, the developments related to the community, and many others. It was seen that when the firms take care of environmental, societal, and governance (ESG) changes, it helps the firm because the cost of debt and equity decreases which automatically helps the financial performance. Following the survey conducted by McKinsey (2017), it was stated that more than 3000 employees said that one of the most important and motivating factors for a firm would be a mindset that is sustained and aligned with the company's mission statement, goals, and values. This will not only help the firm by increasing its sales but will also help with improving the reputation, customer expectations which will push the firm to put in the additional effort that will eventually help and increase growth opportunities. In order to make sure that sustainability in the business is maintained, a few strategies would be applied. The first one would be looking for the problem and making the objectives according to those problems.

The very first step that a firm should take related to sustainability should be driving change which means that the sustainability related to the company, team, and client should be maintained. It is essential to look for the more significant problems, suppose if the problem is wastage. The first thing that the firm should consider has to be the amount of waste that a particular organization is creating. The second step towards a change would be establishing a mission that will pull the firm closer to its motive. The last step would be to craft a strategy. It is crucial to plan everything out so that the execution of the plan can be more accessible and the most hurdles can be avoided.

2.2.1 Economic Sustainability

One of the main pillars of sustainability is the economic aspect. Economic sustainability refers to the financial aspect of a business. Concerning the economic viewpoint, consumers play a crucial role in the sustainability of an organisation through revenue generated and consumer culture (O'Donoghue et al., 2016). Furthermore, economic sustainability for an organisation refers to the efficient use of its resources and showing responsibility towards it

(Sadriiddinov et al., 2020). When the companies produce good products for the environment, they can stand in the market to fulfil corporate social responsibility. The profitability of a business is a common notion about economic sustainability. However, the significant aspects of economic sustainability include risk management, proper governance, and compliance.

According to (Rigamonti et al., 2016), it is deemed pertinent for the organisation to sustain its actions in terms of operating profit in its business for its long-term sustainability. For its long-term economic sustainability is considered an essential aspect of corporate responsibility because this aspect is more focusing on profit, and the company's financial benefit can come with additional risks that can negatively affect the environment. According to (Zhong and Wu., 2015), the economic growth of an organisation must be aligned with the interest of the community, end-user consumers and value chain, and the shareholders and board of directors. If transparency in the accounting methods is present, it can effectively show their corporate responsibility. It will allow the company's stakeholders to be aware of the organisation's operations and practice their right to vote for eliminating any misconduct. As per the views of Niaki et al. (2019), the economic pillar of sustainability helps in counterweighing the measures of the corporation like using chemical fertilisers or fossil fuels and other more sustainable sources. Sustainable strategies help corporations in achieving profitability while keeping within the limits of environmental protection.

Economic sustainability refers to saving resources that will help later. The concept defines the value of the resources today and in the near future. This helps the firm as they have to decide whether or not to sell or buy a particular resource. Economic sustainability is essential so that it would be easy for every human to have access to their necessities since many are deprived of those. In order to make sure that the economic sustainability is there, the present population needs to use the resources at a manageable level, and the least amount of wastage is involved so that the world does not run out of them and the economic development can be easily maintained (Caruana, P., 2020.). There are a few ways to ensure economic sustainability and specific criteria that have to be looked into since that is very important. It is essential to measure the growth, development, productivity, and trickling down of the resources and the performance. The firm needs to make sure that they are economically sustainable as that will

have a huge and direct impact on the firm's financial performance. When the firm is not sustainable financially, it faces issues related to reputation and other severe and quite profound issues that lead to a long-term issue.

When the firm is involved in additional wastage and other unethical practices, it tends to receive hate from environmental-friendly customers as well as environmental activists. This leads to a problem related to the demand and the supply, which directly affects the production and the budgets made by the firm beforehand (Cinelli et al., 2019). This is a problem that many firms face, and it is crucial to come up with some measures that help the firm.

2.2.2 Social Sustainability

Social can be considered as the second pillar for sustainability. The social pillar is indicated with its name 'social', which means that the sustainability in a business must be approved socially for stakeholders, employees, and consumers (Eizenberg and Jabareen, 2017). In other words, achieving good social well-being persistently by the society or a community is referred to as social sustainability. The corporations' sustainable actions for their business also include the social aspect like the people involved.

In line with the points mentioned above, it can be further stated in words by (Missimer et al., 2017) that business operations can affect the community and stakeholders that are the main business component. The large corporation sectors negatively affect the communities by fuel usage or resource wastage, or unsustainable action. The negative impact could hinder their daily life, health, and overall physical and mental well-being. Hence, it is imperative to ensure that the business operations are not harmful to the people.

Similarly, as stated by Atanda (2019) the corporate social responsibility in terms of social sustainability refers to catering for the needs of their employees and executives. It means that treating the employees of the organisations fairly and justly is included in social sustainability. The responsibility shown towards the employees can also be reflected by considering their individual needs like paid maternity leaves and other maternity and paternity benefits, learning and developmental opportunities, and flexible scheduling. In addition, community engagement can be beneficial for companies to achieve social sustainability (Longoni and Cagliano, 2015). A

few of the strategies include scholarships, investments in the local public projects, fundraising and sponsorships. The business's supply chain can be viewed for proper employment conditions and safety, along with fair wage packages.

This speculation of social affiliation recognizes a negative linkage between upheld colonization, upheld desperation levels, and upheld regular resource abuse. There is a uniqueness of evaluation being created theory whether 'regular legitimacy' is a fundamental monetary turn of events and poverty alleviation, or financial turn of events and dejection easing up is required before 'regular reasonability' can even be tended to (Scoones, I., 2007). There is some verification that 'biological acceptability' may be a significant pre-condition of upheld money-related turn of events. For example, the US has been developing a proportion of its property district covered by trees since the 1920s and successfully managing its soils since 1930s (Nobre et al., 2016).

These measures have extraordinarily additionally fostered America's handiness in paper things and food since the Great Depression. Of course, a couple of non-mechanical countries, for example, Costa Rica, are imperilling their long stretch monetary conceivable outcomes by partaking in voracious resource fatigue (Vallance et al., 2011). By and large, deficiencies of ordinary capital in these nations hazard social increments from redesigns in financial, particular, and HR (Cruz and Repetto, 1992). The theory of 'social acceptability calls for monetary advancement obliged by the necessities of social worth. To interface these, an enabling environment ought to be made that smooths out resource use, centres around resource tasks, and empowers fair resource dissemination.

2.2.3 Environmental Sustainability

Environmental sustainability is the most crucial aspect of sustainability (Gholami et al., 2016) to the extent that sustainability alone is referred to as environmental sustainability. Environmental sustainability refers to utilising natural resources and protecting the ecosystem to support health and well-being. Natural resources are somewhat limited on Earth, especially at the current rate of industrialisation. If the organisations and people are not taking measures to ensure sustainability, the natural resources will be lost (Thangavel and Sridevi, 2016).

According to a study conducted by Higón, Gholami, and Shirazi in 2017, most corporations often run their businesses without considering environmental sustainability. As a result, they waste many natural resources during their business operations and disregard their carbon footprints.

According to (Dong and Hauschild, 2017), the company can use several strategies to maintain environmental sustainability by reducing its carbon footprint, reducing water and packaging waste, and stopping dumping the waste in the oceans and other water bodies. Furthermore, if the organisations considered these strategies in their business operations, they earn more monetary benefits. However, it commonly comes with the companies quantifying the externalities mentioned above for tracking and reducing them, like using the carbon footprint measure for carbon dioxide.

In terms of the views provided in the research study by Woodcraft (2015), environmental sustainability is not the only aspect of sustainability since economic and social aspects play an equally important role in achieving overall sustainability in a business sector (Woodcraft, 2015). These three aspects of sustainability are interconnected to each other. According to (Bom et al., 2019), sustainability is strongly emphasised in the cosmetic industry, especially in terms of economic sustainability, and it is discussed in detail in a later chapter.

'Environmental legitimacy' requires staying aware of ordinary capital as a provider of financial resources ought to be kept inside recuperation rates. At the 'sink site', waste radiations from current creation ought to be controlled not to outperform the constraint of the environment to ingest them without impedance (Goodland, 1995). It has gotten average for 'common-sense progression' or 'reasonability' to be described severely to the extent 'everyday practicality' This distortion holds that what is new with the contemporary illustration of overall headway is essential that it is demolishing the environment (Sun et al., 2020). Nevertheless, this view is shallow in the cut-off, for it ignores the market impacts and social variations that are driving natural degradation.

2.2.4 Interconnecting the three pillars of sustainability

Although the three main components of sustainability are unique in their own way, but they always go hand in hand. Purvis, Mao and Robinson (2019) look into the foundation of sustainability into these three pillars. There seems to be a gradual emergence of the concept throughout time as seen from early academia and literature. Although, the concept originally referred to the pillars of sustainability, its conceptualisation differs to those of the UN and has limited meaning to the developing countries. Talking about the consumer behaviour towards electronic waste from the three pillars of sustainable development the research shows that, in developing countries the economic pillar is given the highest importance and environmental comes as the least important and social is somewhere in between. However, the priorities of dimensions differ in the developed countries where environmental and social pillars are of higher importance due to higher welfare and the economic comes last (Shahrasbi, Shokouhyar and Zeidyahyae, 2021). In 1987 the sustainable development as institutionalised in Brundtland report pushes towards the understanding off clearing logical and social problems to enhance economic growth. This approach reflects on the building off sustainability as a three set of equally important economic, social and environmental goals.

Even though all the three pillars of sustainability always go hand in hand, research is done based on taking one of the pillars to be the main focus so as to equalise the three pillars, as sometimes economic development is often associated with values and interests of political and economic elites neglecting the importance of environmental and social issues. Zepharovich, Ceddia and Rist, (2021) writes about the three-pillars sustainability criteria and environmental justice criteria to account thoroughly the issues of unequal distribution of environmental costs and benefits in power is symmetry. Similarly, Sharpe and Barling, (2019) explains about on the social pillar in respect to the food industry. The social dimension sheds lights on various attributes like food safety, quality, ethical trading, wages, trust, equality and many more, the research shows social pillar as a pliable component which is moulded to prioritise changing agendas or pre-existing policies or omitted altogether.

Case study done in the solar thermal electricity project in Mexico shows the relativity between social economic effects which are the result of direct effects during the investment

phase in the supply chain, on contrary to the environmental impacts mainly caused by indirect activities related to the investment phase. The research assesses the need to take into account direct and indirect impact on the supply chain equally accounting for the economic environmental and social dimensions to identify the sustainability hotspots and implementations required to improve the sustainability performance of the project (Rodríguez-Serrano et.al, 2017).

2.4 Cosmetic Industry

When considering the viability and extent of the cosmetic industry, its widespread feminist coverage is evident for its multibillion-dollar worth worldwide. In terms of its origins, the industry advanced after the Great Depression and subsequently World War 2. Since then, both genders have been using cosmetic products all around the world. More companies are claiming to be gender neutral specially regarding skincare (Culliney, 2021). Gender neutral has become the news standard in skin care and makeup it's just changing the perceptions of feminine and masculine products and encouraging brands to rethink their marketing campaigns and positioning (GlobalData, 2021). In other words, the cosmetics industry is a multibillion-dollar global giant that has become one of the most booming sectors during the Great Recession, since mid-1930 after World War II. On the other hand, cosmetics is not a gender-specific sector because it encompasses various products such as powder, shampoos, deodorants, soaps, body care, foundation, shaving, and mouthwash and toothpaste. (Ramli, 2015).

Meanwhile, the cosmetics industry is a significant contributor to the Gross domestic product of a country. On the other hand, its social influence cannot be neglected in the individual lives of a common person (Hvarez and Yazdal, 2014). Amalgamated colour that utilised to face paint people in ancient places (Yahya, 2019). Similarly, the cold cream and oil-based scents were also applied by Romans and Greeks, respectively. Fragrances from the Far East were introduced back to Europe by Crusaders in the 13th of century. Powders or gelatine

extracts were used to create perfumes in the 16th century. Likewise, organic fragrances were created using a variety of aroma-rich substances.

The USA is considered one of the world's leading cosmetic consumers, with a whole array of billion-dollar multinational cosmetic companies. In order to cater for the demand, the country has utilised numerous strategies to cope with incumbent demand. In the light of the study conducted by Kumar (2005), cosmetics is a critical industry, not only regarding contribution to gross domestic product globally but also regarding its profound impact on people's social lives worldwide. Cosmetics, scents, and cosmetic products have been used since ancient times. Here are several historical examples. Red, brownish, and yellow generated from mud, clay, and arsenic were used to paint the face of the people Neanderthals. Curling hair was done using bones. Makeovers, tattoos, and other adornments were used to communicate important social information.

According to the study of Meilhac (2010), cosmetics products have been used for a long time to improve one's appearance dating back to the dawn of civilisation. Cosmetic product was first used in the Western hemisphere in the Middle Ages. However, this sector was completely established in the twentieth century, and during the last two decades, the cosmetic industry has seen significant growth.

The study of Rugman (2005) stated that the cosmetics sector is globally based, with North American and Western European companies contributing for roughly 43% of the total. According to (Cornell et al., 2019), cosmetic products are primarily used by people. According to a report in the U.S., cosmetic products account for approximately more than 60\$ billion in annual expenditure.

The study of Han et al. (2021) states that in 2017, the worldwide cosmetics sector (items aimed to assist people in achieving cultural expectations of 'cosmetic' was estimated at over approximately \$500 billion, with a market rate of over the U.S. \$800 billion predicted by 2023 (Orbis Research, 2020). The Greek word cosmetics is often used in an individual's cultural, fashion, cosmetic, and economic spending.

Cosmetics and skincare items are considered the most innovative and quickly growing products in the dermatological industry. The cosmetics market industry is highly

susceptible to skin tone. All of the creams, tints, eye shadows, and lip products are tinted to match the skin colour. People use numerous cosmetic products for the purpose of enhancing their appearance. The substance used in the manufacturing of cosmetic products is obtained from plants. Many skincare products use antioxidants, fragrances, preservatives, moisturising agents, and other benefits obtained from plant materials to create the final product (Draelos, 2012).

It has been concluded from the study conducted by Ramli (2015) that cosmetics businesses have their market strategies. However, the majority of them focused on commodities, target female customers. This industry is growing due to market developments, politics, globalisation, need, society, and knowledge. Cosmetics and skincare items are considered the most innovative and quickly growing products in the dermatological industry. The cosmetics market industry is highly susceptible to skin tone. All of the creams, tints, eye shadows, and lip products are tinted to match the skin colour. To enhance the appearance, numerous cosmetic and cosmetic products are used by people. The substance used in the manufacturing of cosmetic products is obtained from plants. Many skincare products use antioxidants, fragrances, preservatives, moisturising agents, and other benefits obtained from plant materials to create the final product (Draelos, 2012). It has been concluded from the study conducted by Ramli (2015) that cosmetics businesses have their market strategies. However, the majority of them focused on commodities, target female customers. This industry is growing due to market developments, politics, globalisation, need, society, and knowledge.

2.5 Big Brands of Cosmetics Industry

In 2019, Nar's Cosmetic products from the United States claimed the lead, followed by Lancôme from France, which is currently riding high on the success of its La Vie EST Belle scent. Every five seconds, one bottle of their fragrance was sold worldwide, and it is still a top hit in Europe. L'Oréal made 3 billion euro in revenue in 2018, as per Le Monde, mainly owing to the China market. Dior Cosmetic took the third position, according to a Belgian artist of makeup named Peter Philips, who is the creative and image director for Dior Makeup. He produced world-famous perfumes like J'Adore and provides edge goods (Vogue, 2019).

The ten leading cosmetic brands, ranked by their media compaction factor in U.S. dollars, are. Nar's is the top leading brand having revenue of \$180 540 356. The second leading brand is Lancôme, with a profit of \$134 370 477. Followed by Lancôme, Dior cosmetic is positioned on third with \$114 008 988. The fourth big brand in the cosmetics industry is Laura Mercier which holds a \$112 901 116. Followed by Mercier, Charlotte Tilbury is not behind, having a revenue of \$91 395 872 and regarded as the 5th leading cosmetic brand. Likewise, Estée Lauder, Chanel Cosmetic, YSL Cosmetic, Tatcha and Pat McGrath are other big cosmetics brands globally, considered the most influential makeup brands worldwide (Vogue, 2019).

The other brands include the Gillette brand, and it was ranked to be the 3rd top brand in 2019 with a revenue of about \$8143M. In 2020 Gillette was considered to be the 2nd top brand with yearly revenue of \$8479M. The other top brands include NIVEA. In 2019 it was ranked to be the fourth brand in the world. Its yearly revenue came out to be \$6853M. In 2020, NIVEA came out to be at the 3rd position in the whole world. The monthly revenue of the NIVEA came out to be \$7391M. The other brand known as Estee Lauder was ranked at the 10th position but is considered one of the best brands in 2019. However, it was ranked at the position of 4th in 2020 (Ranking The Top 50 Cosmetic Companies, 2020).

The yearly profit of this brand came out to be \$4952M, and in 2020 the profit of this brand came out to be \$6290M. The other brands which are known worldwide are MAC, created in 1984. It was considered one of the best makeup brands and is also known for the best colour palette in the world. Another brand that is famous for its creation and collection is Givenchy. It was established in 1989 and is one of the best-reputed brands. The other brand is Revlon, known to be the most affordable brand, and are famous for their outstanding creation in the face and hair products. There are various other brands which are resided at local markets (Haig, 2006).

2.6 Sustainability in the Cosmetic Industry

Sustainability becomes the biggest concern for businesses with the increased rate of industry and its requirements. Sustainability means that the recycling of package (Bom et al., 2019) can be done in several ways, including using safe and secure products and reducing

plastics. The sustainability of the cosmetic industry can be measured by using various methods. According to the research, in 2015, U.S. Foods and Drugs stores had banned the utilisation of microbeads in the cosmetic industry after knowing the effects of microbeads on oceans. Therefore, they banned its use in the cosmetic industry (Bom et al., 2019).

Figure 5: Graphical representation of the sustainability in the Cosmetic Industry

Source: Bom et al., 2019

The above picture shows the graphical representation of sustainability in the cosmetics industry, but only the representation of product life cycle. According to the picture depicted above the sustainability in the cosmetic industry is only related to the selection of the raw materials and finding out the best solution in that. It does not show the whole picture of the product life cycle including its packaging, how it's used by the consumers and also the ways it is discarded in the end. It is imperative to take into account overall sustainability from packaging to product throughout the supply chain, in collaboration with the other pillars, social and economic. Taking example of Plastic packaging, in UK 70% of plastic waste comes from packaging. In 2018, The Plastic Pact was launched in collaboration with Ellen McArthur Foundation to change the linear system of disposing off (Plastic packaging | WRAP, 2021). To narrow down the usage of plastic bags, United States has also emphasised the use of biodegradable, and they start to invest money in this. In UK looking at the significant amount of increase in plastic waste that comes from packaging, environmental tax was introduced by government with charges companies using less than 30% recycled plastic as packaging

(Boneham, 2022). Many issues like this need to be solved through research and implemented (Sahota, 2014). According to Abbitt, plastics should be reduced; she said plastic bags are primarily used in the colour cosmetic industry (Bom et al., 2019). If there is no secondary market for recycling, then the product will contain vast amounts of plastic, which is being mixed with magnets, screws, and mirrors (Sahota, 2014). It is the biggest and the worst alarming situation in the cosmetic industry.

Most cosmetic product contains mirrors and magnets in its product packaging to make it easier for the consumers to apply makeup on go and make it durable for travel. However, unfortunately, magnets and mirrors cannot be recycled, and the plastic needs over 1000 years to decompose entirely, while to be thoroughly disposed of the paper takes 2-6 weeks. Therefore, the cosmetic product elements are considered a long-term waste because the mixtures used in manufacturing cosmetic products packaging take much time to decompose (Sahota, 2014).

With the growing age of the usage of the cosmetic industry, sustainability is related to several aspects, including the safety of cosmetics and the factors that impact the environment. Furthermore, it has also influenced the social aspect like the trade conditions (Santos et al., 2016). Therefore, sustainability is gradually becoming the need of the modern era to satisfy the use of products, plan, and strategies. Considering the above picture, the product life cycle of sustainability in the cosmetic industry is of vital importance. Furthermore, to ensure sustainability in the cosmetic industry, selecting the suitable material is very important because this is the primary step to ensure quality (Santos et al., 2016).

Lejla CAS, the founder of the biodegradable brand KNESKO, said that ensuring complete sustainability is difficult (Bom et al., 2019). However, the companies should balance the money, sustainability and safe use of products, not compromising quality (Sahota, 2014). According to one of the researchers, a calculator to measure the sustainability factor is formulated by taking surveys from the number of people working in the cosmetic industry (Bom et al., 2020). They considered every step, which includes the use of the materials in the production process. Also, they studied the bad and the good influence of the product by analysing the data obtained

from the experts. From all the analyses conducted, they form the Excel sheet that reflects the point of view of those experts (Bom, Ribeiro, and Marto, 2020).

The findings showed no single thing; either it is a material, the material for packing, or the practices utilised are not entirely sustainable. However, some plans could be implemented to reduce the factor of sustainability from the product. (Sahota, 2014). The cosmetic industry describes sustainability in two ways: corporate social responsibility, reports covering sustainability, and customer communication.

However, through the research, the most common method to improve sustainability in the cosmetic industry is by utilising renewable energy. Many industries are shifting towards this approach (Santos et al., 2016). The cosmetic industry is enhancing its products by the usage of this approach called eco-focused. They not only use this approach in the products but also in the production process. Hence it is one of the best ways to improve sustainability.

Sustainability in the business goes far past packaging and merges the whole creation measure from sourcing to product creation to its use (Bom et al., 2020). Rising good industrialism and the necessity for resource usefulness are making remedial associations – small, self-governing firms to overall beasts – gain ground towards sensible new development. One way to deal with make less waste is through appropriate packaging. A segment of the top greatness brands is contemplating how to reduce their carbon impression through suitable packaging. In a like manner, their containers are recyclable, with 20% of the plastic is from plastic waste in the ocean.

There are mainly three dimensions of sustainability which are environmental, the social dimension, and the economic pillar. The environmental dimension usually deals with the natural environment or the resource which can be renewable. At the same time, the social pillar contains the communities and the involvement of the society (Fortunati et al., 2020). Finally, the other remaining pillar, economical, contains money, prosperity, wealth, and jobs. Thus, sustainability can be developed by taking all the common properties, which would be viable in all its three pillars, environment, social and economic.

2.6.1 Economic dimension of sustainability in the cosmetic industry:

Economic sustainability refers to the long-term growth of the economy without considering the different factors that are environmental, social, and technological. From the different economist viewpoint, the consumer plays a crucial role in the organisation's sustainability. According to Fortunati et.al. (2020), for economic sustainability, a business's profitability is considered as the common notion for the business outcome. However, the significant aspects of economic sustainability include risk management, proper governance and compliance.

Economic sustainability is considered the driving factor in the cosmetic industry. Because it contains all the economic factors that are price, cost, market reputation, and demand or supply of the product, these are all considered the economic dimension whenever an organisation wants to operate effectively. The economic factor is not an independent variable; it is considered as the subset of the society. According to Demichelis et al. (2018), both are the environmental pillar of sustainability. It means that they are both co-dependents on the environmental pillar. It implies that every activity and plan of the human is dependent on and influences the environment. However, the economic factor deals with the supply and demand, production, and technology usage in the cosmetic industry. Therefore, this factor lies under the society because it caters to all the attributes of the society (Demichelis et al., 2018).

According to Visvizi, Lytras, Damiani and Mathkour, (2018) the main factor that drives the economic growth of sustainability is innovation. Therefore, it can also solve different problems that most of the business are faced while implementing any innovation that is related to social as well as the environmental issues. Most emerging problems that different organisations can face are pollution problems, shortage of resources, and economically unstable. However, in the cosmetic sector, innovation in the product is to change the structure and design of the product. To maintain a sustainable position, most organisations used conventional methods utilised to develop a sustainable environment. Various organisations also used incremental innovations used on a minor level to improvise the design and the process. This innovation is used to enhance the significant work, which includes the manufacturing and

the management process. Hence, innovation can drive economic sustainability in the cosmetic industry, and, in return, the economic factor drives the cosmetic industry.

The cosmetics and personal care products business must adapt and improve in order to design products that will help to further grow the sustainability, acting across the entire supply chain while always keeping the customer's well-being in mind. When focusing on each stage of an item's life cycle, it's critical to know which variables to consider while concentrating on sustainability (Bom et al., 2019). About the planning stage, it ought to be noticed that regularly a massive piece of the ecological effect of an item is characterized at this underlying stage. This stage is amazingly subject to the others, implying that the activities taken at this beginning phase will be reflected in the manageability of the eventual outcome and separate last stages related. While the specific extent of its impact contrasts as per the particular item, the significance of considering manageability during the planning cycle, along these lines, in determining the crude material is evident.

Concerning the sourcing of raw materials, it is perceived that the restorative industry is being compelled to think about elective feedstock for fixings, not just on account of green industrialism interest yet also due to the declining supply of petrochemical feedstock. The theme encompassing the choice of selected raw materials for impractical fixings is a reasonably disputable subject. In some cases, no appropriate consideration is given, and in this manner, an explicit area will be introduced underneath which a few relevant questions will be raised. Be that as it may, this segment will be lifted the shroud of the subject. For the sake of supportability, new restorative fixings are arising uncommonly from horticultural-based raw materials and green science, just as oleo chemistry (Beerling et al., 2014; Saraf et al., 2018).

As earlier said the economic sustainability is directly influenced by innovation and the global pandemic has tested all the limits of the cosmetic industry to innovate. To continue with ongoing problems relating to COVID-19 the brands are focusing on digital, online sales which increased over 23% by the end of 2021. Also, social media apps like tick tock are the new marketing techniques used by a lot of companies (Mimi, 2021). The global pandemic is also seen as a new challenge emerging from the demands and trends of sanitary crisis, hence developing a new opportunity for the beauty industry to innovate and catch up on the economy

crisis and pave its way to recovery (Varnier, 2021). Although there were lots of challenges during COVID-19 for the beauty industry but it has also created a way for new consumers who take sustainable cosmetics regarding with organic and natural beauty products into account as the skin care market went up and cosmetics market like makeup was falling (Culliney, 2020).

2.6.2 Social sustainability in the cosmetic industry

According to the study of Fortunati et al. (2020), social sustainability is defined as the process that promotes the well-being of the people and offers a system that contributes towards social equity and the human rights of the people. It has been observed that the implementation of social sustainability measures can be used in the cosmetic industry to initiate ethical understanding and utilise the raw materials that are renewable and address the requirements of society. The use of renewable energy can also contribute towards a healthier environment. According to Fortunati et al. (2020), It can also build a sustainable environment that can be socially and ethically well for the communities. The cosmetic industry is based on various kinds of operations that includes the production and the packaging of the products. As referred to in the study of Formicola (2018), the implications of sustainability can be integrated with the cosmetic industries by utilising the raw material and can also be effective for building products that are environmentally friendly and contribute towards the security of the environment. One of the most practical aspects of the cosmetic industry is Life Cycle Thinking (LCT), as it can contribute towards sustainability in the company and create safety measures for society and the communities.

Rising good commercialization and the necessity for resource viability are making remedial associations – small, free firms to overall beasts – make progress towards prudent new development. Consistently, the term is used to portray things using innocuous to the environment subtleties, creation practices, or packaging procedures (Fortunati et al., 2020). As to beautifiers business, "green" and "pragmatic" enhancing specialists are portrayed as restorative things using usual trimmings conveyed from supportable rough materials. The cosmetics and skincare industry are known for its profound use of plastics, especially in their

packaging. Plastic waste requires numerous years to break down, and it often ends up slowing down in landfills or eaten by animals.

2.6.3 Environmental sustainability in the cosmetic industry

According to Fortunati et al. (2020), most cosmetic industries perform their operations related to environmental sustainability to ensure the environmental factor to solve carbon emission issues and be effective for post-consumer use. Most organisations use recycled and environment free material in their production and effectively used biodegradable products to ensure the quality and effective pattern of environmental factors. Most companies can create opportunities for reusing the products and packaging material based on effective recycling. Similarly, it has also been observed that the cosmetic industry can bring about positive changes, and the transportation methods can also be environmentally friendly. According to Cinelli et al. (2019), most cosmetic companies used hybrid transportation to be more environmentally friendly for society and the industry. One of the main aspects that are assessed is the material used in the production of the products. It is needed to have minimum aspects of biodiversity and create opportunities for safety and manage the biodiversity in the operations. It has also been argued that the cosmetic companies utilise the raw material regarding the emulsifiers and the exfoliators that can be present in the industry and can also have the operations of formulation in the pollutions concerns. According to Gregurec et al. (2021), operations are needed to be performed according to the environmental regulations that have a limited negative and a positive impact on the environment. Therefore, the cosmetic industry brings about positive changes, but it also negatively affects the organisation by delivering environmental free products in the market. Therefore, the cosmetic industry shall bring about positive changes by using biodegradable products that can be used to implement the significant steps for the environmental cycle in the cosmetic products.

Nuances will be given of new drives that are dispensing plastics from waste streams. Lee Mann, Global Community Trade Manager at The Body Shop, will show how it has set up supply chains for the world's first 'sensibly traded' reused plastic. It has helped out Plastics For Change so that waste experts in India pick plastic waste, which is then used in haircare bottles (Ramli,

2015). The drive is disposing of plastic tainting while at the same time giving a premium to demolished organizations in India. Another speaker will show how plastic waste can be used to make new things. With creating purchaser protection from plastics, different green packaging materials for beautifiers and individual thought are emerging. Nature Works will include the creating use of its Ingeo biopolymers in remedial packaging. The bioplastic material is created utilizing plant sugars. Paul Jenkins, Founder of The Pack Hub, will have a studio wherein new sensible materials will be discussed. The massive theory is going into the embellishing specialist's industry to make valuable things and decrease packaging impacts, at any rate, around economy moreover needs trustworthy usage (Santos et al., 2016). The meaning of a moderate lifestyle to lessen the impacts of remedial and individual thought things will be inspected, similarly, to managing to empower customers to lead a pragmatic lifestyle.

2.7. Strategies to initiate Sustainability in business model

The key focus of sustainability in an organisation is dependent on socio-economic considerations. They include the compromises and concessions made by an entity and the benefits derived from the approach. The strategy realigns the focus of a company towards an agreed goal. The sustainable strategy usually includes various parameters. For instance, long term objectives such as waste reduction and recycling can only be secured through a viable sustainability strategy. However, it is an imperative fact that the business model is directly associated with the sustainable strategy. In various studies such as of Voinea et al. (2019)'s research, the sustainable business strategy must align with the sustainable growth model that includes revenue generation and customer satisfaction. In this regard, the customers have to be engaged necessarily. As witnessed from many occurring in the past, it can be considered that customer engagement can include all the relevant stakeholders. Evidently, the customer-centric business strategy must focus on generating socio-environmental awareness that can be viable for the company.

Additionally, the business must have a feasible strategy to engage the customers. The first critical step of achieving sustainability is to assess and prioritise along with the measurement and reporting. In addition, proper guidance will be provided to stakeholders

about the operations and process of the business. Sustainable strategies also depend on the different components that bring success for the future. One strategy defined in the company to adopt the business model is based on the “Cyclical borrow-use-return model” (Willard, 2010).

(Willard, 2010)

It highlights the five steps towards the betterment of the three sectors of sustainability:

Radical resource productivity: As a solution to overharvesting and depletion of natural capital, companies rely less on materials and energy derived from earth's crust and make use of natural resources more efficiently.

Investment in natural capital: Societies and businesses rely on companies to restore, maintain, and expand ecosystems.

Ecological redesign: Rather than being disposed of in a landfill, companies make use of closed-loop production systems, in which waste is treated as a resource and reused.

Service and flow economy: Companies replace their goods with services and takes back products that are obsolete or no longer functioning and recycles or remanufactures them.

Responsible consumption: Responsible consumption is promoted through educating consumers about where products are made, how they are made, what they contain, how they are packaged, their life-cycle ecological footprint, and other sustainability concerns (Romero and Molina, 2014).

The planning of resources is one of the sustainable strategies; for instance, there must be less or no use of plastic bags in the cosmetics company. Basically, it adds impetus to the sustainability cause. Plastic is one of the main polluters of the world. Hence, a ban over its use can deter a significant amount of waste reduction that can benefit the planet in the longer run. Since plastic is highly present in cosmetic products, it is apparent that plastic reduction can be an integral part of the sustainability study (Azad et al., 2016).

Different strategies and business approaches are used to initiate sustainability in the 21st century business models (Willard, 2020), which will create long-term value by considering the organisation's operations in the social, ecological, and economic environment. In order to achieve sustainability, it is necessary to craft strategies that advance the company's long-term goals. A study conducted by Voinea et al. (2019) showed that different elements could impact the model of sustainable business strategy. CSR initiatives are determined by the philanthropic drive of a start-up, which in turn is determined by the field in which it operates. This element includes business must be commercially profitable and has adequate resources for the sustainable growth of the business. It is determined by the personality and organizational expertise of entrepreneurs whether they will adopt CSR practices. As part of their business models, start-ups engage in CSR through a combination of financial and social capital, with financial benefits serving as a continual motivator for the practice from the outset.

Additionally, the business must have a feasible strategy to engage the customers. The first critical step of achieving sustainability is to assess and prioritise along with the measurement and reporting. In addition, proper guidance will be provided to stakeholders about the operations and process of the business. Sustainable strategies also depend on the different components that bring success for the future. One strategy defined in the company to

adopt the business model is based on the “Cyclical borrow-use-return model”. The planning of resources is one of the sustainable strategies.

Meanwhile, western countries such as the US encourage the biodegradable approach as the practical sustainability study. Therefore, the use of plastic must be reduced in the cosmetic industry to bring sustainability. According to Zott and Amit (2007), many challenges can be solved by doing adequate research and implementing these sustainability strategies. Most of the materials based on plastic are not being observed as fully efficient for the development of the products. This is the biggest and the worst alarming situation in the cosmetic industry. The study showed that one of the successful business model strategies is to maximise the materials and enhance energy efficiency (Porter and Derry, 2012). Another study found that sustainability in the business models can be achieved by closing the loops of resources by reusing the products.

Additionally, the remanufacturing and recycling of the products can be done to bring sustainability to the cosmetic industry (Henfridsson and Lind, 2014). Furthermore, the products must be substituted with the renewables and integration of the natural processes. The sufficiency must be achieved by providing the information that enhances less consumption (Karadag, 2015). The business model must include the strategies to utilise the resources to enhance the social and environmental advantages, creating value for the unattended stakeholders and including them in the value creation process. The strategy must include the scaling of sustainable solutions and technologies.

Building the sustainable business model and its success is based on the employees, customers, retailers and investors (Hall et al. 2010). The sustainable strategies are significant for the businesses as it helps the employers, and the stakeholders bring the company's economic and financial success. The study done by Cantele and Zardini, (2018), suggests the social, economic, and formal practices dimensions of sustainability have a positive impact on competitive advantage, and are mediated by company reputation, customer satisfaction, and organisational commitment. Additionally, it demonstrated that the competitive advantage contributes positively to financial performance as a second-stage mediator. Sustainability is based on assessing the issues and crafting the strategies over time to bring the modifications in

the business (Wheelen and Hunger, 2011). The foundations must be based on the pillars that bring social, economic and environmental acceptance in the society about the products and procedures of the company. The changes must be brought and embraced in the business models by checking and examining the leadership positions. The leadership is responsible for ensuring the employees about bringing the motivation and enhancing the commitment to bring success in any organisation. The study showed that one of the successful business strategies is maintaining a friendly environment between the people working in the business (Pereira and Barbieri, 2012). The built-up of morale and ethics is necessary to help understand the situations and objectives of the business that showed the value and contribution to the business.

Transparency is one of the components in the business that helps the customers build their trust and enhances their performance. The only method to achieve transparency is to open communication with the customers and all the stakeholders about the information disclosure and bring more clarity and accuracy in the processes. The faults must be recognised and overcome by integrating practical strategies (Schaltegger et al., 2011). The appropriate marketing and promotion procedures must be integrated to enhance the visibility of the cosmetics products and achieve sustainable development. The study demonstrated that the cosmetic company could achieve sustainability by educating the consumers about the products.

Additionally, the innovation must be brought into consumers' knowledge so that they can be more attracted to the use of cosmetic products. Innovation is one of the most critical aspects to achieve the businesses goals, and this is also associated with the use of technology in the business model (Schaltegger et al., 2016). The improvement in the relationship of customers and sales was found helpful in bringing the improvement within the business model. Innovative strategies such as using technology can help reduce waste in the environment and increase profit margins. According to Chin et al. (2018), the improvement in customer care services can help deal with the competitiveness and efficiency within the market. Assertively, the role of the business model cannot be neglected in terms of succeeding in a sustainable strategy. The present corporate world is full of innumerable vagaries that seek to derive profits from maximising utility. However, these revenues come at socio-environmental costs. They must be eliminated in the meantime to dispose off the future implications.

2.7.1 Business Model (BM) of the cosmetic industry

The business model of any industry described the process and innovation process that can be achieved by delivering an innovative business model. BM usually targets various consumers and is also based on different categories that can impact the organisation's overall performance. Salins et al. (2019) specify that the BM of the cosmetic sector is based on several factors that can affect the organisation's overall performance. The primary factor in the Business model of the cosmetic industry is selecting appropriate consumers targeted by the industry. The cosmetic company can decide to serve single or numerous customer segments. According to Ray and Mondal (2017), to remain successful, customers must be classified into several sub-segments regarding their needs, demography and behaviour. Therefore, the BM of the cosmetic sector has to emphasise single or small segment groups and focus on them. If the company decides to serve more than one customer segment, they must be different from each other. According to Zito (2017), they classified two primary factors in the cosmetic industry: behaviour and demography. Due to the diversity among the customer age and their preferences, every organisation needs to understand the basis of their customer and the business's compelling nature.

Another factor affecting the business model is the value proposition to provide effective products and services to the customer. It classifies that issue to be resolved and offers a recommendation that suits the situations and requirements of the consumers better than other substitute products available in the market. The value proposition illustrates which services or products are capable of creating value for the selected consumer segment. On the grounds of this perspective, the companies working in the cosmetic industry offers the latest, up-to-date collection of specific occasion make-ups in addition to general make-up items. The industry has switched to organic products that provide another value to customers in chemical-free makeup, causing no side effects and skin diseases (Zito, 2017). Most of the brands offer a different product that is much different from the existing products. By delivering differentiated products in the market, organisations can gain a competitive advantage by delivering quality products. The quality of the products is more excellent and more valuable than the other products

available in the market. Another factor is Channel. Channels play a critical role in the consumer journey; they impact the value proposition of the organization and provide a means to comprehend customer after purchase assessment, a primary means of building loyalty. Zito (2017) argues that not all the services and products can be sold by applying the same marketing channel techniques; these channels can be indirect or direct. The organisation also decides to utilise channels that they own, such as websites or partners, to intermediate amid them and the clients, such as retail stores (Salins et al., 2019).

Every top-rated brand offers an effective product in the market by considering the factor of innovation and effective products. Most of the time, they sell their products through departmental stores and big stores to ensure that it positions high brand value in consumers' minds. Some of the brands have never sold the products from low reputed stores. The organisations prefer to sell their products by their outlets rather than marketing through small shops on the streets (Ray and Mondal, 2017). Most of the companies have now shifted to online marketing channels to access the mass market in few clicks. It has allowed the firms to reduce their marketing cost as a significant business model target (Michael, 2020). Therefore, the organisations have shifted majorly to online marketing channels.

Customer relationship is another component that can affect the business model. According to Confente and Brunetti (2017), signifying that customer relationship is an essential component of the business model. It allows the organisation to retain their loyal customer for long-term growth and increase the organisation's revenue. Therefore, the cosmetics industry is heavily concentrated on improving its customer relationships. Many organisations robust their customer association to implement a practical understanding of the organisation. If the organisation has effective and loyal customers, they focus on attracting those who cannot try the products because it allows the companies to keep their customers engaged and associated with the organisation in the long-term objectives.

2.8. Sustainability-oriented innovation of SMEs

In a competitive environment, innovation is the main factor for the success of SMEs as depicted in the research done by Wagner, (2017). It was noticed that innovative procedures

could bring changes in the market and makes it easier to achieve sustainability. At the intermediate level, innovation is seen as a technology-specific innovation system that is built upon successful coalition building of actors and institutions within the narrow context of the innovation. In their text, Dyerson and Preuss, (2017) argues that corporate sustainability, innovation, and entrepreneurship are symbiotically related and together create a nexus of linkages that can be examined at both the micro-scale and the macroscale. For the business's long-term growth, innovation was also found helpful in achieving sustainable solutions for a long time.

It was reported that sustainable-based innovation methods are considered new in terms of prepared products, services and processes that also found helpful in decreasing the negative environmental and social impacts. To bring the innovations in the organisation by integrating the technical measures and marketing strategies was found beneficial for the companies to achieve corporate sustainability (Bergmann and Utikal, 2021).

The drivers of sustainability in SMEs constitute voluntary engagement, legislation, motivation, knowledge and collaboration, and proper communication with the stakeholders. Stakeholders include suppliers, retailers, employees and the customer. The small management and medium-sized enterprises are mostly comprised of about 250 people that work to proceed with the business and achieving financial gains. Some of the factors involved in sustainable environmental strategies of SMEs constitute organisational structure and innovation in the management styles, manufacturing activity, innovative capacity, technological approach, and External Corporation. The innovation in manufacturing the new products in SMEs enhanced the opportunities for cosmetic companies to increase their engagements in entrepreneurship (Medrano et al., 2020). The activities of customer sales relationships are also considered as one of the innovative aspects of the company.

The study highlighted that innovation strategies of SMEs must be market-driven along with addressing the crucial conditions of society. These conditions must be analysed and assessed to protect the environment by achieving sustainability and enhancing the awareness among the people about the manufactured products. These services and products are specialised to attract large size global companies for SMEs (Morcillo et al., 2021). One of the

innovative and sustainable methods for SMEs is to bring innovation in developing new products by providing market opportunities and meeting customer demands by handling the supply chain pressures. It was noticed that innovation in the products of SMEs involves the substitution of already used materials with more sustainable products.

For instance, the products can be prepared to help in energy saving, which results in lowering the cost required in preparing the products (Klewitz and Hansen, 2014). There must be a mechanism to examine the environmental aspects that include designing products and selecting raw materials for the product preparation. The environmental impacts of the prepared materials and used components must be assessed to analyse the impact of products on the environment. Furthermore, the higher the investment in integrating the green core competency of the organisation, the better will be innovation performance (Klewitz and Hansen, 2011). The lifecycle assessment (LCA) is a procedure that promotes the more use of products with an environmentally friendly design that enhanced the whole life cycle of the prepared products. Some drivers used to adopt these practices that help the companies work in the competitive environment (Adams et al.,2016).

It was reported that LCA provides the benefits in terms of savings linked with a whole life span of products that include preparation, disposal, training etc. LCA is considered an effective method for enhancing the product's design to deal with compliance issues in terms of environmental aspects. SMEs can also achieve economic advantages by responding to the pressures such as higher demands of customers for the products and services of companies (De et al., 2020). The innovation strategies were found helpful for SMEs because they decrease the use of material, consumption of energy reduce wastes to ensure the delivery of clean and eco-efficient products. Some of the SMEs also employ the network-based system to decrease the resource constraints and further involve sustainable practices. The study highlighted that proactive companies and innovative-based SMEs integrate the processes to achieve environmental sustainability that also provides social benefits. The companies must bring innovation to meet the market demands and also secure competitiveness in the environment. The companies such as the cosmetic-based industries can integrate innovation in their use practices by collaborating with effective partners (Hansen and Klewitz, 2017).

The effective partners can be larger-scale buyers that can help in bringing the innovation of products and provided services. It was observed that only good communication skills are insufficient for SMEs to deal with the barriers and radical innovation. These practices recommended that knowledge-based companies exert a more significant influence in comparison with value chain partners. There are different types of sustainable and innovative practices used by SMEs to achieve economic, social and environmental benefits (Maletic et al.,2016). In the cosmetic industry, innovation strategies can be employed in designing the products, processes, composition and product manufacturing. The electronic items can be used and the promotion of natural products to make a remarkable position in the industry. The conventional processes used in the industries include the use of eco-friendly processes to achieve sustainability. The use of clean technology can be integrated for this purpose. The main reason for using these innovative methods is to deal with the competitive market, strict laws related to product's preparation and their effects on the environment (Harsanto et al., 2018).

The study showed that innovation based on lean and sustainable practices increased the competitiveness of SMEs in flexible and sustainable manners. The cosmetic industry can use these innovative strategies to gain economic and social benefits. The lean procedure is based on increasing the efficiency of the products manufactured by the industries and providing services (Buhl et al., 2019). On the other hand, the sustainability-based innovation measures are based on responsiveness. Therefore, the combined practices of sustainability-based innovation methods can be used by SMEs to enhance the outcomes for the supply chain. These strategies are also helpful for the policymakers and employers of SMEs to achieve sustainability and enhance their performance (Caputo et al., 2017).

Besides, physical exercise or social interaction can be further advanced via innovation for this purpose; main spots include; public, open spaces that improve mental and physical health. In turn, these sustainable measures often lead to happiness. In the long run, the approaches reduce environmental stressors such as air or noise pollution, leading to respiratory and cardiovascular disease (Pollalis, 2018). Therefore, the measures depict the present state of the sustainable innovations employed by various entities.

2.9. Transforming sustainability challenges into a competitive advantage

The cosmetic industry faces many challenges to maintain sustainability. The performance of corporate sectors must be improved in the companies that can be useful to deal with serious challenges (Arseculeratne and Yazdanifard, 2014). Many of the research studies provided information about incorporating proper and innovative measures to transform the challenges involved in bringing sustainability into competitive benefits. Different theories proposed the ideas to deal with these challenges. Some theories, such as stakeholder theory, institutional theory, and others, help the industries deal with competitive benefits.

Considering the significance of sustainable competitive advantages, researchers have observed various affecting variables in a similar context. However, little is known and acknowledged with respect to the innovation of IT. The varied capabilities of IT and the available IT resources can bring a massive difference in the organization, it can either be beneficial for the company, or significantly insufficient efforts can bring down an entire industry. According to Huang et al. (2015), companies can perform significantly at an advantage when the technological resources and capabilities are well-aligned with the company's knowledge resources, governance, and relationship resources. Not only this, according to Azad et al. (2016), the personal capabilities of people involved in IT and its functions also contribute to the sustaining efforts of the company.

However, there is a need to explore a lot more research to understand the influence and effect of IT capabilities and intangible resources. However, Peter Deck (2017) briefly talks about knowledge resources, also a chief intangible resource of IT, that effective knowledge management and strategies can significantly affect the company's sustainability. The paper also discusses strategies to determine and verify the underlying assumptions of intangible resources of companies.

Therefore, in order to produce an empirically diversified study, the researcher has created further dimensions of intangible resources and IT capabilities. Moreover, IT capabilities can be measured by the business partnerships, including internal and external linkages, application of strategic thinking, business process integration, IT management and

infrastructure, human resource, and relationship resource. However, the intangible resources are the knowledge resources of IT, governance of those resources, and the related resources.

The problem arises when a particular sector of the industry is targeted. In this case, the context of the UK, however immensely diversified industry sectors already available, but the research knowledge and capabilities lack the knowledge of upbringing of innovation and technology. In order to be a resourceful study, the research has to be empirical and updated with the recent norms. Since the IT industry is the most fast-paced among all, major companies are often concerned about their IT personnel and which qualifications and skills are credible now. It also creates a problem when the company is lacking creative production and innovation.

Some business models are based on non-sustainability, such as “Business model canvas (BMC)”. This model comprises nine parameters: customer segment, customer relationship, value proposition, key partners, essential practices, key resources, and cost structure. The model is found beneficial for the companies because this model is deal with a few elements. Companies such as cosmetic industries and other SMEs must employ the sustainable business model to deal with the challenges and enhance social, economic, and ecological gains (Yahya, 2019). One of the studies proposed that the effective business model must comprise three components: creating value-based products and enhanced efficiency of the delivery system. This indicates that new resources, innovative technologies, and critical activities must be based on value creation. The second component is based on increasing the value proposition that includes the parameters to enhance the quality of products and services and customer segments and relationships. The value capture is the third component of the business model based on improving cost and generated revenues. The first element of strategy that is helpful for the companies to increase their strength for dealing with challenges includes the value proposition. It is linked with the offering of the company services such as delivering products or other services. The value proposition is considered the basic rule for the organisation’s development, survival, and success. The second elements considered essential for a successful business model are the value creation and effective delivery system. There must be developed in the different sectors of an organisation, such as organisational system, operations, product

preparation, management strategies, marketing schemes, procurement measures, and good communication skills.

The companies can use sustainability measures to promote the efficacy of supply chain management. Additionally, the strategies of value creation can help the companies with the sustainable operation and reporting. It indicates that organisations can use different strategies to enhance the value creation of the products and increase the delivery system (Davey and Sanders, 2012). The third main component of the business model is value capture, also termed value appropriation. The business model used this strategy to enhance the financial benefits concerning cost structure and generated revenues. The companies or SMEs and the cosmetic industry can deal with sustainable challenges by doing effective partnerships with internal and external stakeholders. The customers and suppliers, employees and others working within the organisation must be dealt with appropriately by providing incentives and performance management (Rajpal, 2013).

Few factors are helpful to maintain the stability in the SMEs, including the legislation, the competitive dynamics of industries, considering the public opinions, and assess the technology level. Employees' engagement should be increased in a company to achieve high capabilities and ensure transparency and decision-making skills. Success can also be achieved by extending the network of stakeholders within the companies (Jannette, 2014). The study showed that companies must need to enhance environmental awareness to meet market demands. It was noticed that the traditional practices in the organisation or industries also used the strategies of value proposition, value creation and value capture.

However, there is a significant difference between the traditional business model and the sustainable business model that help industries to deal with sustainability challenges. The traditional value proposition-based business model focused on the customers and the willingness of the customer to pay. On the other hand, the business model based on sustainability deals to achieve flexibility and stability in the stakeholders' relationship. In addition, the traditional business model also used value creation and enhance delivery services which were based on the utilisation of resources and capabilities (Lin et al., 2012)

The networks can link the suppliers and the customers. However, the integration of a systematic thinking process among the employees in the sustainable business model enhanced the employees' engagement, motivation, and learning. Furthermore, an effective business model can be used in industries such as the cosmetic industry to enhance companies' competitive advantages. The traditional business model was focused on achieving more benefits in contrast with the competitors. However, in the recently proposed business model, the focus is on competing with the competitors and collaborating with more industries. Sustainability can be achieved by using sustainable and green cosmetics, one of the modified approaches to deal with environmental challenges in the cosmetic industry (Dunhil, 2018). Sustainable cosmetics are those products that are prepared by using the natural ingredients generated from renewable products (Sahota, 2014). The cosmetic brands must incorporate the eco-based approaches in their products and manufacturing the other supplies.

2.10. Analysis of Sustainability Reports from major Cosmetic Companies

In 1987, when the report "Our Common Future: Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development" was published by Brundtland, an emphasis was made on a sustainable way of living. It was an urgent call by the General Assembly of the United Nations:

- Develop long-term environmental strategies to achieve sustainable development by the year 2000 and beyond;
- Recommend ways to move toward greater co-operation among developing countries and countries at different stages of economic and social development and to achieve common and mutually supportive objectives that are based on the interrelationships between people, resources, and the environment;
- To examine ways and means by which the international community can address environmental concerns more effectively;
- This discussion will focus on defining shared perceptions of long-term environmental issues, what actions should be taken in the coming decades, and what aspirational goals should be set by the international community to protect and enhance the environment.

Since there has been awareness among consumers about environmental and social issues, which has pushed and driven the cosmetic industry to be greener and more sustainable. As a result, there have already been marketing strategies to motivate brands to create a green market. The government's policies and regulations have also played a significant role in driving sustainability in the cosmetic industry. (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

Rising GDP and change in lifestyle has added to the tremendous growth of the skincare market. The cosmetic companies use attractive marketing strategies and change the packet style, allowing natural fit recyclable packaging to advance cosmetic products. Also, there is seen increased side effects as most of the consumers have read about the ingredients. However, recently, cosmetic companies are investing in research and development across the product line (Goljic, 2020). There has been growing awareness among the consumer regarding environmental and social issues. Even though the vital decision of buying a cosmetic product is personal, the consumers prefer to have environmental and ethical considerations to be regarded (Liobikien and Bernatonien, 2017). As a result, consumers are pushing towards cosmetic companies to be sustainable, reflecting in the marketing strategies of various more prominent cosmetic companies like L'Oreal, Estee Lauder, Unilever to name a few. The brands are getting motivated to take actions regarding sustainable strategies to strengthen their position in the market, using green cosmetics as a new marketing strategy (Csorba and Boglea, 2011). Although there is an increase in green cosmetics, the FDA restriction list of compounds comprises only 13 chemicals that adversely impact skin compared to 1623 substances disallowed by the European cosmetic Commission (Goljic, 2020).

With the rise of social media influencers and social channels like YouTube and Instagram have become the new advertisers of cosmetic products. The traditional retailers are changing and driving these marketing innovations in various ways, from increased transparency to target pricing according to the desired customers. According to cosmetic industry statics from 2018 to 2019, H&M's assortment of cosmetic products increased by 94.8%. The competitive environment of the cosmetic market is increasing significantly. The L'Oreal foundation spent \$9.16 billion on advertising in 2017. The other significant players in the cosmetic advertisement are Coty Inc., Shiseido Co., Estee Lauder and LVMH. The cosmetic company is not only bound to

women customers but also the men's Personal Care industry. It is predicted to rise by \$166 billion by 2022, rising seven point 7% annually for beard care products (Goljic, 2020). Although the rise of the global cosmetic market is evident, the pandemic has impacted the cosmetic market, and it is set to decline by 20 to 30%, with the numbers being even higher in the US. The cosmetic industry was impacted by the global recession in 2009 and is considered one of the few recession-proof industries. Due to the global pandemic, 17% of women stopped wearing makeup, which affected the retail shops, dropping down the cosmetics sale by 36% but increased online sales by 90%. The survey shows that 66% admitted wearing less makeup than before the pandemic outbreak, and 16% started wearing more makeup amidst the pandemic (Cvetkovska, 2021).

Outline for analysis of Sustainability Reports

The sustainability reports of the major cosmetic companies like L'Oreal, Estee Lauder, P&G, Unilever (See Appendix E) will be analysed for this research to get a clear insight into the sustainability operations done. The reports showed the work these companies are doing regarding sustainability and innovation to get the cosmetic industry more in line with sustainability's social, economic and environmental factors. The researcher used the most recent sustainability reports of the biggest cosmetic companies listed in the Appendix E.

To analyse the sustainability reports from the cosmetic companies, the researcher used Nvivo. The researcher used word frequency search with stemmed words to get the most common words used in the sustainability reports, as shown in appendix F. The researcher focused on stemmed words like sustainability, economic, social, package, emission, and innovation from the results generated. Then each report was analysed, looking for the sustainable practices the companies were following and were made into code (appendix G). The graph below shows the range of these words used across the reports.

On the initial reading of the reports, the researcher found few common words that word used in all the reports depicting the company's criteria to be sustainable. Most companies use the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) to guide them through their overall

sustainability (Appendix E). Another term present in 18 out of 20 reports was circularity, depicting circular economy and life cycle thinking. Also, innovation was part of all the reports may it be technological innovation or product innovation. Reports show how the more prominent companies follow sustainability guided through innovative ideas and circularity.

The Amorepacific group commits to three focus areas which are sustainable lifestyle, inclusive growth and circular economy. The approach is towards impressing sustainable lifestyle, promoting inclusive economic and social development and preserving the environment for future generations. It also prioritises sustainable consumption by addressing the issues to consumers and integrating social and environmental sustainability. The goal is to incorporate at least one environment of social benefit into 40% of the new products stop, but the innovation doesn't stop at product level so the decision to integrate environmental and social sustainability to the design and operations to the stores. As seen in other reports, the main objective is to reduce the environmental footprint caused by water usage, CO2 emission, and responsibly sourcing ingredients. There is also a need for consumer awareness regarding sustainable lifestyle. However, not everything is possible until everyone comes together to support; henceforth, Amorepacific group has introduced guidelines to its suppliers to assess their sustainable practices. These sustainable goals also help keep suppliers on the same track and collaborate with them to improve their working conditions. As for the social aspect, the primary commitment is to support 200,000 women and various foundations to prevent cancer in females. The Amorepacific group also promotes circular economy through the circular use of resources to reduce environmental impact and efficiently use resources. The resources are not only the ingredients but also water usage in production and waste produced at the end of the life cycle for the product packaging.

Avon's primary purpose that drives the company is making a positive difference in the life of women. Women's economic development is embedded in their DNA, which guides their social sustainability by supporting causes like the Pink Light project in their own Avon promised to help and violence against women and girls. Moreover, there are also concerns about the impact

of plastic pollution and future plan to sell responsibly sourced cosmetic products. The report is guided chiefly to the betterment of women on the charities Avon parts with for the same. They are moving towards environmental sustainability and their 2020 goal, which identifies reduction of greenhouse gases, increased recycling, eliminating PVC packaging, moving from paper brochure to e-interactive shoppable brochure, reducing water consumption, waste and recovery in tackling deforestation. Avon is now a member of the Sustainable Packaging Initiative for Cosmetics (SPICE) and terracycle in Brazil to achieve their packaging goals. To develop a circular economy to close the loop in plastic packaging, Avon is also a member of Rede De Cooperacao Para o Plastico (REDE).

Beiersdorf sustainability agenda focuses on the environment, society and consumers while contributing to The United Nations SDGs and the ten principles of the UN global compact. The company aims to be more transparent, for which they launched a 600 ingredient glossary of Nivea products available online. This was the response to the growing interest in the sustainability of the products by consumers. Transparency is not only related to what goes in the product but also the packaging formulation which is evidently indicated in their report with the measures and initiative taken by the company to create so. Talking about environmental sustainability, like other more prominent brands, Beiersdorf aims to reduce greenhouse emissions throughout its value chain by 2025. Going forward towards reducing plastic packaging, 90% of the bottles in Europe will be made of recycled PET; also, they achieved the target of sustainable sourcing of raw materials based on palm oil. The most outstanding achievement was that production was powered by 100% renewable electricity. With the cooperation of Evonik, Beiersdorf is part of a project to convert carbon dioxide into care products through artificial photosynthesis to harness renewable energy CO2 and water funded by the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF). The company uses circular economy as part of environmental sustainability to create more sustainable packaging using recycled material, refillable and reusable packaging. Also, as a social initiative, they are part of various projects like the carbon disclosure project and global shea alliance relating to environmental sustainability. Adding onto that, there are various collaborations with

international non-profit organisations like Plan International Germany, Care and Ashoka, to name a few.

Being a creation driven company, Chanel aims to design experiences with desirable products and generate impact on the environment and society. Chanel takes sustainability as its ambitious goal with the mission outlined in the Paris Climate Agreement to reduce carbon emission by 1.5 degrees set out to be achieved by 2030. The company has been carbon neutral since 2019 through natural-based solutions like sourcing 40% of their global electricity through renewable resources. Keeping in alignment with the sustainability goals, Chanel also supports The United Nations SDGs to protect and preserve nature. Mission to a low carbon economy Chanel is partnering with technological innovators and scientific partners for solutions. Chanel is mainly working around carbon emission while working towards the betterment of people and communities impacted by climate change. They have collaborated with SULAPAC as it is essential to generate new technologies and innovative packaging materials that are biodegradable and bio-sourced. It is a great way to reuse FSC certified wood chips and plant-based materials. A long-term view, an inclusive transition and a shared challenge are what to be the guiding lines towards the sustainable approach of Chanel.

Colgate sustainability report clearly defines their work under the United Nations SDGs to enhance their business performance. The main three pillars they perform according are people performance and planet. As evidenced by the name under people, they work according to their values to give back to the communities by supporting their employees' health and Wellness, commitment towards human rights, equal pay, and education. They also have a supplier diversity program which consists of companies operated by minorities, women, disabled people, veterans and members of the LGBT community. They encouraged their suppliers to add value and innovation to support their common goal. Talking about environmental sustainability, under their planet pillar, they commit to no deforestation, climate change, sustainable use of water, zero waste, sustainable buildings, and educating consumers towards reducing waste. They hope to drive sustainability to product and process innovation and improve the new products' sustainability profile. Like many others, they are also working towards promoting

renewable energy and reducing greenhouse gas emissions through manufacturing. Their next goal is to have zero waste sent from manufacturing to landfills.

Coty's sustainability strategy guided by UN SDGs is structured around: the cosmetic of our product, our people and our planet. Their vision is to be a more circular business and create a sustainable and inclusive world. The sustainability criteria will be embedded into the innovation process to provide ingredient sources to create better formulations for the customers. As for the environment, they are committed to reducing carbon emissions by 2030 and working towards the water footprint and waste generation across the supply chain and taking a lifecycle thinking approach towards the environmental effect to include sustainability into the circular principles for the products. They have created a Beauty That Lasts index, which comprises four main parts Good For The Planet, including reducing packaging; Good For People and society including cruelty-free; Good To Be Natural, including biotechnology; Good For Me, including clean beauty. Like Avon, they have also partnered with SPICE to create sustainable environmentally friendly packaging and part of the Ellen MacArthur foundation to understand the potentials of circular economy principles.

It is evident from the reports that change is coming, but it is slow as a lot of more prominent companies in sustainability reports point out to the changes being made in the new products, while there are millions of plastic bottles still sitting on the shelf of retail shops which were made out of virgin plastic and would probably end up in the landfill. It is still hopeful to see sustainability being the criteria while launching new products to reduce the environmental impact.

“Strong governance will be essential to track our progress, hold ourselves accountable and ensure sustainability is embedded into our business at all levels.”

It was evident from most of the reports that the companies are focusing on achieving net-zero carbon emission, zero industrial waste to landfill and water usage to be the main environmental impacts to work at. Also, as the talk of transparency across the cosmetic industry is increasing, companies are moving forward to put the innovative technologies to address issues within the supply chain and identify responsible sourcing towards the ingredients. Also, as plastic pollution

is tremendously increasing and harming the seas, another sector led by innovation is the packaging to use recyclable reusable and refillable products. The companies are also educating their employees and training them on sustainability and corporate social impact. The social side of sustainability has never been a problem in these companies, which is evident through their reports that outline various charities and organizations that they are part of to build a better world for all. Many companies are working with EcoVadis, evaluating, identify, review and control sustainability throughout their suppliers. Estee lauders goal towards sourcing key ingredients met with a tremendous technological advancement, as cosmetics have various ingredients that come from various sources, making the supply chain complex and hindering traceability and transparency. Este Lauder used blockchain technology to trace their Madagascan vanilla supply from harvest to production.

2.11 Theoretical Framework

2.11.1 Green Consumerism Behaviour

Consumer behaviour has experienced a substantial change; environmental and health awareness has gained an influential role. Consumers even tend to think regarding the future generations, and they even consider the protection of the state of the environment dutifully. The trend to use cosmetics has earned momentum all over the world; however, the definite quantity that is being used is not defined through any of the factual statistical data. As per the theory of planned behaviour (TPB), behavioural intention tends to have three factors: attitudes to a behaviour, subjective norms, and PCB that is the perceived behaviour control (Mansvelt, 2011).

In 2018, CTPA, that is, the Cosmetic Toiletry and Perfumery Association has discussed that the consumer attitudes tend to use the product attributes, which involves the functions, elements, packaging style, and materials with regards to the fragrance, as well as price, for influencing the purchase behaviour (Singhal and Malik, 2018). The green purchase attitudes defined that the performance regarding the green purchase behaviour can be assessed either positively or negatively. The environmental awareness and the sensitivity of the price reflect the level with regards to the green purchase attitudes. Knowledge tends to influence the overall

decision-making procedure of the consumers. Significant green products even come right at the intention of green purchasing (Marto, 2019). Green trust and green purchase determination have a link that certainly inclined through the perceived price (Smith, 2010). The greater level of the perceived price tends to result in a higher level of trust from the customer in the case of the green products, thus, has a more significant impact on the purchase intent.

The protection with regards to the environment as well as the trends of green marketing has resulted in changing the demand along with the behaviour of the consumers. The customers are highly interested in the environmentally friendly lifestyle and the products because they pay heed to the views regarding environmental protection but even want the personal benefits from such green products (Yaacob and Zakaria, 2011). The green initiatives can be witnessed in different areas, like the usage of green energy at the time of the production and manufacturing, or the appearance with regards to the environmentally friendly packaging based on zero wastage (Yaacob and Zakaria, 2011).

The cosmetics industry is in the quest to search for sustainable solutions for increasing bio-efficiency while also keeping into consideration the basics of the circular economy (Sarkar, 2012). Awareness regarding consumption tends to prefer the natural and biologically humiliating packaging rather than the plastic packaging, that in the aptitude of their nature like waste, which causes loads of damages to the environment (Riberio and Marto, 2019). The increasing level of environmental awareness in society works as an incentive for the customers who tend to use green cosmetic products. The rapidly growing industry on the international market is the market regarding green skincare products instead of the other green cosmetic products.

Customers prefer personalised cosmetic products, and it has become an extensive practice. They desire to choose different ingredients in the product as per their particular requirement on their skin, colour, hair, etc. The customers tend to consider the customized products more effective than the products found on the shelves of the store. Thus, while connecting the theoretical information with the research topic, it can be stated that the palette with regards to the green cosmetics that includes the ingredients, active ingredients, style of the packaging, as well as technological solutions, is exceedingly expanding with the constantly

changing demands of the market (Malyan and Duhan, 2018). Moreover, the legal regulation can even work as a guarantee of safety. Furthermore, environmental protection is turning out to be more superficial within the cosmetic industry (Kraaijenhagen, 2018).

2.11.2. Conceptual Framework

The business model must be incorporated with the key ideas that bring value in creating the products in the private and public sectors (Schaltegger, Lüdeke-Freund and Hansen, 2011). This strategy is used as a critical driver to bring innovations by enhancing efficiency and consistency. Sustainability can be achieved by extending the customer values and enhance the modification in the designing and preparation of the products. The quality of the products must be increased that helps the customers to gain the benefits by purchasing the products. The relationships with the customers must be based on collaboration so that sustainable revenues can be generated. Assertively, the aspect assumes that the value creation of the business model is vital to the diversification of sustainable measures at an organisation (Medula, 2020).

Developing the conceptual framework started with a most generic idea of combining sustainability which has three parts, economic, social and environmental to whole life chain of the cosmetic product. As derivative from the literature based on sustainability, the need to construct the idea that incorporates the advantage towards the environment but also taking into aspect the social factors, economical structure and longevity of the business as clearly stated when writing the Our Common Future Report by Brundtland (1987):

“The environment does not exist as a sphere separate from human actions, ambitions, and needs, and attempts to defend it in isolation from human concerns have given the very word “environment” a connotation of naivety in some political circles.”

Figure 6: Conceptual Framework

The life cycle of cosmetic products starts from sourcing, production, packaging, distribution, consumption and finally to recycle (Bom et.al, 2020). However, the overall circularity regarding the full consumption of the product depends on the assessment of different aspects of sustainability at each level of life cycle. The concept of life cycle thinking along the supply chain to the end of the life of the product is to avoid the effects mainly on the environmental sustainability causing due to product or its packaging.

Figure 7: Cosmetic product life cycle with a sustainable approach - Life Cycle Thinking (LCT)

Source: Bom et al. 2020

Figure 7 illustrates the need of circularity that can help sustainable implant development in the business model of the cosmetic industry. This framework profoundly explains the steps in a complete life cycle of a manufactured product from scratch to end in terms of sustainability. This is based on the factor used to combine the sustainable strategies by modifying the ecological innovation approaches. This highlights that sustainability involves the very first step of manufacturing that is the raw material acquisition. Suppose the material required for the production meets the standards of sustainability. In that case, it is more likely to have a safer production within toxic and hazard-free chemicals, eventually leading to environmentally friendly products. Following this, the packaging that is crucial to consider in aesthetics should be recyclable or biodegradable material. After finishing, the distribution is the next step in life cycle assessment that is necessary to consider because transport causes CO₂ emissions that are the starter of major environmental issues as global warming, deforestation, and glacier melting. This framework also highlights motivation, which is applied in terms of awareness as a most crucial factor. Following this framework will enable safer and environment-friendly production with minimum waste generation and threats to water bodies and landfills after disposal. There must be additions of the factors such as value proposition, value-creating, and value delivery (Morgan, 2021).

The concept of circularity is also evident in the sustainability reports of bigger companies. Many are now collaborating with the Ellen MacArthur foundation to learn more about the circular economy. The research done by Bom et al. (2019) shows the cosmetic product life cycle with a sustainable approach from design to post consumer use of the cosmetic product. Recycling and repurposing waste adds value to a circular economy model by recovery and revaluation of waste, developing five circular economy models in organizations, namely: circular supply chains, recovery and recycling, product life cycle extension, shared platforms and product as a service (Lacy and Rutqvist, 2015). In addition to improving differentiation, reducing costs, generating new revenues, as well as reducing risks, such models help companies make better decisions and reduce the impact of their decisions on the supply of virgin resources. These five circular business models have seen substantial adoption over the past decade, although there are still many opportunities for change. Start-ups were initially

responsible for driving innovation through circular business models. In recent years, big multinationals have also stepped up their efforts (Sehnem et al., 2022).

Meanwhile, the social cause association in business organisations is also responsible for the compilation of these initiatives. However, cosmetic producers need to adopt the agro-organic business model to equip the organisations with efficient and viable alternatives seeking change. For instance, sustainable cities as the SDG 16 of the UN can only be accomplished if each organisation aligns its strategy according to the sustainable perspectives promoted worldwide (Peter deck, 2017).

2.12 Chapter summary

In short, the chapter has discussed the sustainable and environment-friendly approach in the cosmetic industry. Nowadays, companies realise the environmental incentives that motivate consumers to purchase green products. They are also aiding the global trend concerning environmental protection. The reason based on the social concern in the environmental awareness is the reduction of mineral as well as the petrochemical resources that are used for the manufacturing of the cosmetic products. Cosmetic as well as personal body care products are broadly used in surplus amounts. Thus, the level of the recurrent usage tends to cause leaking back into the environment in exact enormous quantities. Many products are there which are biologically reactive. It refers to the fact that they tend to work as a hazard to the ecosystem as well as to the health of the human.

Various companies are trying to produce a diversity of disposable by-products that are recycled in valuable mixtures. The description and valorisation of those products shape them into extremely valued products for the dissimilar areas of biotechnology such as cosmetics and even help decrease their impact on the environment and the other associated treatment costs. SMEs need to think strategically based on the customers' demands that what can be proposed through which they can earn well, sell in tremendous amount and is also sustainable. A green consumer approach is suggested in this chapter, with which SMEs can study the mindset of the consumers that demand sustainable cosmetic products. Therefore, the study aimed to trace out the initial measures that cosmetic companies can adopt to reduce pollution while halting

environmental degradation. The socio-environmental perspective is also gaining prominence because social media has enabled its users to contest the stereotypical attitudes of the organisations, and the increase in environmental advocacy such of Greta Thunberg's vocal concerns has generated awareness among the masses.

CHAPTER 3: RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

The research methodology is one of the foremost parts of the research that highlights the methods used by the study for conducting the analysis. According to Raimundo, Echeimberg and Leone (2018) it has been observed that there are various kinds of research methods that can be used by the researchers for addressing the research problem. Turnbull, Chugh and Luck (2021) have highlighted that it is based on the nature of research and the methods of data collection that is employed by the researcher. The following chapter has highlighted the methods followed in the research and has mentioned the accuracy of research methods for solving the research problems. The success of the research is based on the transparent methodology that the researcher uses for conducting the analysis. The research methodology section allows the researcher to select the possible research method and research philosophy designed for the research. According to Raimundo et al. (2018), researchers can use various research methods to address the research problem. According to the study conducted by Turnbull et al. (2021), they highlighted that the methodology is based on the nature of the research and the data collection methods employed by the researcher. At the end of this chapter researcher also highlight the methods followed in the research and has mentioned the accuracy of research methods for solving the research problems. This section of the study aims to deliver the sounding methodological approaches in order to carry out the research in a suitable environment. The approach that the study has conducted is a qualitative approach that has been promising in conducting the influence of small and medium-sized enterprises in the cosmetic and other forms of industries. Behind every research approach, there is a necessary need for establishing a perfect approach to analyse the collected information. Thus, the methodological data is constantly analysed on the basis of a practical research approach. The section of methodology is designed to express the critical points catered to in the study. Usually, it expresses the primary design strategy and the sources of collection of required information present within the evident literature.

The term positivism has been observed significantly, adopted in most of the analysis studies such as experiments, quantitative analysis, and empirical studies. In the context of

positivism, the studies conducted by researchers believed in the facts and figures, and the studies also depend on social reality. In the case of strategies associated with small and medium-sized enterprises, the approach related to positivism can be believed to be promising as the data is driven from the realisation of present scenarios (Ryan, 2018). On the other hand, interpretivism is the subjective approach and is influenced by the understandings of history, personal traits, experiences, and culture. Thus, based on the nature of this study conducted, the methodological approach best utilised can be the approach of positivism. It is because the data concerning the cosmetic industry has been taken into account through current changes and trends of small and medium-sized enterprises and are based on the facts with respect to relevant models or theories. Furthermore, the methodology chapter of the study has focused on the critical design parameters essential to predicting the nature of research and analysing the norms of research through considerations of multiple eminent factors, which are divided into various headings and discussed in depth below. Thus, the study involves sections based on the selection of eminent research approaches, the basic design of the research for assessing the available data, collection and analysis of data using the qualitative approach for the impact of SMEs on the cosmetic industry, ethical values and limitations of the conducted research, size of population and sample considered under review, and lastly, the summative conclusion of the whole chapter including essential methods implied.

3.2 Research design

According to Nayak and Singh (2021), the research design highlights the nature of research by the research topic. Depending upon the type of data available, the research may be a qualitative, quantitative or mixed version of qualitative and quantitative research. The current research has employed the qualitative research method because it allows the researcher to perform the subjective analysis. As recommended by Edmondson and McManus (2007) and Easterby-Smith et al. (2015), looking at the exploratory nature of the research, qualitative method is used. In order to understand and describe the sustainable business model innovation process of organizations, we need to conduct interviews and observations that consider the behavior and perceptions of their agents (Creswell, 2014; Platts, 1993). For the analysis, the

researcher designed a short questionnaire to select the small and medium-sized organisations to perform adequate research based on the data they gather from the research process. This questionnaire comprises of 15 mixed questions, few of which are multiple choice to simple questions about the company and its sustainability overview. This short questionnaire was generated to get an idea of the companies to be able to select a range from various regions, product and sustainability themes. Through different questions, the researcher implements an effective innovation business model that is innovative and sustainable for the business. To gain accurate findings on the theoretical underpinning that created a massive value for the research and identify the different problems faced by the cosmetic sector. Qualitative interview is the main data collection for this research after the sustainable reports of the cosmetic companies.x

The interview questions are greatly influenced by the literature already present in the area of focus. Literature reviews provide a theoretical basis for the development of conceptual framework which is elaborated in the previous chapter and influences the research approach.

Preparing for the research: The research preparations is derived from the research questions, to answer them and fulfil the research objectives the data needed partially comes from the previous data sources and interviews. The research is qualitative in nature because the researcher collects the secondary data by reviewing the previous data available in the form of sustainability reports and research done around the main key aspects. With the research's clearly defined aim and objective, the researcher also took interview as the source of primary data to combine and reflect on the derivative results. Initially, the research was based on derived data from the sustainability reports of various cosmetic companies and research done around it. But, due to insufficient data related to the sustainability work done in the specific cosmetic industry, the secondary data was extracted from the mix of various researched done from the time the word sustainability first came into light. To understand the objectives clearly interview structure was implemented to gain insight into the current norms in the cosmetic industry.

Collecting primary data: For the current research, the main source of qualitative data are questionnaires, interviews, and previous research. To find accurate data is more important

to conduct effective research. Data collection methods that are popular include qualitative interviews, in which interviewees are given the opportunity to discuss their experiences and views (Hox and Boeijs, 2005). The research articles were assessed for their rigor and how they described the process of secondary analysis or specific strategies to improve the data. The researcher also used different contextual materials such as transcriptions, prototypes, insights and reflections, and observation notes to evaluate the research problem effectively.

Analysis of data and generation of results: A compelling proposed research data will be analyzed based on thesis and research objectives for a sustainable business model. Studies that are based on theoretical propositions or conceptual frameworks can be properly analyzed in a systematic manner. The conceptual framework can be defined as a set of concepts, assumptions, expectations, beliefs, and theories supporting and informing the research conducted. In a quantitative sense, content analysis is a method of data collection intended to provide numbers to statistical procedures. Unlike this, qualitative approaches do not clearly delineate data collection from analysis, which can happen simultaneously and in an interactive manner. In this regard, content analysis is defined as the process of analyzing data collected by other means like in-depth interviews and psychoanalysis (Mayer, 2016).

Reports: Writing and illustrating papers and reports will lead to the formation of thesis and research reports. Starting with a clearly stated research question should be the first step in writing a research report. Studying a topic is shaped and directed by the research questions. Understanding the theoretical and empirical basis of the study is made easier with a literature review. Providing sufficient detail about how data were collected and analyzed is a requirement of any good research (Drisko, 2005).

3.3 Research philosophy

According to Abu (2019), the process of collecting, observing, and using data or information about a phenomenon is highly essential for the methodology and study philosophy. The philosophy of research offers specific information on data collection that may be examined and completed. Furthermore, the process of research philosophy is based on assumptions, and

there are four different approaches to process research philosophy: Positivism, Pragmatism, Realism, and Interpretivism. The subject or topic influences the researcher's choice of research philosophy. Furthermore, in the western heritage of science, two primary ideologies have been identified: interpretive, also known as anti-positivist, and positivist, also known as scientific.

Furthermore, realism research philosophy is founded on a human mind's notion based on reality. The branch of epistemology contains a statement of the scientific method. This concept is further broken down into two categories: critical and direct. Second, interpretivism research philosophy refers to a norm that specifies that a researcher focuses on a particular aspect of social world analysis. The researcher's interests determine the research philosophy. In addition, pragmatism has used a variety of data collecting approaches. In this case, both qualitative and quantitative research designs can be employed. The pragmatism that thinks that both types of data have equal value provides both types of data the same amount of significance. Finally, positivism is a research ideology that is founded on factual facts obtained via analyses (Ryan, 2018). Since the researcher has based his research on qualitative research design, the best philosophy for this kind of research design will be interpretivism. Qualitative research design uses interviews, surveys and questionnaires which are the best source to obtain social view on the topic. These sources provide an individual's opinions which is also the goal of interpretivism. Interpretivism believes that truth is complex to understand unless people and their behaviours towards the truth are interpreted.

3.4 Research approach

The research strategy is concerned with the study procedures and practices that remove the choice of data collection and analysis techniques from the equation. This section of the research methodology focuses on identifying the research approach that will be used to conduct the study. The method is chosen based on the researcher's strategy for determining when the hypothesis will be created and tested. The research approach may be classified into two categories, based on the current study (Manning and Stage, 2015): inductive research and deductive research. Rather than utilising hypotheses at the outset, the inductive research

technique focuses on hypothesis development as a consequence of the research investigation (Zhao, 2019). When the data gathered is qualitative, it also refers to utilising this approach.

The other sort of research technique is deductive, which focuses on establishing a hypothesis based on existing theories and then constructing a hypothesis based on existing theory at the start of the investigation. Due to the extreme quantitative character of the data, researchers frequently choose this research strategy (Gregory and Muntermann, 2011). The hypotheses that are established at the start of the investigation are then tested. Various tests are running on the data to conclude whether the hypothesis is correct or not. A comprehensive conclusion of the findings is provided, along with the recommendations.

However, this research is based on qualitative data collected through interviews, surveys, and questionnaires. The best research approach to be used with qualitative research is the inductive approach, as it focuses on developing the hypothesis by the end of the research. The data that is collected from the sources mentioned earlier is analysed in detail, and a conclusion is concluded along with the hypothesis at the end of the research. A data-driven approach determines that the study's goal is to gain an understanding of a phenomenon using an inductive approach through thematic analysis. It is expected that a new theory related to the research problem will be generated by the end of the research process.

3.5 Data collection and analysis

The data collection and analysis method is based on the nature of the research that the researcher wants to achieve (Turnbull et al.,2021). The researcher observed that the nature of the following research is subjective, and the findings and analysis are also based on the assessment related to the qualitative investigation. The following research has been designed by using qualitative data with the help of secondary data already present and interviews designed to address the research questions. The researcher decided on a qualitative investigation based on the data collection selected for the current research. Through interviews, it helps in designing the themes and gaining appropriate responses for the research.

Literature review is a method of analyzing published data by measuring authorship, affiliation, and citations, as well as keywords, in order to highlight articles and show linkages between articles on a specific topic (Bellis, 2009; Fetscherin and Usunier, 2012). It is used for describing, evaluating, and monitoring the state of a particular field over time, using metaanalysis to identify the key components and theoretical frameworks of a given research area (Fetscherin and Heinrich, 2015). In addition to identifying the articles that describe the business model field, the bibliometric analysis also revealed the most cited authors, top keywords cited, and the journals in which they appeared.

Data were collected from the Elsevier Scopus database and Google Scholar using the main keywords related to the research. the main keywords searched work business model, business model innovation, sustainable business model and circular economy. At the time reset started the amount of secondary data present related to the above keywords based the research prognosis. The stats take into account the limits 2 the published reviews articles and journals that are in English only. Hence for to say the other publication times in other languages were excluded and could be taken as a cap for this research.

The Elsevier Scopus and Google Scholar databases are adequate for the construction of initial data collection for the literature review in the sustainable business model field. The search started with “sustainability” as the mean term and through snowballing and random sample check the duplicates were avoided. Followed by more in depth research articles based on business models and cosmetic industry. An extensive literature review led to identifying the initial sample of papers that were then studied in depth. Moreover, since business models are a recent research topic, it is essential to analyze its emergence and progress in advance of analyzing its content.

The sustainability reports of big companies in the cosmetic industries have been publishing for few years now. These reports are the insight into the work that is being done in the cosmetic industry at this point and can be referenced back to the few years back. Followed by the articles and research is done on sustainability, these reports are the evidence of how a sustainable business model is incorporated to achieve the goals. Hence an overview and

analysis of these reports it brings into light not only the challenges, but also the work done towards a sustainable goal.

Thematic analysis will be used to analyse the data based on different methods. This section of the study involves describing and analysing the methods used for collecting and assessing data from the analysis section of the study regarding the sustainability model and its impact on the cosmetic industry. Based on the facts, two major types of data are used extensively in the almost maximum number of studies. These include qualitative and quantitative data (Choy, 2014). According to (Saunders et al., 2014), the available data collection methods involve improvements in data quality and lead to promising results. The data gathered through primary analysis has been found significant in assessing the central purpose of the study (Bazeley, 2013). Secondly, secondary data is the collection of information on the basis of available resources such as publications, social media platforms, websites, and journals (Smeyers, P., 2008). The study under review is based on the qualitative assessment of crucial information generated. Thus, the primary source of the method involved in collecting the qualitative data was the utilisation of interviews. Interviews are commonly used as a data collection tool in most qualitative studies (Gill and Baillie, 2018). They are the purposive discussions between two or more people. The factors associated with collecting data through interviewing are promising as during an interview, the direct interactions involve assessing information directly, highlighting the deep motives of an individual. Thus, the direct means of assessment involves the clear understanding of the interviewer about the next person, and it clarifies the interviewer about the condition of the individuals by assessing through different queries (Gill and Baillie, 2018).

The study's researcher conducted semi-structured interviews as a qualitative assessment by considering respondents from various selected companies who were part of the cosmetic sector. An objective goal of qualitative interviews is to access subjective information about difficult to observe phenomena in context (Easterby-Smith et al., 2015; Tracy, 2013). The use of qualitative interviews is an exploratory form of enquiry compared to strictly questionnaire-based methods, because they provide an opportunity to expand upon answers and follow up on the topics that are raised (Easterby-Smith et al., 2015).

The interviews were conducted in order to allow discussions rather than straightforward questions and answers (Lewis, 2015). Moreover, due to the terrible situations of a virus outbreak, the meetings involving physical presence were challenging to cope with. Thus, the primary data was collected via email and zoom applications, sending follow-up questions through mail to interviewees from the selected firms. A maximum of three emails was sent to the interviewees; one was a reminder message. A total of 150 firms were contacted, most of the companies did not respond, and 25 interviews were confirmed. However, five companies rejected the interview at the last minute due to different reasons within the firm (Hagaman and Wutich, 2017).

Also, the research involved the use of a 'RADaR' technique, which helped to organise a large amount of qualitative data into structured and analysed data (Watkins, 2017). The test involved designing a transcript, which involved the materials associated with recorded interviews. The transcripts were arranged in a single document for assessing the responses efficiently. Lastly, the information generated was gathered in order to generate themes which are discussed in detail in the sections of chapter 4. Cross-case analysis has been found promising in providing assistance in achieving meaningful outputs and results generated from received data with the comparing analysis of each case (Cruzes et al., 2015). The comparison is based on the information found within the analysis, meaning that cross-case analysis gives a general assumption about cases based on the features found (Cruzes et al., 2015). Therefore, the data-driven from qualitative approach was easily extracted due to various signifying factors obtained from the study. However, the study is appropriate to include cross-sectional analysis as well, as it may allow comparison between various small and medium-sized cosmetic industries under the same level of interventions.

3.6 Sampling technique

When collecting data, there are situations when the researcher collects a large number of data that is impossible to interpret. All the data is valuable and authentic, but the researcher needs limited data to include in his research so that the research becomes simpler. For this purpose, he uses different sampling techniques to obtain small data from the large data bank (Alvi, 2016.). This data is more concentrated and authentic for the researcher to use. There are

two main types of sampling techniques which are probability and nonprobability sampling. These are the techniques that are widely used by most researchers. These techniques provide the researcher with an equitable and fair share of the population. Probability sampling is a sampling approach in which a researcher uses a method based on probability theory to choose samples from a larger population (Daniel, 2012). If a participant is to be deemed a probability sample, he or she must be chosen at random. Non-probability sampling is described as a sampling strategy in which samples are selected based on the researcher's subjective assessment rather than random selection (Vehovar, Toepoel and Steinmetz, 2016). It is a more lenient approach. The researchers' knowledge is highly reliant on this sampling approach. It is conducted out through observation, and it is extensively used in qualitative research. There are two types of non-probability sampling techniques, which are called convenience and snowball sampling techniques. Nonprobability sampling is the best suited with the qualitative research method; hence the researcher used nonprobability to sample his data. The researcher used convenience sampling techniques. Convenience sampling means the researcher will work on only those articles which are readily available to the researcher. Convenience sampling is used because it is both times saving and cost-efficient.

3.7 Sample size and population

The usual definition of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) is any business with fewer than 250 employees. There were 5.7 million SMEs in the UK in 2018, which was over 99% of all businesses. As the nature of the cosmetic industry are personal services, and it is difficult to assign a specific sector the SME's because most of the business has their online store, manufactured their products. So, the sample group of the current research are based on the target market for the research. A sample questionnaire was sent to 150-200 SMEs in the cosmetic industry in the UK, through which 40 businesses will be selected for focus interviews.

Due to the pandemic condition, the researcher was not able to collect interviews for a long time. As, majority time was spent with retail stores closed it became much harder to get in

contact with the required companies. Fortunately, researcher was able to contact the British Beauty Council which helped the researcher in contacting with the majority of the cosmetic brands. After sending interview request to more than 150 cosmetic companies, the researcher was able to interview 20 personnel from various cosmetic brands. It included the professionals from the cosmetic industry and strategic managers and CEOs of the companies (Appendix H). According to a study conducted by Zangirolami et al. (2018), they highlighted that organisations must address the sustainability issues while implementing any change in the research and provide accurate responses to the designed research question. Through interviews, the researcher will be able to assess the responses they gain from these target markets.

3.8 Ethical consideration and limitations

All phases of the research will follow ethical principles and values. This ensured that no one could be harmed or suffer adverse consequences from the research activities and assured that findings would be derived from sufficiently adequate and appropriate methodologies to warrant accurate results, conclusions and further recommendations (Cooper and Schindler 2006). According to Walter (2006), the researcher must ensure confidentiality, anonymity and protect the respondent's data. The ethical consideration increases the validity and acceptability of the research. The ethical issues are usually related to the authenticity of the information and the right of participants, responders, and industries involve in research

As the power of researchers over respondents is critical to understanding the ethical concerns that accompany social research, the principles most concerned in the protection of respondents were informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality (Walter 2006). Ethics are considered as the eminent elements of any study prior to publications or detailed research. The study has been analysed on the code of ethics and has been observed considering the ethical rules and regulations before the initiation of the research. Ethics are essential elements of research; the comprehensive research study involved a promising assessment of results based on sound research ethics. The study observed analysis of various individuals without any complications. It was declared during the study that none of the considered individuals of

various sectors was imposed to any kind of physical or psychological risks during the overall tenure of study (Matukevica et al., 2021). Secondly, all the considered individuals were informed about the details and background of the study in advance, and every individual was informed in advance about the usage of their personal data as they were told that they would have the right to access their data and to conclude the interview according to their own interest at any point of the study. The study involved the individuals participating through voluntary means, and it does not include any rewarding system or money for the study participation. The interviews conducted for qualitative assessment were conducted in a private habitat, and they were all prepared in advance. The information regarding the patterns and criteria of interviews were kept confidential and were not used outside the committee premises for other studies. However, based on the qualitative assessment of the critical data, the study faced some problems of obscurity while dealing with the data. The study data was based on scientific findings, and it would be hard to analyse the evidence generated in complete security. Thus, one limitation that can be said to be the important limitation was the accuracy of collected data. The accuracy was difficult to determine since the data was generated on the basis of interviews only.

When conducting interviews, it is impossible to analyse if the interviewees remember facts or speaking truth or speaking lies in the interviews. These specifics are important because the people interviewed have held high positions in the organisations and may prefer to keep some information. Also, since the time of the interview varied from 20 to 40 minutes, most of the interviews can be expected to provide biased information. This can be caused due to the loss of interest of such interviewees during the session conducted because most individuals hesitate to participate in interview sessions due to a lack of communication skills (Sahota, 2014). Interviews can not only investigate a phenomenon, but also gain insights into its interpretation from the viewpoint of the interviewee, depending on the skill and expertise of the researcher and the topic guide (Easterby-Smith et al., 2015; Kvale and Brinkmann, 2014).

Lastly, the horrific situation of virus outbreaks has caused several firms to be restricted through online means. The restriction through this pandemic has caused the researchers to conduct online interviews, which has caused significant disruptions in the data, as the

researchers are unable to analyse the data through physical means. The interviews conducted through physical means have been observed as very promising as the interviewees are based on the direct means through their facial expressions and body tone (Vindrola-Padros et al., 2020). In light of this, qualitative interviews are an excellent means of gaining rich, in-depth data for this study, due to the subjective and hard to observe nature of the phenomenon, sustainable business model innovation, and the exploratory nature of the research.

The researcher ensured the privacy of respondents in a protected place and has not been used for any other purpose. However, there were certain limitations, such as the availability of the respondents, in the sense of time and meetings bring done over call or video instead of in-person. Similarly, due to the pandemic, most of the respondents share their thoughts via an online mode that created a communication gap between the researcher and the respondent.

3.9 Summary

The researcher has utilised the data collected through the interviews and has carried out the thematic analysis in this regard. The number of selected respondents was 20 who were professionals in the cosmetic industry. The researcher also ensures the confidentiality of the respondent data and does not use it in any research and for personal benefits.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS AND FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

The following chapter has highlighted the finding and has performed the analysis of the data that has been collected during the research. The chapter is comprised of the thematic analysis which is used to design the themes according to the interview questionnaire. These themes have individually evaluated the responses of the interviewers and have presented them in light of the literature. Secondly, the assessment of the research objectives and evaluation based on the findings of the thematic analysis and the responses gained in this regard. The chapter also provides the discussions of the findings that has been used for answering the research questions and getting the results of the research that can be used for deriving the conclusion of the study. As the study is based on the aspect of initiating sustainability through the business models in the cosmetic industry that can perform well and can also gain more profitability with the help of implementing sustainability operations. According to Del Vecchio et al (2021) the means of sustainability can bring about positive changes in the industry and can also gain more consumers satisfaction for opting these products.

This chapter of the study is aimed at providing the analysis of data collected for conducting the research. The study has focused on the sustainable business models in the SMEs of the Cosmetic Industry. The background of the topic has been presented in the previous sections and the issues and problems involved. It has also set the objectives and research questions of the study setting the background to conduct the study. Literature background has also been presented previously, which has elaborated the studies' background and literature. The theoretical background of research has been set in the previous section for developing the conceptual framework for this study.

Furthermore, the methodology has been set in the previous sections for elaborating the techniques and approaches that are used for the study. It also highlights the techniques employed for analysing the data. The following chapter presents the analysis based on the technique as elaborated previously.

The chapter elaborates on the technique used to conduct the study. The study uses thematic analysis for conducting the data analysis, which elaborates the themes developed from the interviews of the participants. NVIVO software has been used for developing the codes and themes from the interviews. These themes help to explain the main findings obtained from the responses of the participants of the study. Thematic analysis is the most common kind of analysis in qualitative studies. It focuses on identifying, analysing, and interpreting the patterns of meanings for the qualitative nature of the data. This chapter explained the process of developing the themes and the table of the thematic developments. Furthermore, each theme is highlighted in the study, elaborating the responses obtained and the analysis conducted. Finally, the discussion of the objectives in line with the analysis conducted has been presented in the study.

4.2 Process of developing themes

The thematic analysis process is considered the most effective and efficient data analysis plan mainly applied in qualitative research. Under thematic analysis, the researcher creates themes from the interviews' collected data (Braun et al., 2018). Due to the relevance and data gathered in the study, this approach is selected to be the most suitable approach for evaluating the data. The study evaluates the sustainable business model in the SMEs of the cosmetic industry using the approach that is more applicable in terms of qualitative data. In this regard, thematic analysis has been selected that involves different levels or steps. For conducting this study, the framework of Braun and Clarke (2006) is followed. This framework elaborates different significant stages for conducting the thematic analysis which includes, becoming familiar with data, generating the initial codes, searching for the themes, reviewing themes, defining the themes and writing up (Terry et al., 2017). This way, including all steps in the thematic analysis technique, helps researchers maintain the correct information flow and provide proper interpretations for drawing a solid conclusion. Szedlak et al. (2015) have elaborated the six stages process for reporting, evaluating, and evaluating the raw data gathered from different participants. Firstly, it requires the review of the transcripts several times through fragmentation into comprehensive and smaller units. The review could either be

done on its own or using qualitative data research software like NVivo to help out construct the themes and main ideas of the qualitative data. The flow diagram below highlights the process as held for this study.

Figure 8 Thematic Analysis Process

These steps have been followed to conduct the thematic analysis in this study as well. The following is provided with a detailed description of each step included in the thematic analysis process as conducted in this study.

4.2.1 Attaining Familiarity with Data

The data has been collected via interviewing 20 CEO's and founders of SMEs in the cosmetic industry, and hence it becomes inevitable for understanding the data. Hence, the first stage involves transcribing the data correctly. The raw data has been ready to be understood; hence researcher read data through splitting units and then reading it again. As the interviews were conducted by the researcher, it helps in the better understanding of data to be processed. The process of re-reading the data and going again through the manuscripts again, familiarizes the data more for the process of analyzing. The process of attaining familiarity with the data helps in a subjective assessment of attitudes, opinions and behaviour of those being interviewed.

4.2.2 Initial Code Generation

The second stage is the most crucial phase in which related initial codes has been created as per the responses gathered. In the process of initial coding, it was essential to search the keywords on the basis of the frequency being used. The codes have been developed through different keywords such as enormous company drive change, carbon-neutral, certification, packaging problems and many more. These codes have been generated using NVIVO software. The guide to developing these themes and codes comes greater from the literature and the sustainability reports of the main cosmetic companies.

4.2.3 Searching for Relevant Themes

The third step of the study involves the broadening of the codes that are formulated in the previous stages of the study. The codes have been collated in this step, and critical relationships have also been identified between the codes generated. Hence, the potential themes are formulated for further review. While reading through the sustainability reports there were basic themes which guided into the formation of relevant themes which are connected throughout the cosmetic industry whether it's for larger cooperation or SME's.

4.2.4 Thorough review of the themes

In the thematic analysis, the fourth step is to evaluate the formulated themes of the previous stages. This step's primary purpose is to appropriately review the associations formulated after this stage; themes are adequately named and defined. They are judged based on their suitability for the research. Hence, the researcher for the particular study has consumed sufficient time for reviewing associations and themes for determining their relevance. The suitability of the themes could also be verified with the research questions and objectives so as to answer the main questions and fulfil the main objectives of the research.

4.2.5 Naming and defining the themes

In this stage, the potential themes are being refined, and they are also made specifically for the study. Additionally, themes are also defined based on the keywords, codes and literature review. The themes that are recognised are (1) Sustainability Challenges faced by SMEs in the cosmetic industry, (2) Challenges faced by start-up SMEs from product to supply chain in the Cosmetic Industry, (3) Environmental Sustainability Outlook of SMEs in the cosmetic sector, (4) Economic Sustainability Outlook of Cosmetic SMEs, (5) Social Sustainability Outlook of Cosmetic SMEs, (6) Measures to cope with sustainability challenges for SMEs of Cosmetic sector and (7) Measures to cope with start-up challenges for SMEs of Cosmetic sector.

4.2.6 Discussion of themes and Analysis

The last stage of the thematic analysis procedure involves a descriptive discussion about the formulated themes to search for the underlying meanings and implications of the responses. This will help in addressing the research objectives and research questions of the study.

4.3 Thematic Analysis

4.3.1 Theme 1: Sustainability Challenges faced by SMEs in Cosmetic Industry

To start with any research, it is empirical to verify the respondents to be interviewed to generate an idea that the respondent is well versed to answer any questions. The preliminary questionnaire asks a very basic question of is the company aligns with sustainable practices.

The main approach to be classified as a sustainable business and to be able to put it through to the consumers is to attain sustainability certifications. The respondents were asked about the sustainable certification of their business, to which one of the respondents has presented the following arguments.

"No, not currently. I think, you know, we are too small, honestly. So I mean, we are vegan and cruelty-free, but from a sort of eco-credentials, we just try and you know, our boxes are FSC, we use glass bottles, we are sort of approach is keeping our house in order because we are so small, we take the point of view that if we make changes, however small they are, at whatever point we can, then it adds up to a much bigger picture. So, for example, earlier this year, we switched from using the plastic packing tape to the craft paper tape. And you can see a little sticker or closures we used to they used to be clear plastic and we have just switched to paper stickers. They are so plastic is one of our little bugbears. So, we are always looking for where we can switch that out, you know, are packing beans or their potato starch packing beans. Trying to think what else we have just launched some, some razor ones for the face, which are plastic, but they are made with 80% wheat straw. So yeah, again, it is that thing of just questioning ourselves at every point along the process."

From the analysis of the above statement, it can be viewed that sustainability certification is quite a challenge for the SMEs in the cosmetic industry. This is because of the reason that they are pretty small organisations, and hence it is difficult for them to gain sustainability certifications and to engage in such activities. The above response indicated that it is difficult for small organisations to gain a sustainability certificate due to economic reasons. Also, even though the company it's not certified does not mean that they are not taking necessary steps to birds making their company more sustainable as seen with the example of removing plastic in their packaging to more sustainable paper once. Although it makes it easier for the customers with the guided certification but it not always means that the companies that do not have certification are not sustainable enough.

Worldwide, the COVID-19 pandemic has inflicted destruction in most of the industries, and verily, the beauty as well as cosmetics industry is not an exclusion. Though the beauty

industry managed better in comparison to other segments, there was a probability that 2021 will turn out to be one of the most difficult years for this industry (Gregurec, Tomičić Furjan and Tomičić-Pupek, 2021). One of the challenges for the industry considering the present situation is the reduced supplies. The manufacturing of the beauty products had many issues due to lockdown. Moreover, the closing of the cosmetic shops has resulted in the sedentary lifestyles. Accordingly, the number of customers who tend to visit the cosmetic stores has decreased. Most of the manufacturers had cancelled many events as well as launch campaigns of the beauty products. Thus, the revenue of the industry declined.

Beauty, as well as beauty products, are highly a favourable for the audience. In fact, the cosmetic products are getting a serious business chance while witnessing a stable and constant growth. It is due to the implementation of the sustainable business model that nowadays, SMEs are preferring to have social media marketing, vlogging, blogging, etc. through which, all the new cosmetic products are tried, their testing proceeds, products are promoted, and then advertised with the help of the influencers as well as celebrities (Malkar and Johri, 2019). It is the best way that any SME can adopt as its suitable business model while being in the cosmetic industry.

The respondents were also asked about the challenges they faced when starting up their business in terms of sustainability. The respondent has replied to this.

"Yeah, I think there is a couple of things like everything; when you turn to more sustainable alternatives tend to be more expensive. So the materials, finding manufacturers that use renewable energy, for example, um, you know, having more eco and kind of environmentally conscious transport, it is all more expensive. So I guess there is just like a price that we have to pay in terms of, you know, our product cost in order to be more sustainable. And I think generally, like the availability, a lot of this stuff is becoming more and more available, but our brand was started in 2017. And there really was not a lot on the market at that point. And so even just finding suppliers that had good materials, or, you know, we are willing to have conversations around sustainability, it was quite hard. But I would say like, availability and price are probably the biggest challenges."

From the above response, it can be stated that sustainable products are relatively expensive which makes it challenging for the organisations to develop sustainability in their business especially in case of SMEs. It is further added that the other challenge for sustainable development is finding the suppliers that have an excellent level of materials which is environmentally friendly. even though the companies starting a sustainable cosmetic business are working to their best of ability, they cannot do that without the help of manufacturing companies which have a long way to come towards sustainable practises. also to be fully sustainable taking into life cycle of a product into account, it is important for cosmetic companies, manufacturing, transportation call mark disposal, procuring of raw materials to go hand in hand towards a sustainable outlook. Overall, from the above analysis, it can be interpreted that availability of the sustainable products and their prices are the major issues that are being faced by the SMEs of the cosmetic industry when introducing sustainability in their business.

Another Respondent has added;

"Cost mainly, we have our shampoos are housed in glass bottles. So the premise is that you buy them once. And then you can refill that bottle. So the bottle was a one time investment. And because it is glass, it does not mean it is not going to change in it is really beautiful. But obviously, a glass bottle is considerably more expensive than a plastic bottle. And obviously, we have to use a plastic pump, but it is better that it is going to be reused rather than chuck it away and just buy a new bottle every other month or so. So plastic is because it is just everywhere. Even sometimes, you would ask for an aluminium lid for one of our glass jars when you open the lid when you get the sample. It has got plastic seal around the top. Yeah, it is like just it is just everywhere. So yeah, cost plastic and order quantities. As a small business, wanting to make the right decision, and we would be happy to take the cost per unit. Make it higher if it does mean that it does reflect our ethos, but when you have got to order 15K- 20,000 With one jar, we cannot run those, that volume for all of our products at the moment, it's just too high. So sometimes that does limit us on the packaging, minimum order quantities."

From the response, it can be illustrated that the cost is the main challenge when implementing the sustainability in the organisation. SMEs are unable to bear such expenses due to which they cannot afford to be involved in the sustainable practices as it is costly. It has been identified from the above response that the availability of the product is also an issue while implementing the sustainable practices. This also indicated that such practices might also limit the packaging and minimum order quantities. It is imperative to note that even though there are packaging products available which are fully recyclable like glass and aluminium there are added components to it which are still plastic and unfortunately it is become difficult to get rid of those plastic components to make the packaging 100% recyclable. Also taking into account these recyclable packaging materials like glass and aluminium of a more pricier as the demand it's more than the supply and most of the companies do tend to choose cheaper options like plastic. Therefore making it difficult to bring down the overall price of the product for it to be available for everyone and hence due to this reason most of the sustainable cosmetic are labelled as under high rent cosmetics due to their price point an economic viewpoint. Therefore, from the above responses, it can be interpreted that the cost and the availability of the products are the significant issues for the SMEs to be engaged with the sustainable business practices.

The business of the cosmetics is evergreen as well as highly popular. It is important to sustain in the market with the better business model. The cosmetic business is a prevalent venture, therefore, to have some of the vendors, selling the alike products in the market is common. Thus, it is needed to have a thorough market research as well as analysis as a strategy of a successful business plan. SMEs must study the level of the competition in the market while observing the ways which the existing companies are using to sustain (Bennett, 2014). Moreover, a sustainable and quality business model is that helps in attracting more customers and retaining them. The cosmetic industry is quite expensive thus, price setting, ensuring quality products, etc. needs to be checked.

4.3.2 Theme 2: Challenges faced by start-up SMEs from product to supply chain in Cosmetic Industry

The respondents have been asked to elaborate on the challenges that the SMEs are facing in terms of manufacturing and supply chain. Choosing the right cosmetics manufacturer can be a challenge. Several factors must be considered before making the big decision, such as the type of product needed, how much the company is willing to spend on manufacturing, and where the product will be manufactured. To elaborate process it could be started with firstly deciding to have domestic or overseas manufacturers call mom requesting a quote from these manufacturers, negotiating terms and contracts call mom monitoring the supplier and finally deciding on the manufacturer that suits the company and its goals in the long term (McKeon, 2021). The respondents have provided with varying responses. One of the respondents has added that;

"Um, we did a lot of research to find the partners and suppliers that we use. So I guess it was just the time it takes to do the research and meet people and check everything. So I guess the main thing is just the time to sort of investigate everything."

The above response indicated that the partners and suppliers impose significant challenges that can be a challenge for the SMEs from the product to the supply chain in the cosmetic industry. The proper planning, however, is required for meeting those challenges. It is implied that the suppliers provide the products or the raw materials, and hence their cost and quality are significant aspects, so maintaining the cost and quality can be challenging. It is a constant struggle for small businesses, take instance if to reduce the overall prices an international manufacturer is chosen to procure good quality ingredients but the cost of shipping increases. Similarly, if a domestic manufacture is chosen the labour cost and raw material crossed increases but the supply cost it's taken down as it's been domestic.

Another respondent has added that;

"Vast majority, I would say. So here is a really good example. This is our cleansing oil, which is our best-selling product. So glass bottles, which obviously fully recyclable, but plastic pumps. Yeah, and there just is not an alternative to that at the moment. I mean, even for big

brands, yes, that is virtually impossible, particularly fitting it onto a glass bottle. So that is a challenge for us. And something we are always always looking at. We are actually launching a new brand towards the end of the year. And we are going to I have got a bottle here I can show you actually, we are going to be using these bottles, which is 100% post consumer plastic. And that is a brilliant company in the Netherlands. So that is just another way of trying to business a completely different way. But another way of being sustainable. "

It is implied from the above response that adopting fully recyclable products are pretty challenging in terms of the cost. The challenge is the packaging of the products that are being done using the glass products. Therefore, it is considered from the above response that recyclable packaging is also one of the challenges that the cosmetic industry faces. It is further implied from the above response that the cost and the packaging are different challenges faced by the SMEs as they are small firms and would have difficulty accessing the products that are less costly. The main packaging product for most of the businesses to make packaging sustainable comes down to reuseable or recyclable products like glass and aluminium call mom biodegradable products like cardboard packaging and potato starch fillers 2 recycled post-consumer plastic which is still an effective way as it uses the plastic already in the ecosystem chain and it's not manufactured to add onto the humongous amount of plastic already available.

4.3.3 Theme 3: Environmental Sustainability Outlook of SMEs in the cosmetic sector

The respondents were interviewed based on the environmental sustainability outlook of SMEs in the cosmetic sector, and the respondents were asked questions based on the environmental sustainability, and the respondent has answered the following question as follow:

" So, glass bottles, which are obviously fully recyclable, but plastic pumps. Yeah, and there just is not an alternative to that at the moment."

As per the response of the participant is considered essential to sustain the environment, and it enables recycling opportunities to be considered. As identified in the

literature, most of the products in cosmetics can cause harm to the environment as most of the testing is done on animals. Therefore, most organisations use recycled and environment free material in their production and effectively used biodegradable products to ensure the quality and effective pattern of environmental factors. In terms of the sustainability, SMEs are facing issues. Basically, the beauty industry tends to produce the products that have a mixture of many chemical components. Thus, nowadays people keenly show their interest in the organic, sustainable, as well as ecologically friendly personal use products. This makes the public worried regarding the safety of the beauty products. Consumers are now highly aware of the level of skincare that they need as well as the severe impacts of the harsh chemicals that are used in the beauty products (Joyce, 2019). Such awareness, mixed with the augmented environmental awareness, infers that the cosmetic brands, as well as the manufacturers, will have to use more sustainable production procedures and elements for winning the buyers and thriving in the cosmetic industry.

"We are going to I have got a bottle here I can show you actually, we are going to be using these bottles, which is 100% post-consumer plastic. And that is a brilliant company in the Netherlands. So that is just another way of trying to business a completely different way. But another way of being sustainable".

The above statement suggests even loads of challenges regarding availability of the products that are fully sustainable, the smaller companies are still trying out of the way to give the best out in the world. Taking example of this company which already has a brand that uses glass bottles, still for the other brand they're trying to achieve 100% sustainable product by using postconsumer recyclable plastic bottles. Just keen to see the initiative and drive for change in these smaller companies disregard what the challenges may be.

One of the main aspects that are assessed is the material used in the production of the products. Another respondent answered the same question using the following words:

"That is a really good question. I do not think so. Well, it depends on some of our ingredients. So for example, our super boost if I got on here, I will see previous night jobs, which is our CBD oil for face is I want to say probably 80% strawberry seed oil. And the strawberry seed

oil is a really nice ingredient because it is a by-product. So, from the kind of juice or jam industry from the strawberries, they take the seeds so they would be otherwise discarded. And they make the oil from the strawberry seeds. So, there are a few small things like that. But otherwise, I mean, obviously, with the new brand using the post-consumer plastic, there is Yeah".

The participant was asked the question that involved going deeper into sustainability that involved the usage of upcycling products. The answer of the respondent indicates that the upcycle products are being used; however, the development of these products is based on seed oils is extracted from strawberries and CBD oil. When it is about the products that people tend to buy, the consumers are highly adopting a green approach. Natural as well as organic ingredients all across the categories of the product are turning out to be more prevalent for their constructive health as well as environmental effects (Szromek, 2021). The beauty industry is replying to the consumers while making such eco-friendly products as well as packaging a reality for the ones who are fond of their makeup products and even love their planet. Moreover, this helps with the development of juice and jams, and post-consumer plastic is used, and this has caused the costs of sustainability to decrease. This could be seen as an extra step towards sustainability, the companies are not only using good raw materials which are recyclable, but they are going a step further into using the products that are a waste from one of the industries and using that waste to create something new and useful. This shows a great term of responsibility and collaboration between the two industries. Another respondent has answered the same question using the following words:

"It came from my personal story where my sister formulated skincare; when I was recovering from leukaemia, my skin was very, very sensitive, very irritated. And we just were not satisfied with using conventional skincare that has a lot of questions or, at best, just sort of filler ingredients. So there started formulating skincare for me, and she really believed in the transformative benefits of plant-based skincare. And that is what she did, she started formulating those blends, and we really see the skin health benefits from using plant-based ingredients. And now there is a lot more science and data to back up the choices that we make. For example, we use upcycled hemp seed oil in our blemish recovery oil. And that hemp seeds grown in the UK, and the seeds would otherwise have been sent to landfill because they do not

meet the food grade standard. But they are set aside, the antioxidant value increases over time, so that it really creates a beautiful luxurious oil that contains 52% more antioxidants than its standard counterparts. So that is a really good example of an oil that is better for your skin. But of course, better for the environment as well because it is saved from going to landfill."

The respondent of the participant indicates that is important for the usage of plants to be considered and it helps with the overall benefits and disadvantages to be identified. Furthermore, the seeds are considered to be helpful, and its helps with the development of plantation and helps the plants to grow at a faster rate. This has helped the cosmetics industry to grow, and most of the companies can create opportunities for reusing the products and packaging material on the basis of effective recycling. Similarly, it has also been observed that the cosmetic industry can bring about positive changes, and the transportation methods can also be environmentally friendly. The cosmetics industry is in the quest to search for sustainable solutions for increasing bio-efficiency while also considering the basics of the circular economy.

Moreover, the legal regulation can even work as a guarantee of safety. Furthermore, environmental protection is turning out to be more ostensible within the cosmetic industry. Environmental sustainability refers to utilising natural resources and protecting the ecosystem to support health and well-being. Natural resources are somewhat limited on earth, especially at the current rate of industrialisation.

The first critical step of achieving sustainability is to assess and prioritise along with the measurement and reporting. In addition, proper guidance will be provided to stakeholders about the operations and process of the business. Sustainable strategies also depend on the different components that bring success for the future. The environmental impacts of the prepared materials and used components must be assessed to analyse the impact of products on the environment.

4.3.4 Theme 4: Economic Sustainability Outlook of Cosmetic SMEs

The following theme reflects evaluating economic sustainability on the basis of the cosmetic SMEs where the respondents were asked about the importance of economic sustainability. In this basis, participant I2 has responded that:

"Yeah, that is a very, very real issue, something called MOQ. So your minimum orders quantities. Yeah. And for many, for many small businesses, it can be a real issue, not just for sustainability, but just generally, where you do not yet have the economies of scale. For us, we use recycled paper for our packaging, cardboard, that can all be recycled, and we are really intentional about that. And use as little packaging as possible, while still protecting the, the, the products themselves. So we are always looking for new innovation, but as I mentioned, MOQs can be a bit of a hurdle"

As per the response of the above participant, it is clear that the cosmetic SMEs are taking action towards the improvement of economic sustainability. The respondent has indicated that the primary focus towards the improvement of the economic sustainability is through minimum order quantities (MOQ). The use of MOQ not only enables the organisation to obtain the minimum raw material for the manufacturing the products but also increases the sustainability. The strategy also reduces wastage during production, which is overall beneficial for the economy. Furthermore, it was also determined from the responses that the organisation uses paper for packaging along with cardboard which can be recycled. As a result of these strategies, it enables the organisation in saving materials and costs, which is beneficial from an economic point of view. Another response provided by I8 illustrates the economic sustainability from the view of cosmetic SMEs:

"There is such a thing with a lot of smaller brands, specifically, that we went with, like the patches hired to work with the raw material suppliers will know kind of everyone in the cosmetic industry as like, especially the bigger ones. And we see these amazing innovations and that Oh my God, I have got this recyclable thing. And we are like, oh, cool, how much is it and they are like, Oh, it is this and you have got to, you have got to buy 200,000 or when I, one of

the people, we were not ever going to be able to do that. So you are almost always is a small brand waiting for that bigger brands to commit to that volume. And then like roll it onto the market, but a lot of the bigger brands like it takes them years to change. And then there is like the people at the bottom trying to drive the change that just can't because they cannot afford to. And so it is this kind of like catch 22 situation all the time, which is so frustrating, I get it from a smaller brand perspective."

Concerning the above response, it is clear that the smaller brands in the cosmetic sector are also taking significant initiatives to enhance sustainability. As noted by the above responses, the companies are partnering with the raw material suppliers for gaining new innovative ideas as to how to improve sustainability through their supply chain. Enterprises both small and large have realised how collaboration is essential for enhancing sustainability in the supply chain. There must be a ban on the microbeads usage. An act was passed in 2015 regarding the Microbeads-Free Waters Act (Gopal and Priya, 2019). It was based on banning the microbeads like an ingredient in the formula. Microbeads refer to the tiny plastic particles which tend to go from the soap that people use in daily life, to the ocean. Microbeads tend to pollute the waters, as well as infect the food chain through the toxins. Microbeads products are currently used though, in 2018, their production was stopped (Gopal and Priya, 2019). If this elimination strategy is adopted, it would be a win-win for the bath products as well as for the ecosystem.

Therefore, the enterprises are collaborating with the suppliers to bring sustainability for improving the initiatives of R&D, optimising costs for the consumer and expanding the business reach. The SMEs, in particular, gain motivation and confidence by analysing the more significant brands commitment towards sustainability. Therefore, the cosmetics SMEs emphasise economic sustainability by emphasising the smart-growth, long-range planning, expenditure on the R&D, cost saving, and conserving resources. Hence, these strategies can be effectively undertaken through partnering with the supplier for improving the economic sustainability. The respondent I10 has further described the economic sustainability outlook of cosmetic SMEs, which is the following:

"Yeah, of course, it costs more to be to think about things from a sustainable point of view, like, even, you know, we have to we have to buy, you know, cushions for like packaging our trade orders, but I did not want to, I did not want to buy the plastic ones. So I actually bought a machine from Germany that makes the compostable potato starch ones. So we have got that now, so we make our own air pillows. We recycle like loads of stuff. It costs more to have like biodegradable poly bags for like sending out to Amazon and stuff than it does to just have plastic ones. It costs money to get audited for carbon. Like it does cost more money to do these things. But I think that it is an investment in the business and I really don't see it as like a hindrance. I just see it as like kind of doing our duty."

As per the response provided above, it is clear that the economic sustainability efforts made by the cosmetic SMEs are highly costly where they are required to make significant investments to ensure that the operations are beneficial for the economy. For instance, it was noted by the respondent that he had purchased a machine from Germany for making air pillows for packaging its trade orders. This particular process enabled the company to reduce its dependence on plastic material and more on potato starch, which was beneficial from economic sustainability as it led to conserving plastic materials. Moreover, the response provided by the participant indicated that the use of potato starch and biodegradable poly bags was considered highly costly. Regardless, the SMEs are required to make investment to the business for being a successful organisation and fulfilling their duty towards sustainability of the economy. In respect to the overall responses provided by the participants, it is clear that the cosmetic SMEs are making significant efforts towards the economic sustainability. There has been a great level of focus on the usage of the renewable energy. The beauty brands are trying to become healthier through the adoption of a more eco-based approach (Leskinen, 2020). Through this, they are not only changing the products but innovating their manufacturing too. The incorporation of the natural ingredients tends to the manufacturing of the products healthier with the sources of the renewable energy by the wind-powered factories.

4.3.5 Theme 5: Social Sustainability Outlook of Cosmetic SMEs

The concept of social sustainability is defined as the least characterised way of assessing different approaches to maintaining sustainability and form sustainable development. It is assessed that social sustainability has received less attention than economic and environmental sustainability, which mainly connects with the social norms being followed by organisations to manage and identify the business impact on workers and employees (Ajmal et al., 2018). In recent years, the growing concept of sustainability is prevalent in the cosmetics sector. The power of consumers has made sustainable development prosper in the sector, which focuses on the environmental aspects and reflects the holistic approach towards economic and social Sustainability (Roca-Puig, 2019). Similarly, in cosmetic SMEs, social sustainability refers to the health, career progression, motivation, freedom, collaborative workplace and well-being of the employees working in the organisation. On this, one of the respondents stated that;

"Sustainability is vital for the life of this planet; then the cosmetic industry has to be Sustainable."

This reflects that sustainability, including economic, social or environmental, is vital for cosmetic SMEs' progress. It is evaluated that social sustainability represents the human side of sustainability, which is essential to respond to the maximum wages, freedom to join an employee union, suitable living conditions, a clear policy for corporate principles, and so on. Moreover, companies in the cosmetic industry are more focused on forming a social sustainability approach to ensure human rights provision and establish care policy for the employees. On this, one of the SMEs' employees provides the response that;

"We have done various collaborations in the first year of our existence, and the first we call them kick back hands, so they kind of have a charitable element to them. So the first one we did was for wild, a wildlife fund in Australia after the bushfires in 2019 - 2020. And that is sort of one charitable element we have done and then we also did, another kickback can fundraise for Darfur. So there was an issue in Darfur around getting soap to two communities that were really isolated during COVID-19, and there was a rule and anxiety around making sure that they had

basic sanitary facilities that would help them prevent them from spreading COVID-19 which we did some fundraising for as well."

From the response as mentioned above, it is analysed that the adoption of social sustainability is significant from a societal point of view, and thus, it is not possible to achieve complete sustainability by large organisations. For instance, countries like Malaysia and EU member nations comprises 99 percent of SME businesses (Ali et al., 2018). However, it is evaluated that sustainability through supply chain management is also crucial for the progress of social outlook in SMEs and forming a positive brand. On this, a cosmetic brand's start-up's CEO highlighted in the interview response that;

"And, you know, where payers have the London living wage, and, you know, we are committed to sort of ensuring that there is a triple bottom line, so to speak for our contribution."

This is further evaluated that social sustainability implementation in SMEs is crucial to responding to employees' needs and effectively enhancing motivation by deploying healthy approaches. On this, respondent of another cosmetic SME tried to fulfil the demand of social cause and charity through the utilisation of their products. It is stated as;

"But I think, well, we tried to weave our shampoos and conditioners, we donate a percentage of our profits to plant trees. Obviously, that does have an impact on the world, which is great. But obviously, it does have an impact on putting giving people jobs in those areas and being able to give them a job in poorer countries where they need to plant trees and stuff."

In line with the above-mentioned response, it is analysed that COVID-19 outbreak is also regarded as major factor that has influenced SMEs to critically assess the need of motivating workers and following equal wage policy to prevent the adverse consequences and provide positive social outcomes. On this, a small cosmetic in London practiced the social responsibility where respondent stated that;

"So the things that we do is really demand transparency from our suppliers to make sure that all of their workers are being paid fairly."

In this regard, the implication of corporate social responsibility is also valued across cosmetics SMEs to enhance awareness concerning the workplace ethics and criteria for setting up employees in a comfortable and suitable workplace environment. This is further evaluated from the small cosmetic start-up founder that;

And they have some corporate social responsibility. So a lot of them have programs if they're outside of the UK, places like India or Africa. They have programs to educate their workers on things like business. They have things like pensions, free holiday, you know, making sure that those workers are really being treated fairly is really, really important to us as well."

During such a crisis period, it is analysed that small and large firms face complexities in retaining employees and maintaining social sustainability in the cosmetics sector. D'Amato et al., (2020) evaluated that support from various stakeholder groups is one of the significant incentives to practice social sustainability. Whereas, many SMEs avoid being more socially sustainable due to higher investment and costs spent on marketing and the employees. For instance, one of the respondents stated that;

"Yeah, it is really difficult, because you do end up paying more, and you do a lot of like, you know, it's not just your product cost. But also, we pay a lot to internal staff and external consultants in order to do a lot of this work. So it is like a big investment for us."

However, many SMEs tried to be competitively different; the Skincare brand, launched 4 years ago, has actively practiced and implemented social sustainability by setting up manufacturing and supply chain. On this, the respondent stated that;

"Our manufacturer has ethical guidelines in place and only work with suppliers that are known and trusted within the industry, who can qualify their ethical trading in terms of human resource, environmental sustainability and care."

Similarly, the company's vision and mission were based on the supply chain and motive to serve the community, reflecting their idea of implementing social sustainability in the cosmetic sector. On this, the Director of Skincare brand stated that;

"Looking after the welfare of the people directly and indirectly within our supply chain and community."

The above-mentioned fact reflects that SMEs operating in cosmetics sector lack enough bargaining power which reflects the importance of solicit support from supply chain partners to implement social sustainability standards.

4.3.6 Theme 6: Measures to cope with sustainability challenges for SMEs of the Cosmetic sector

Major corporations in the cosmetics sector have essentially deployed luxury in-house teams for assuring sustainability, but SMEs lack proper investment, adequate resources and funding, which has led to significant disruptions in maintaining sustainability. Matukevica et al., (2021) elaborated that SMEs face challenges to remain competitive in a constantly evolving marketplace. Sustainability initiatives guarantee the way to maximise energy efficiency and reduce environmental impact to embed in day-to-day operations. However, it is also assessed that many SMEs in the cosmetic sector mainly focused on the implementation of sustainability at 3 M', which refers to the idea of balancing the harmony between social, economic and environmental aspects for measuring the progress and growth of the organisations (Ong and ZienYusoff, 2015). The provision of equal access to resources and opportunities is crucial for SMEs in the cosmetic sector to empower sustainability.

This research discussed the aspects mentioned above in the form of different interviews' responses and perspectives regarding sustainability measures and challenges. On this, one of the responses stated concerning the difficulties and ease of implementing sustainability guidelines;

"Both have their different complexities, i.e. big companies may have more resource but bigger logistics to negotiate, while smaller companies have less resource but are more adaptable and can make quicker changes."

Similarly, another respondent, the director of a new cosmetic start-up, highlighted its vision and mission on sustainability and stated that;

"Well, we are trying to be as sustainable as it is as much as possible. We use glass packaging. We, we are using recyclable packaging. Our business cards are printed on recyclable cotton and recycled t-shirts. We are using vegetable ink. So we kind of looking at different stages. I try to be as sustainable as we can. So at the moment, we will be launching two new products that will come in aluminum tins. So there is going to be zero plastic. So yeah, it is a work in progress."

While some SMEs owners do not know about the importance of sustainability guidelines which reflects significant obstacle in implementing the sustainability principle as the respondents stated that;

"Are there any guidelines for a sustainable process? We know we follow the GMP, good manufacturing practice, obviously, but I am not aware of a sustainable guideline."

However, from the findings of the literature, it is analysed that the SMEs in cosmetic sector is moving towards the rapid integration of sustainability in all three areas for improving longevity and quality of the products. Ali et al., (2018) elaborated that SMEs in cosmetics sector should focus on reviewing sustainability as an opportunity, but not a burden which significantly helps in attracting rapidly growing consumer group that is willing to pay for the sustainable products and services. To cope with the existing challenges, start-ups are encouraging sustainability which is discussed from different perspectives. One of the owners of Indie brands, cosmetic firm in London stated that;

"Become carbon neutral and eventually carbon negative. Become completely plastic-free (we largely are already but it is challenging to find an alternative to lids and pipettes that are entirely plastic-free). Influence our supply chain and industry to engage in Sustainable Swaps, to add up to make a bigger impact."

Moreover, some start-ups considered that communication tools integration and in order to maintain sustainability in transparent way is another critical factor that helps in resolving cost and production challenges (Shamburger, 2021). Further, it is assessed that transparency and effective communication is key to sustainability that ensure consumers the ethical guidelines in the product development and supply process. On this, a respondent stated that;

"I think, you know, communication is so vital within the industry. And I am pleased to see that you know, communication is becoming truthful. So I think you know, truth is a big quality that I how, you know, comes out in cosmetic that we need to have. And that means if you know if there is truth in there be truth in sustainability in product performance in safety standards and in communication as well."

Similarly, it is evaluated from the research that attaining environmental certification for cosmetic start-ups is a significant measure in coping with sustainability challenges. This allows companies to reflect the set of targets and measures defined for curtailing obligations regarding environmental impact (Romero et al., 2018). The point regarding the adoption of environmental certifications was evaluated in the study and obtained different perspectives by the respondents.

"No, not currently. I think, you know, we are too small, honestly. So I mean, we are vegan and cruelty-free, but from a sort of eco-credentials, we just try and you know, our boxes are FSC, we use glass bottles, we are sort of approach is keeping our house in order because we are so small, we take the point of view that if we make changes, however small they are, at whatever point we can, then it adds up to a much bigger picture. So for example, earlier this year, we switched from using the plastic packing tape to the craft paper tape."

Another owner of the cosmetic brand mentioned his viewpoint and explained that;

"Yeah, so we are certified vegan and cruelty-free. We have a bunch of credentials around. So we are palm oil-free, and we have FFC packaging, we have fair trade payment for all of our supply chain as well. We are just about to get B Corp certification. And we are also getting certified carbon neutral from the carbon trust. So those two are in the next couple of months, we will be able to announce those."

Similarly, to cope with sustainability guidelines in social and economic way, companies are turning towards organic products from plants and minerals to replace microplastics in cosmetics (Romero et al., 2018). It is proven as an essential measure that is considered beneficial for SMEs to manage a finite amount of resources adequately, and prevent greenwashing. On this, one of the respondents stated that;

"Yeah, so all of our formulations are 100% natural. I think organic is important because it upholds like really high standards of farming and agriculture. But for us, again, you know, using a lot of like upcycled ingredients, or being, you know, really smart about the kind of plants that we use, the ones that are highly renewable, that do not need a lot of water to grow, is something that is, you know, the forefront of our mind. But yeah, I think it does not always mean just because you're natural, it means that you are sustainable for sure."

This reflects that organic and natural products are significant measures in ensuring sustainability guidelines and an overall eco-friendly workplace environment. Moreover, the effectiveness of social, economic and environmental aspects are found essential for maintaining competitiveness, cost-effectiveness and efficiency across the organisation.

4.3.7 Theme 7: Measures to cope with start-up challenges for SMEs of the Cosmetic sector

Although the industry is extensively growing by adapting the latest trends of the market, start-ups face complexities in digitisation, globalisation, and sustainability to reshape consumer behaviour concerning personal care and cosmetics (Vorster, 2018). To cope with packaging and

waste management issues, adequate packaging, recycling, and green labelling are essential in maintaining a competitive advantage for the start-ups. Different perspectives obtained on this,

"So for us, it is about using a minimal packaging as possible. And even to the extent of, you know, looking at the different sizes of boxes that can be sent for customer orders, I am really winnowing it down to the smallest size, using packaging that can be recycled. And just looking at every step along the way to make it a sort of eco-friendly and light touch as possible. So I think there is always more we can do. And of course, the most sustainable thing we can all do is just stop buying things full stop. But we are social beings. We like to connect, and we like to feel good, and we want to have, you know, happy healthy lives."

Another owner of the start-up highlights that;

"We make good sizes of things. And yeah, it is just really all about, you know, getting results from just the smallest amount of product as well. But it is really difficult, we offer a return scheme for our packaging. So like a refill scheme, which is doing really well. So I think things like that really help with like packaging, and I am kind of avoiding too much going to landfill."

Innovation is also deemed essential for the start-ups to reshape consumer experience and gain competitive advantage through managing digital space and prevent greenwashing (Teng, 2017). It is evaluated that many firms pretend to use wrong products that led to skin cancer and exposure to harmful disease, which reflects consumers turning away from the start-ups, resulting in declined sales. Therefore, the use of organic and natural products is essential, which is evaluated from start-up experience to resolve significant challenges. On the, one of the participants evaluated that,

"And I personally, you know, I am lucky enough to be able to afford to buy organic food and I believe that the quality of organic product, you know, is better than the one the farming using pesticides. So yes, I do think that there is a benefit of using natural and organic ingredients. But I also think that it is not sustainable to have all skincare and cosmetics, and now everyone is switching to natural ingredients because they come from natural sources."

On the other side, the risk regarding legal and financial funding is another obstacle that hinders the start-ups from managing. It is further studied that appropriate legal certification, the implication of corporate social responsibility, implementation of standards and sustainability guidelines are deemed necessary for delivering positive and profitable outcomes for the start-ups (Matukevica et al., 2021). On this, many respondents answered similar statements and highlighted the practices being followed;

"Legally-required cosmetic testing would show a pass or a fail on this. Same with natural products and 'toxicity' – anything is toxic if used in an unsafe way/dosage. Toxic ingredients would not pass legal cosmetic testing. If a product passes legal testing, then it is deemed to be safe."

While, some of the owners are being responsible for eco-friendly practices and stated their vision and mission to prevent challenges in the cosmetics sector by improving the supply chain.

"So we are actually building a proprietary supply chain that absorbs more carbon than it releases. And so our mission is very much centred around reducing our carbon emissions. So from now until 2025, we have pledged to reduce our emissions by 25% year on year, ultimately getting us to the point where we are carbon negative, and this is not through offsetting. This is actually through carbon reduction in our supply chain."

One of the start-up owners also highlighted the effectiveness of digital technologies in empowering sustainability and mitigating manufacturing and production challenges of the brand and state that;

"We are in Europe. But again, it is through the website. So we see Oh, like, wherever it can go to our case, we sold globally through the website, so"

This represents the use of digital technologies to resolve challenges for cosmetics start-ups and fulfil the consumer needs efficiently to achieve sustainable competitive advantage, whilst forming a positive brand image.

4.4 Discussion of Objectives

Objective 1: To identify the challenges that SMEs face in the cosmetic industry regarding sustainability and the challenges that SMEs face at start up from product to supply chain.

Sustainability is a problem worldwide, either global warming or the build-up of unbiodegradable waste such as plastic. The cosmetic industry is trying to minimise its contribution to these effects (Sendawula, Turyakira, and Bananuka 2018). As from the manufacturing to the supply chain process, the cosmetic industry has a significant role to play in the rising environmental problems faced around the globe. The manufacturing process requires vast amounts of power to run high voltage plants so that the product can be produced, the power generation has a sizable amount of contribution to global warming issue as the greenhouse effect is the leading cause of global warming and since 90% of the greenhouse gases present in the atmosphere are methane and CO₂. Power generation plants are the cause for most of the CO₂ emissions around the globe as coal and gas-powered plants burn these fossil fuels to run the generators; hence CO₂ emissions are high leading to environmental issues such as depletion of the ozone layer and air pollution and not to forget the global warming issue which is the worse. These issues are related to the environmental pillar of sustainability while two more pillars affect the cosmetic industry: sustainability's social and economic pillars (Chen and Lee 2010). It is seen that the cosmetic industry conducts operations related to environmental sustainability in order to ensure the environmental factor in order to solve the issues of carbon emission while also being effective for post-consumer use. To ensure the quality and effective pattern of environmental factors, most organisations use recycled and environmentally friendly materials in their production, as well as biodegradable products. Most SMEs use these to create opportunities for reusing products and packaging materials based on the effective recycling properties of the used materials. Further, the use of electric vehicles to transport these finished products can help in reducing CO₂ emissions as traditional diesel engine trucks can contribute quite a lot to the CO₂ emission in the atmosphere leading to the greenhouse effect that is a vital factor of global warming. . Based on the assessment of Turunen

and Halme (2021) it has been assessed that one of the most commonly observed models that can be used by the companies is the triple bottom line model that has a major role in creating value for the society and the environment. Szromek (2021) has also highlighted that the companies can bring about positive changes by implementing the methods of suitable operations that can not only be effective for the companies, but can also bring about positive changes in getting more consumer satisfaction. Based on the assessment of Del Vecchio et al (2021) it has been professed that the use of models for implementing suitability can be effective for the companies for creating better value and determining the means of innovation in the companies. According to Ünal et al (2019) the business model for SME's would be suitable and sustainable is another tool for exploiting the business sustainability that can be effective for bringing innovation and creating the better Lifecycle of the operations to deal with the stakeholders such as the circular economy business model. It can also be used for generating the sustainable environment for the businesses and creating a layer for the protection of the organisational chores and operations based on the findings of the thematic analysis.

According to the research of Turunen and Halme (2021) it has also been assessed that the businesses are growing effectively and has been performing well for enhancing the operations and creating the manageable context within the industry. It has also been assessed that the service industry can also contribute towards the operations that has bridged the gap between the operations and can also help in creating such models that can safeguard the environment and can also create more value for the consumers in this regard as referred to the research of Donner, Gohier and de Vries (2020) and Ünal et al (2019). As professed in the study of Fortunati, Martiniello and Morea (2020), it has also been assessed that the implementation of sustainability business models contributes towards the reduction of waste and also helps in reducing the cost of operations in this regard. The businesses models can be applied in the case of cosmetic industry for bringing diversity and innovation in the companies based on the assessment of Winkler (2021). Similarly, it has also been used for enhancing the means of openness and creating the matching cycles in the operations for dealing with the lack of resources (Yun et al., 2020). These findings have also been supported in the study of Donner,

Gohier and de Vries (2020) and Fortunati, Martiniello and Morea (2020) and has also discussed by the researcher in the interviews.

Plastic waste is another global problem as due to the increasing population; there is not enough space on land to dispose of plastic waste; hence most plastic waste is dumped in oceans. This has a significant effect on marine life as this non-biodegradable waste significantly affects the ecosystem. This waste threatens marine life as many fish and turtles, even birds consume this plastic, thinking that it is food causing the deaths of millions of marine lives around the globe (Moongvicha 2016). In today's cosmetic industry, plastic is the primary raw material used to produce products and packaging. SMEs were using plastics for packaging for two reasons; firstly, it was cheap. Secondly, it was durable. An effective replacement for plastic is not yet introduced by many organisations trying to adopt new, more biodegradable packaging materials the growing concern regarding plastic waste. Since plastic is not easily disposed of and studies show that plastic may take more than a thousand years to decompose completely, new alternatives are necessary to ensure that the earth's environment is safe for every living thing. Further due to the fact that many SMEs are short on funds to implement new and more sustainable approaches into their operations (LamoureuxMovassaghi, and Kasiri 2019). Most SMEs are seen transferring to biodegradable packaging that is made of paper since paper can decompose of in a period of two to six weeks. This is the cheapest and effective manner to deal with the plastic situation around the world. As developing countries, many need to adopt this the most as in these countries there are no effective recycling methods to dispose of these wastes effectively, especially wastes such as plastic as due to it un biodegradable properties it is challenging for developing or underdeveloped countries to recycle or effectively dispose of this waste without harming the environment.

The cosmetics industry faces numerous challenges in order to remain sustainable. The performance of corporate sectors in companies that can be useful in dealing with serious challenges must be improved (Matukevica, Piitulainen and Yassin, 2021). Studies show incorporating appropriate and innovative measures to transform the challenges involved in bringing sustainability to their advantage. New ways for tackling global environmental problems are necessary for a sustainable future. SMEs need to adopt new and effective

business models in order to mitigate the growing environmental problems. One of the modified approaches to dealing with environmental challenges in the cosmetic industry is the use of sustainable and green cosmetics (Das, Rangarajan and Dutta 2019). Sustainable cosmetics are those that are made with natural ingredients derived from renewable resources. Cosmetic companies must incorporate eco-based approaches into their products and manufacturing process to promote sustainability.

Further customer behaviour is also an essential factor to take into account as due to shifts in trends, consumers prefer products that are greener and more sustainable as everyone has the urge to contribute a little towards the environment they prefer to shop and utilise products that are promoting green and sustainable approaches to their products. Since every individual needs cosmetic products to make them look good and elegant, leading brands are trying to make their products more sustainable while SMEs are also trying to coup up with these leading brands by introducing green products that are safe for the environment while providing a revenue for the firm (Maroder and Proietti 2021). Further, SMEs need to promote awareness to their consumers by advertising a green environment on their product's packaging, ensuring that their products are green and not harming the environment in any way.

Objective 2: Challenges that SMEs face in the cosmetic industry with regards to sustainability.

The second objective of this research study was to mention the challenges faced by SMEs in the cosmetic industries and how the companies maintain their sustainability after facing multiple challenges each day. Moreover, all the aspects were mentioned for the reader to get an idea about the SMEs and cosmetic industries. Cosmetic industries contribute to a significant part in the business markets. Customers' perception and satisfaction levels are reflections of the sustainability of a company or industry. Customers are very much concerned with the quality of cosmetic products more than the quantity of a product (Shalehah et al., 2019). Marketing industries have to make changes in their working plans as per the needs and want of the customers'. Sometimes, minor amendments in the workflow or business plans create significant losses or downfall of a company (Chen et al., 2017). The study conducted by

D'Amato et al., 2020, has highlighted the challenges that business organisations face towards sustainability.

One of the main issues in business sustainability is dialogue and cooperation among the operators and the key partners. Moreover, scarcity of resources causes difficulties and hurdles for any company. It can be stated as cosmetic companies have to focus on their packaging and attractive marketing tools. These business companies have to invest much of their money in promotions, advertisements and packaging of products. International markets have huge networking area that helps in maximum engaging population worldwide. Management of small and medium enterprises reflect the viability and growth of a company. Managers face issues in policy making because of the internal and external factors that influence the industries such as pharmaceutical companies, cosmetic industries and biomedical industries, etc. SMEs have fewer contacts and partnership opportunities as compared to the international market. Sustainability among cosmetics industries relies on different parameters such as recycling, packaging, security, and the products' and brands' image. Cosmetic packaging is not environmentally friendly because products are packed in plastic containers and boxes that are not easily degraded. International markets are looking forward to biodegradable packaging materials. These approaches and environmental interventions are difficult to afford by small or medium business companies. Many researchers have explained that it will take a long period of time in introducing effective recycling tools for plastics. This serves as a drawback for cosmetic companies. This has affected the sustainability and image of the products. Low-quality packaging and labelling also impacts in the customers' loyalty and satisfaction levels. In addition, sustainability has vital importance with the life span of the products and their usage. Innovative technological tools are very important for all types of industries because it helps in the growth and development of the business markets. Innovation and critical analysis are two crucial factors for cosmetic industries. Women are more interested and engaged with the cosmetic industries. They pay their more attention to the types of services and facilitates provided by similar industries. These industries have to stay alert and updated so that they can bring innovation and novelty to their services. Workers use innovative marketing tools to grasp the attention of the maximum population through effective marketing. It has been assessed in

the study of Gallo, Antolin-Lopez and Montiel (2018) that the companies face several challenges in regards with the implementation of sustainable business operations in the beauty industry. According to the study of Jin and Shin (2020) it has been assessed that the business models based in sustainability is based on the proactive operations for the creation of monetary and non-monetary value for the companies. It is used for the creation of value for the broad range of stakeholders who are present in the industry for creating the link between the operations and the means of sustainability in the company based on the study of Lüdeke-Freund, Schaltegger and Dembek (2019). In terms of the views provided in the research study by Donner, Gohier and de Vries (2020) has highlighted that the sustainability development in the companies can contribute towards the delivering of social, economic and environmental operations that are there in the companies and combine to create the value for the consumers. It has also been assessed that there are different social dimensions that are needed to be observed by the companies before implementing the sustainability in the businesses as argued in the study of Gallo, Antolin-Lopez and Montiel (2018). The research conducted by Ray and Mondal (2017) has highlighted that the consumers are willing to adopt the products from the brands that are performing according to the ethical and social requirements and are also dealing with the waste properly.

On the other hand, according to the arguments of Donner, Gohier and de Vries (2020) the companies that are not effective in terms of addressing the requirements of environmental safety gain low standards from the consumers and also face challenges in terms of addressing the issues of the environment. One of the most important aspects that is considered by the businesses is the use of biodiversity and the use of biodegradable products that results in low carbon emission and can also be effective in terms of making better interventions for the pollution control as referred to the research of Lüdeke-Freund, Schaltegger and Dembek (2019). It has also been assessed that there are variety of other challenges such as bringing innovation and having value proposition of the company that can contribute towards gaining long term competitive advantage based on the research of Koistinen et al (2018). Similarly, as referred to the responses earned from the interviewees, it has been observed that one of the biggest challenge is to implement the suitable operations of logistics and the supply chain that can be

effectively working in the companies for creating value. Lastly, according to the arguments of Gallo, Antolin-Lopez and Montiel (2018) it has also been assessed that the companies need to create the value with the help of sustainable operations, whereas they face challenges in terms of having the technological aspects and lack of support from the management that can affect the overall business model for sustainability and innovation.

Similarly, in terms of the views provided in the research study which was given by Jernström et al. (2017) has stated that there are few factors that affect the SMEs such as supply chain, collaboration in R&D, and customer value-added. Drivers and stakeholders also influence on the growth and development of business markets. Moreover, SMEs need these factors with the strength to enter the cosmetic market. Socio-economic issues affect the sustainability of a company to a great extent. People are following trends and the phenomenon of word of mouth. Online reviews and customers' perceptions are directly linked with each other these days. Social media has several websites and pages that contain content about the quality of products and services. Fake news and beliefs are also widespread that are associated with brands' images and products. Managers and heads of the marketing departments have to bear such issues that bring everyday challenges.

International and national markets have the collaboration of many different partners and firms. Different people have different mindsets, and managers face issues in adopting strategies due to the difference in opinions among the drivers and the stakeholders. Social stability refers to environmentally friendly approaches and social equity. The needs and wants of the people and their rights are considered on a priority basis. Social stability with respect to the cosmetic industry depends upon ethical and moral values. Cosmetic industries have to launch such products that can fulfil all the ethical concerns and are environmentally friendly. A research study by Formicola (2018) states about the ethical values and their links with the quality of products.

Moreover, this study has explained that the implications of social sustainability in the cosmetic industries are integrated by using raw materials and the products involved in the manufacturing processes. It is a difficult task for each cosmetic company to keep an eye on

each parameter associated with the moral and cultural norms and values. Due to difference of lifestyle and cultural attributes, consumption and manufacturing of products have variation. Eco-friendly and environmentally sustainable products are the step towards the sustainability and growth of an industry and its developments for business expenditures. Good commercialisation and engagement with maximum loyal customers are the most common challenges that an industry face each day. Now, it has been noticed that organic cosmetic products are very much highlighted and are on trending products because of their manufacturing raw materials and natural ingredients. People are so much obsessed with the chemically synthesised products, and it needs much time in coming back to the natural products.

Objective 3: To identify what business model for SME would be suitable and sustainable in the cosmetic industry context.

Another objective of this research study is to give an idea about the business model and its importance in the company's growth and development. There are several attributes that have been discussed in this research study to give detailed information about the relationship between SMEs and their customers. Business models and business plans are very important for each industry. Similarly, marketing mix and 4Ps are also essential components of the marketing mix because they cover important factors such as, price of the products, their promoting strategies and approaches, the marketplace and people whom to be targeted by the companies and industries (Wani, 2013). Industries at both national and international levels, whether they are public sectors or private sectors, depend upon the business plans and business models. The business model of any industry is based on the innovative tools and processes used to attain sustainability and growth (Wirtz, 2011). It usually targets the customers based on companies' performances and goals. Several types of business models are suitable with respect to the business sustainability that are opted by SMEs, such as the One-for-one model, Bundling model, Subscription model and product to a service model, etc. (Giesen et al., 2007). These models aim

to provide the best service quality and sustainable approaches to both the business firms and the customers. The main objective behind these business models is to provide better opportunities to the companies and to ensure quality products to the customers. Many researchers have highlighted the importance of business models that they are very significant for a company to compete in the business markets with similar firms and ensure their customers gain the best products or services (Bocken et al., 2016). Business models are the innovative steps that a company adopts, and it has several steps and procedures that are very crucial and important to be obtained. Another research study that was given by Hennart (2020) have stated about the bundling models and their importance for SMEs. The bundling model describes that SMEs are independent firms, and they organise their mechanisms by controlling their outputs and systems. Business models also focus on the relevant type of customers that are important and associated with the business firms and organisations. BM of cosmetic companies is based on the pattern of several aspects that are key components of their business cycles such as raw materials, population size, packaging and effectiveness of the products with their uniqueness and novelty (Voigt et al., 2017). Customers are the primary and most important components of every business organisations because their satisfaction and perceptions are the reflection of the performances of business companies (Meirovich and Bahnan, 2008). Business models and business plans are made or designed by the management departments, and their effectiveness and analysis are done by the managers. These managers should be trained and qualified enough that they can evaluate the wants and needs of the customers and their feedbacks related to their services and goods.

Moreover, each company has to make several policies and strategies that are important for them to compete in the business markets. The main objective of these business strategies is to introduce the best possible comfort to the customers, so that relationship between the customers and the organisation became strong (Schaltegger et al., 2016). It has been evaluated by many research that low and middle-class customers are more loyal than the upper class customers because of the restricted resources and availability of the services and products. Upper class customers have large variety of services and resources that their desires may change, and they can fluctuate in their perceptions. These customers are very much active in

the society and surrounding world that they follow the trends and other person's perception. These bring difficulties for SMEs to run business models. Sometimes, a single change in the policies can be the result of a great downfall for a business organisation.

According to Geissdoerfer, Vladimirova and Evans (2018) the businesses need to implement the strategies based on sustainability with the help of implementing such plans and creating the opportunities for getting better returns. It has also been assessed that the companies need to understand the business requirements and shall also bring about innovation with the help of developing business initiatives and creating the options for reducing waste in this regard as referred to the study of Caldera, Desha and Dawes (2019). It has also been assessed that the companies have several options and strategies that can be used for having innovation and gaining the strategies for innovation in the company (Bocken, Boons and Baldassarre, 2019). As response by one of the interviewees, the stakeholders are the key participants in the research who can play a major role in designing the opportunities for sustainability in the company based on the assessment of Weissbrod and Bocken (2017). The goals are also needed to be set and shall also be communicated to the stakeholders for bringing better innovation and designing the tools for bringing innovation and sustainability based on the assessment of Ritala et al (2018) and Fleming et al (2017).

On the other hand, according to the research of Oderanti and Li (2018) it has also been observed that the companies can opt for the businesses tools that can be used for designing innovation and showing better responses towards achieving sustainability. It is imperative to bring about the methods of innovations and create the methods of environmental justice that can be used for showing more efforts towards the innovation and creating the means of sustainable development in the companies as referred to the study of Ritala et al (2018). The researcher has achieved the objectives and has gathered the data from the respondents where it has been assessed that the means of innovation can be achieved with the help of integrated assessment of the models of sustainability that can be used for bringing success and creating the methods of environmental justice within the business community. These aspects has also been supported in the study of Caldera, Desha and Dawes (2019) that has provided with the assessment that the use of the methods of environmental evaluation can be categorised as the

most effective methods for gaining the tools for sustainability and innovation in the company. Hence, it has been assessed that the use of these tools can be used effectively by the companies for bringing innovation and creating the methods of better risk assessment in this regard.

Another research study has mentioned that the cosmetic industry chooses customers segments on the basis of the available resources (Haddara et al., 2020). If a company decides to target several groups or classes of customers, they have to take variety of approaches and innovative strategies. There are two primary factors such as customers' perception and customers' preferences. Business plans are designed by keeping these two things in consideration. Companies launch such products suitable for the customers' age groups, preferences, needs and want, etc. The value proposition is referred to as the suitable services and products launched by the cosmetic companies to create customer segment values. Another research that has been given by Bocken et al. (2013) has illustrated that excellent business plans and models are very difficult to be made because of the variation in the thoughts of the workers and the employees. National or international firms have linked with many other departments and firms that belong to different societies and cultures. Sometimes, it gets challenging to fix one focal point or select the best option among the thousands of ideas and new plans. These ideas and thoughts are the reflections of different mindsets and cultural and traditional norms. There are several networking sites that work to facilitate customers online. These days, customers are very much interested in online purchasing of goods rather than physical shopping because it saves time and money. Many cosmetic industries are facilitating at the doorsteps so that they can gain many customers' values their money. Many beauty industries are facilitating at the door steps so that they can gain much customers' values. It has been assessed that there is a variety of methods that can be used by the companies for solving the challenges and creating the methods of innovation with the businesses. It has been assessed in the study of Inigo, Albareda and Ritala (2017) that the tools can be used for dealing with the challenges and opting for the suitable means of innovation in the companies. It has been assessed that the tools can be used for reducing the overall cost of operations and can also be treated for dealing with the business challenges in this regard based on the assessment

of Geissdoerfer, Vladimirova and Evans (2018). The researcher has found that the tools can bring better opportunities for the general public for creating the likelihood for the consumers and creating the methods of better environmental assets in this regard as referred to the study of Foss and Saebi (2018). It has also been assessed that the companies that adhere to the requirements of sustainability can be used for bringing the plans to life for the future based on the research of Wirtz and Daiser (2017). It has also been assessed that the means of innovation can also be categorised for dealing with the better environment and getting more benefits for the environmental success in this regard. The implementation of these business strategies and models create the opportunities for reduced cost that can also be used for research and development for bringing innovation and leading towards better means of business solutions that can be effective for the environment based on the research of Geissdoerfer, Vladimirova and Evans (2018) and Inigo, Albareda and Ritala (2017). These findings are also supported in the study of Pieroni, McAloone and Pigosso (2019) that has provided with the assessment about the implications of sustainability that can be used for innovation in this regard. Hence, it has been assessed that the implementation of these programs can be used for getting the likelihood and gaining more profitability in this regard.

4.5 Chapter summary

The researcher has evaluated the implications of sustainable business practices that can be used by the companies for bringing innovation and solving the challenges in the businesses. It has been assessed that the means of sustainability is based on different factors that can contribute towards the strategies and culture for bringing innovation in the businesses. It has been summarised that the use of models for implementing suitability can be effective for the companies for creating better value and determining the means of innovation in the companies. The business models can be used for gaining the better strategies and means of innovation that can bring successful changes in the businesses and can also be used for creating profitability in the company. Similarly, there are different social dimensions that are needed to be observed by the companies before implementing the sustainability in the businesses. Therefore, the companies can bring success and can also create the opportunities for success in

this regard. It has also been concluded that the stakeholders are the key participants in the research who can play a major role in designing the opportunities for sustainability in the company. Hence, these stakeholders are imperative for creating the opportunities for success and can also help in bringing success for the company.

CHAPTER 5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

The following is the last chapter of this study, and this chapter aims to give appropriate conclusions for this study and the recommendations and implications. The chapter provides an overall recap of the whole study and aims to conclude the study on a positive note by providing an excellent and effective conclusion for the research. The first section of this study summarises the key findings of the study. All the necessary and essential findings from the study are described briefly in this section. Further, the recommendations for future researchers are provided in the next section. Followed next is the implications of the study are defined. The following section consists of the limitations faced by conducting this study and future directions for studies that may be carried on related topics as this one. The last section provides a suitable conclusion for the study.

5.2 Discussion of key finding

This section summarises the findings around sustainability, circularity and business model innovation in the cosmetic industry through the process of analysis in the last chapter and The literature review.

5.2.1 Challenges

The research has addressed the research question 1: *What are the challenges that SMEs in the cosmetic industry face from product to supply chain?*

It has been evident through the literature the overall challenges experienced by SME's from the initial level. The main concern of any business now is the plastic waste disposing system. It's empirical through the data in chapter 2, the companies are trying their best to reduce the use of plastic from the initial stages off the product packaging to helping out the consumers in making the choices to recycle it at the end stage. it is also evident from the analysis the struggle companies face while choosing the packaging of their products due to the reason that firstly plastic in packaging is convenient and and secondly even though there is

innovation, the economic factors play a huge role in the decision of replacing plastic with other materials. On the other hand, it is also sing through the analysis of the interviews done, that there are few components in the packaging that do not have any replacement other than the plastic components.

The challenges start from initial stages of choosing raw materials, as it needs to be ensured that is sources are sustainable as it indicates the primary step to ensure quality of the product. Although there are raw materials available which are sustainable, it leads to a grave economical challenge as they are marked at a higher price than the others due to the shortage. The analysis of the interview shows that the economic factor to be the greatest challenge for all. From procuring to organic raw materials or recycled packaging, using carbon neutral packaging and distribution channels, the economical expect of the business gets affected but there is a drive for the smaller companies that's still chosen to be sustainable at the end of the day. Even though these companies are sustainable, for it to be easily marketed towards its customers sustainable certification helps a lot. These certificates help consumers identify and choose easily the products they want to invest in. But the sustainability certifications are expensive and not the first thing that small businesses want to invest in.

Choosing the right suppliers it's crucial in the early stages, as to be transparent and overall sustainable the raw materials for the product should come from the suppliers that understand the need on the betterment of the industry. Not to mention the cost and the order quantities which makes it much more harder for the in small businesses to invest into innovative products which are sustainable.

In the past years, COVID was another challenge that played major role and impacted lots of small businesses. There had been both positive and negative affect depending on the steps taken by individual companies towards lockdown and increased online activity. Few companies went 200% online and closed their physical retail business to handle this significant challenge to the sales. COVID-19 brought huge changes to the industry; it changed the consumer habits who were encouraged to buy products from physical demonstration to buying it online. Where makeup and cosmetics was declining in the sales, on the other hand the skin care market was

booming as well as the companies were launching antibacterial products. The consumer perception of skincare and makeup has change, which has changed their buying concept, leading way to new marketing strategies in the pandemic like situations. So it led to decrease in the availability of supplies.

The biggest challenge faced by the cosmetic industry at this stage is the transparency. From smaller to larger businesses, due to the various steps and raw material involved in making of a single product, it becomes difficult to track down to the lowest level. Companies like Beiersdorf are aiming to be more transparent in the procurement of their ingredients used in the Nivea products. But transparency is not only related to words the formulation of the products or packaging but also the measures an initiative taken by the company to do so.

5.2.2 Sustainability in Cosmetic Industry and SME's

The research has addressed the research question 2: *What does economic, social, and environmental sustainability mean to SMEs in the cosmetic industry?*

Sustainability as a concept is seen for a long time now in the cosmetic industry specially in the larger co-operations. The literature based on the sustainability reports of these mega business show the work done in this field and the future plans too. The five-year or ten-year plans of these organisations cover from social to environmental aspects of the sustainability. These companies are using attractive marketing strategies and have separate research and development department investigating into new innovations regarding the product packaging and distribution channels. To partake in the social issues, where is companies growing awareness in consumers regarding the steps taken like inclusivity and fair wage. also millions go into charity work across the globe to help out the social issues call mom plus awareness towards the current situations like black lives matter, women's economic development, climate agreements, education and other issues that are highlighted in the United Nations as SDGs.

Similarly in the small businesses as well, these issues are highlighted but at a lower level but it does not make them any smaller in their act towards the SDGs. There are examples of

smaller companies taking social initiatives like on purchase of a product planting a new tree, fair wages across the company and gender equality. it is great to see the evidence presented in the analysis on how the UN sustainability development goals influence not only the bigger companies but also small and medium size companies in the cosmetic industry. It is visible from smaller to larger companies the idea of circularity in life cycle thinking from the beginning to the finish of the product life cycle.

5.3.3 Sustainable Business Model

The research has addressed the research question 3: *How can these challenges be faced while integrating sustainable practices in the business model?*

Sustainable approaches can be found in the strategies, visions, and self-concepts of proactive case organisations. Several of the cases perceived themselves as sustainable organizations that strive to do all their business in a sustainable manner. In other cases, sustainability considerations were also incorporated into the corporate or business strategy and implementation indicators were developed. The business model innovation activities based on these indicators aim to translate their sustainability objectives into the prioritization and product lifecycle management processes. While other organizations prioritize specific sustainability strategies, such as reducing resource consumption, becoming climate neutral, or acting as a good neighbour, and integrate them into their business model development activities; these can be done by holding dedicated workshops.

Figure 9: Business Model with Life Cycle Approach

Sustainability at an overall level is very important at this time and moment. The above figure shows the life cycle approach towards the circular business model taking into correspondence the initial stage of procuring raw materials, to its use by consumers and ending up in a landfill or getting recycled. Starting on from procuring the raw materials, companies have to decide on a supplier that understands the company sustainable policies and are sustainable in their own way. The raw materials either natural or chemical, its affect at the end of its cycle should be taken into account. For example natural ingredients that are biodegradable and the end of their life cycle. The man made or chemical ingredients which do not have an adverse effect on the life cycle of other animals or plants. The raw materials can also be procured through other industries also known as the upcycled ingredients.

Most of the companies will need a production site where they can combine all these raw materials and develop a sustainable product. It should be taken into account the sustainability guidelines of these companies like their CO2 emission, the packaging used during transportation and their social construct. Similarly, as it was evident from the literature the most waste is generated because of packaging off the product and not the product itself. It is of grave importance to use packaging which is recyclable, decomposable or reusable. There are packaging solutions like aluminium and glass which are easier to recycle and be used as packaging materials for other products in any other industry. Similarly the distribution channels should be set up in a way to carbon emission levels are lower. The distribution channel takes into account the journey from raw materials to the production line, to the packaging and finally being distributed to the warehouses or retail stores for the consumers.

It was seen in the analysis of the data that consumers are enlightened about the life cycle of these products and also the companies are advising consumers to choose better. As it is the responsibility of the consumer after the purchase made that how the product and its packaging is disposed. Well most of the packaging could be recycled to use as more packaging call some will end up into landfill. To make this life cycle approach to work with zero impact the packaging in the landfill needs to be biodegradable to cause the least affect on the soil and earth.

5.3 Summary of Findings

Sustainability has become a serious concern across the world, and the global businesses and companies play a significant role in the sustainability of the environment. Companies operating in the cosmetic industry also play a significant role in maintaining the sustainability of the environment because the manufacturing and supply chain process of the cosmetic industry contain practices that can either improve the sustainability of the environment or it can also destroy the sustainability of the environment. The cosmetic companies which produce sustainable products and use recyclable packaging for their products improve the sustainability of the environment. On the other hand, the cosmetic companies which produce the standard

products and use plastic material in their products and packaging of products destroy the sustainability of the environment. In this research study, the sustainable business models of small-medium enterprises were discussed, particularly of the businesses in the cosmetic industry. The data was collected through a qualitative research design; hence, the thematic analysis method was used in order to analyse the collected data. There was a total of 6 different themes identified and discussed in the research study. Firstly, the challenges which are faced by small and medium enterprises in the cosmetic industry for obtaining sustainability were identified, where it was observed that since the companies in cosmetic industries do not have many resources or since they are small or medium scale industries, hence, it becomes challenging for these companies operating in the cosmetic industry to obtain a sustainable certificate.

Moreover, it was also identified from the research study that sustainable products are more expensive as compared to the standard cosmetic products. Therefore, producing sustainable products increase the cost of the company, and as a result, the sales of the company declined due to high prices. Hence, it becomes difficult for small and medium enterprises to obtain sustainable products.

Moving forward, it was observed that the suppliers and partners also become a challenge for small and medium enterprises in the cosmetic industry, starting from the production process to the supply chain process. These challenges can be complex; however, if the proper techniques are followed, then these challenges can be tackled. It is evident that the suppliers provide the raw materials to the companies for the cosmetic products. Hence the quality control of the raw material and the cost of the raw material is dependent on the supplier, which gives the supplier strong power in this industry. Hence, the suppliers can be a challenge for small and medium enterprises in obtaining sustainability in their production processes and selling sustainable products.

Moreover, recyclable and sustainable products can be complicated to find, and it can be very costly for the companies operating in the cosmetic industry. Not only the products can be sustainable, or they can bring challenges. Instead, the cosmetic product packaging can also be

sustainable by using the recyclable packaging rather than using the glass products for packaging, which means the cost of packaging of cosmetic products can also be challenging factor while obtaining sustainability in the cosmetic industry for small and medium enterprises.

The manufacturing process of companies operating in cosmetic industries requires a high amount of power usage in order to run the power plants which can convert their raw material into finished products; the power plants that use a high amount of power are not sustainable for the environment. Instead, they harm the environment because the high usage of power results in air pollution, and as a result, the global warming effect is also increased. Moreover, these power plants become the cause for a majority percentage of CO₂ emissions across the world since the gas power plants and coal power plants usually burn fossil fuels in order to run the generators smoothly. As a result, the CO₂ emission increases, leading to the weakening of the ozone layer, increase in air pollution, and increased global warming by a significant percentage. These discussed issues are concerned with the effects of the mentioned practices on the environment; however, there were also some issues identified which can affect the cosmetic industry. It was observed in the study that companies operating in cosmetic industry now ensure that they follow practices which are consistent with the environment of the world. To ensure the quality and effective pattern of environmental factors, most organisations use recycled and environmentally friendly materials in their production, as well as biodegradable products. Most SMEs use these to create opportunities for reusing products and packaging materials based on the effective recycling properties of the used materials. Lastly, it was observed that small and medium enterprises need to promote awareness to their consumers by advertising green environment on their product's packaging ensuring that their products are green and are not harming the environment in any way.

5.4 Recommendation

In this research study, multiple challenges were identified which are faced by the small and medium enterprises in the cosmetic industry. However, there are some techniques or methods which can be followed by the companies operating in small and medium enterprises

in order to tackle these challenges. It was identified that the suppliers could become a significant challenge for SMEs in the cosmetic industry since they control the quality, and the cost of the raw material and finished products is mainly dependent on the quality of raw material which was put into the process. This challenge can be tackled by finding as many suppliers as possible because when there are more and more alternatives available to the company, it will result in less power or control of the supplier over the cost and quality. Moreover, the other challenges were the high cost of sustainable products; this problem can be tackled by using recyclable products, which the company can reuse. In this way, the companies will be able to use an expensive product multiple times, and as a result, the cost of the sustainable product will not impact much to the company. The companies can use this life cycle approach taking into account each and every step of the business model and trying to make it as sustainable as possible. It is difficult to be overall sustainable but it is the effort that matters. The circular business model with the life cycle approach and innovation can help guide the companies towards a more sustainable outlook. It can be helpful for the people who are just starting up companies and also to who already have a business model and can use this to do my each part of the business and make it sustainable one at a time.

5.5 Limitations and Future Directions

The study faced quite a few limitations during its course; time was the main factor when researching as due to lack of time, it is believed that sufficient data was not gathered to support the research argument further in the literature review process data was gathered from previous research and studies. Since many of these studies were in the form of books, journals and articles, they were not readily available for use. Many of such studies were paid to access or ultimately had their access locked, leading to insufficient data to support the research aims and objectives. Further interviews were conducted for the study since time was an issue not all participants were approached in time, leaving with a low sample size for the study. These were the few limitations faced during the course of this study.

For a sustainable future, new methods and approaches are necessary to ensure that the coming future is safe and healthy for new generations. Hence the study indicates that researchers must conduct studies to improve the state of the earth. It is the responsibility of every industry worldwide, either cosmetic, construction, or any other industry that has some kind of negative impact on the environment, to find new ways to operate with sustainability the primary objective. New studies must be conducted to introduce new methods to reduce CO2 emissions and to dispose of plastic waste effectively. Since plastic is hard to decompose, new and greener recycling methods need to be adopted by industries to ensure for a more sustainable future.

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APPENDIX A

Participant Information Sheet

Sustainable business model for SME's in the Cosmetic Industry

You are being invited to take part in a research study. Before you decide, it is important for you to understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Please ask me if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part.

What is the purpose of this study?

The two main objectives of this research are:

- To develop tools and identify challenges that sustainable business model faces in the cosmetic industry.
- To identify which business model would be suitable and sustainable in context to SME' in the cosmetic industry.

Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen to take part in this study because you are part of the Cosmetic industry and your participation in research is valuable to us.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you do decide to take part, you will be given this information sheet to keep and be asked to sign a consent form. If you decide to take part, you are still free to withdraw at any time without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

This will be a detailed interview related to the sustainable aspect of your business. The researcher will broadly discuss environmental, social, and economical sustainability as part of your business.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

We believe that the risks are minimal. We understand that there are many demands on your time and there is some inconvenience in taking part in the interview. You are free at any stage to withdraw from the interview or take time out if you wish.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Whilst there are no immediate benefits for those people participating in the project, it is hoped that this work

will have a beneficial impact on how sustainable practices can be implemented in existing business models. Results will be shared with participants to inform their professional work.

Data Protection Privacy Notice

The data controller for this project will be the University of the West of Scotland (UWS). The UWS Data Protection Office provides oversight of UWS activities involving the processing of personal data and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. UWS's Data Protection Officer is Emma Cockrow and can be contacted at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk.

Your personal data will be anonymised. If you are concerned about how your personal data is being processed, please contact UWS in the first instance at dataprotection@uws.ac.uk. If you remain unsatisfied, you may wish to contact the Information Commissioner's Office (ICO). Contact details, and details of data subject rights, are available on the ICO website at: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/data-protection-reform/overview-of-the-gdpr/individuals-rights/>

What will happen to the results of the research study?

Results of the research will be published. You will not be identified in any report or publication. Your institution will not be identified in any report or publication. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please ask us to put you on our circulation list.

Who has reviewed the study?

ESS Ethics Committee

Contact for further information

If you require any further information, please contact:

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SE1 6NP

UK

[REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

Thank you for taking part in this study.

APPENDIX B

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Title of Project: Sustainable business model for SME's in the Cosmetic Industry

[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]
[REDACTED]

Personal details withheld.

You have been invited to take part in a study to develop a sustainable business model for SME's in the cosmetic industry. The aim of this study is to identify what business model would be suitable and sustainable in context to SME's in the cosmetic industry and to develop tools and identify challenges that sustainable business model faces in the cosmetic industry. By completing this form and agreeing to give your full consent, you agree that you have read and understood the participant information and understand what is being asked of you in this study.

Please read the following statements and, if you agree, initial the corresponding box to confirm your agreement:

	Initial below:
I confirm that I have read and understand the participant information sheet and instruction sheet for the study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.	
I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time up to one month after completing the study without giving any reason.	
I understand that the information I give is confidential and any publication resulting from this work will not identify me personally.	
I consent to the processing of my personal information (<i>age, sex, and contact details</i>) for the purposes explained to me. I understand that such information will be handled in accordance with all applicable data protection legislation.	
I agree to have my voice/likeness digitally recorded.	
I freely agree to participate in this study.	

Signatures:

Name of participant (block capitals):

Name of researcher (block capitals):

Date:

Date:

Signature:

Signature:

PALAK SHARMA

APPENDIX C

INTERVIEW QUESTIONNAIRE

ABOUT THE EMPLOYEE

Name:

Position in the company:

How long have you been working in the company?

Which are your core products?

ABOUT THE COMPANY

1.What does your company stand for in its mission and vision for the future regarding sustainability?

2.What are your views on the company's sustainable policies?

3.Does the company have any sustainable certification (private or government)? What are they?

PRODUCTION / MANUFACTURING

4.Do you manufacture your own products or outsource it? Would you consider making in house?

5.Are there any challenges faced at production level and how do you overcome them?

6.How is it made sure that the production process is sustainable? What are key aspects or guidelines to follow?

7.Which guidelines doe the manufacturing companies follows if product is outsourced?

8.Is it important for the raw materials to be organic in nature and why?

9.Can customer track the product line till the root level? Comment on the transparency of the production process

10.How is the packaging sustainable? Does packaging manufacturing companies follow same sustainability rules a well?

11.What are the competent products or companies? Reason behind their selection.

SUSTAINABILITY

12. Was the sustainability aspect built from the beginning or implemented at later stage? Why was either preferred to be done at early or later stage of business?

13. What were the challenges faced during the process of building or converting into a sustainable business?

What drives the environmental sustainability in your company?

Safety to use natural or organic products regarding toxicity, allergy problems or use of natural preservatives or is it true that preservative free is much safe?

Cosmetics using biodegradable waste of agro-industries such as coffee grounds, green coffee oil from defective beans; coffee silverskin generated during roasting coffee; Use of those by-products like cocoa pods during cocoa plantation which if discarded causes black pod disease.

14. Does your company use upcycle products?

15. Which is the main product which is loved by the customer due to reasons purely based on the quality of ingredients?

16. What aspects are under environmental sustainability are followed by the company?

17. What were the challenges faced to implement guidelines to create a product which is environmentally sustainable?

What drives the social sustainability in your company?

18. What is the company's viewpoint on social sustainability during production process? Like Does company where product manufactured has fair wage system?

19. How does your organization work towards the welfare and satisfaction of its workers?

20. What does social sustainability mean to the company?

What drives the economical sustainability in your company?

21. If you decided to incorporate sustainability at later stage, what were the effects of that decision on the economic sustainability?

22. Was there any effect on economic sustainability due to changes in the environmental or social sustainability?

23. What does economic sustainability mean to the company?

DISTRIBUTION AND SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION

24. How is the distribution process made sustainable, whether its online or retail business?

25. How do you motivate your customers to follow sustainable process even after buying the products? Believing and accepting the continuous process of sustainability. For example, Lush gives free product on returning the packaging.

26. Does the size of the company make it easier or difficult to follow sustainability guidelines?

27. What are the company's plan for future with respect to sustainability?

APPENDIX D

Brand selection questionnaire

Company Information

The following questionnaire is regarding basic company information. You are invited to participate in a research project regarding sustainable practices in the cosmetic industry.

1. Company Name

2. How many employees are working under the company?
 - Less than 50
 - Less than 250 but more than 50
 - More than 250
3. Where are the company headquarters?

4. Which are the main continents or countries the customers from?

5. Is the business online or through retail outlets or both?
 - Online only
 - Retail store only
 - Both

6. What are the main products?
 - Personal Care
 - Fragrances
 - Makeup Cosmetic
 - Bath and Body
 - All of the above

7. Do you manufacture your own products or outsource it?
 - Manufacture in house
 - Outsource
 - Partially both
8. How would you rate sustainable practices in your production process, 10 being fully

sustainable.

9. Is packaging sustainable?

- Yes
- No

10. Was the sustainability aspect built from the beginning or implemented at a later stage?

- From beginning
- Added at a later stage

11. Is it possible for the customers to track the product line to the root level?

- Yes
- No

12. What changes would most improve competing products currently available from other companies?

13. Which aspect of sustainability is considered most challenging to implement?

- Environmental Sustainability
- Economic Sustainability
- Social Sustainability

14. How well does the website communicate your company's sustainability practices?

- Extremely well
- Very well
- Moderately well
- Slightly well
- Not at all

15. How much have sustainable practices changed in the last 5 years?

APPENDIX E

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals as mentioned in the Sustainability Reports of 20 selected MNCs

COMPANY	SDG 1	SDG 2	SDG 3	SDG 4	SDG 5	SDG 6	SDG 7	SDG 8	SDG 9	SDG 10	SDG 11	SDG 12	SDG 13	SDG 14	SDG 15	SDG 16	SDG 17
Loreal	Dark Green																
Unilever	Dark Blue																
Estee Lauder			Yellow														
P&G			Yellow	Orange	Orange												
Shiseido			Green	Green	Green												
Natura			Light Blue	Light Blue	Light Blue												
Coty						Yellow											
Johnson & Johnson			Red														
Amorepacific			Grey														
LVMH Guerlain	Blue																
Beiersdorf	Light Green																
Go	Yellow																
LBrands																	
Avon			Light Blue														
Henkel																	
Colgate	Yellow																
Chanel																	
Kose																	
Pierre Fabre			Light Green														
Groupe Rocher			Dark Blue														

APPENDIX F

Word	Count	Similar Words
products'	4194	product, production, productive, productivity, products, products', products'
sustained	3476	sustain, sustainability, sustainability#, sustainability#master, sustainable, sustainably, sustained, sustaining, sustains
report	3006	report, report', reportable, reported, reporting, reporting', reports
company	2891	companies, companies', company, company''
business'	2499	business, 'business, business', businesses
packaging	1446	packag, package, packaged, packages, packaging
consuming	1429	consum, consumables, consume, consumed, consumer, consumers, consumers', consumes, consuming
water	1428	water, watering, waters
suppliers	1321	supplier, suppliers, suppliers'
brands'	1295	brand, branded, branding, brands, brands', brands''
peoples	1279	people, peoples, peoples'
financial	1277	financial, financially, financiers
environmental	1274	environmental, environmentalism, environmentally
relations	1255	relat, relate, related, relates, relating, relation, relational, relations, relations', relative, relatively, relatives
cosmetic	1207	beautiful, beautiful', beautifully, cosmetic
socially	1202	social, sociale, sociales, socialize, socially

APPENDIX G

Name	Description	Files	References
Carbon Emission	Initiatives taken towards the goal of zero carbon emission by 2030	22	35
Circular Economy	Following the rules of circularity and collaborations with the Ellen McArthur Foundation	20	27
Economic Sustainability	The economic dimension of sustainability	22	28
Environmental Sustainability	The environmental dimension of sustainability	22	168
Innovation	Work done in the sector of product and technological innovation	22	39
Plastic	Updates on the amount of plastic packaging used	21	28
Recycle	Work done or future plans regarding recycling of packaging	21	45
Social Sustainability	The social dimension of sustainability	22	67
Sustainability	Overall sustainability and company mission and vision	22	215
Transparency	Transparency with the ingredient and across the supply chain	19	43

APPENDIX H

Interviewee List

I: Interviewee

Interviewee	Sector	Position
I1	Skin Care	CEO, Founder
I2	Skin Care	CEO, Founder
I3	Haircare	CEO, Founder
I4	Skin Care	CEO, Founder
I5	Skin Care	CEO, Founder
I6	Skin Care	CEO, Founder
I7	Haircare	CEO, Founder
I8	Makeup	CEO, Founder
I9	Haircare	CEO, Founder
I10	Skin Care	CEO, Founder
I11	Makeup	CEO, Founder
I12	Haircare	CEO, Founder
I13	Skin Care	CEO, Founder
I14	Fragrance	CEO, Founder
I15	Cosmetic	CEO, Founder
I16	Cosmetic consultancy	CEO
I17	Cosmetic consultancy	CEO, Founder
I18	Cosmetic	Founder
I19	Cosmetic	CEO, Founder
I20	Skin care	CEO, Founder

APPENDIX I

List of Sustainable Certifications

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